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Characterisation of Inland and Coastal Waters with Space Sensors

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Authors:

Dominique Durand, Dmitry Pozdnyakov, Stein Sandven, François Cauneau, Lucien Wald, Anita Jacob, Kjell Kloster and Martin Miles

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<p>Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center (NERSC)</p> <p>Edv. Griegsvei 3a N-5037 Solheimsviken, Norway Phone: +47 55 29 72 88 Fax: +47 55 20 00 50 E-mail: dominique.durand@nrsc.no Web-site: http://www.nrsc.no</p>	<p>ARMINES Ecole des Mines de Paris / Groupe Teledetection & Modelisation (EMP) Rue Claude Daunesse Po. Box 207 F-06904 Sophia Antipolis, France Phone: +33 (0)4 93 95 74 60 Fax: +33 (0)4 93 95 75 35 E-mail: cauneau@cenerg.cma.fr</p>
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<p>INVESTIGATORS</p> <p>Dominique Durand, NERSC Stein Sandven, NERSC Dmitry Pozdnyakov, NIERSC Franois Cauneau, EMP Lucien Wald, EMP Martin Miles, NERSC Kjell Kloster, NERSC Anita Jacob, NERSC</p>	<p>REVIEWERS</p> <p>Luigi Alberotanza, CNR/ISGDM, Italy Annick Bricaud, LPCM, France Niamh Connolly, Univ. Cork, Ireland Roland Doerffer, GKSS, Germany Sam Ekstrand, IVL, Sweden Ulrich Horstmann, Kiel Univ., Germany Ian Robinson, SOC, UK Michael Schaepman, RSL, Switzerland</p>	<p>AUTHORISATION</p> <p>Bergen, February, 1999</p> <p>DIRECTOR</p> <p>Ola M. Johannessen</p>

Executive Summary

The overall objective of the study is to document the present capabilities of Earth observation (EO) for quantitative estimate of geophysical parameters related to inland and coastal “water quality”. Further to investigate the improvements that can be expected with the new generation of EO sensors, and to give a prospective view of what could be achieved in the longer term with optimised satellite instruments. The project has involved a review of user requirements, an extensive literature review concerning space remote sensing techniques and algorithms, an explicit comparison of the EO capability with the identified-application requirements.

The study consists of four major parts: 1) an introductory part that is a compilation of definition and clarification of terms and concepts used in the rest of the report, as well as the presentation of general information concerning the characterisation of inland and coastal waters, and the current use of EO data; 2) a review of user requirements for Earth observation from a number of sources including reference documents for EU policies, CEO’s customer segment workshops, EU funded R&D projects and space agencies’ projects. Based on these findings, a list of quantitative requirements for sixteen EO derivable geophysical parameters and for six application areas are drawn up; 3) A technical part that describes and evaluates operational and in-development EO algorithms for deriving those geophysical parameters that have been identified in the user requirement review. Based on this evaluation, an explicit comparison between EO capability and user requirements is presented; 4) A prospective view on future capabilities of EO, provided that application-optimised sensors become available.

The customer segment investigation shows that there are many different user-groups who can benefit from using information from a few key satellites, e.g., SPOT, Landsat, NOAA, and ocean colour sensors to some extent. The main result of the survey is that there is a limited number of specific requirements to the quantitative measurements that EO data can presently provide. It appears that EO data can contribute with information within many applications, but use of EO data to extract useful parameters can only be done for about 15 to 20 parameters relevant for observation of “water quality”.

From a technical point-of-view, most of the algorithms making use of EO data are based on empirical models that are not directly applicable to coastal and inland waters in general. Moreover these types of algorithms are hardly applicable to regions with lack of *in situ* data. Hence it is difficult to predict the accuracy that could be achieved in specific regions. Most applications that relate to inland and coastal waters require spatial resolution of about 100 m or better. This accuracy is not met with present sensors, since they are not dedicated to operational issues and local investigations. However remote sensing has already a valuable and recognised role in defining baseline conditions. For example the impact of natural disasters can be evaluated against these conditions, even if remote sensing cannot play a very helpful operational (real-time) role during the evolution of a disaster.

During the next decade, several sensors will be launched, which should partly overcome the current limitations of EO sensors. Hyperspectral sensors, very high resolution instruments, multi-satellite constellation and application-dedicated micro-satellites are foreseen to improve drastically the capability of remote sensing for serving operational monitoring of inland and coastal waters. Associated with these new technologies, improved algorithms and new methods are being developed. Their potentials for operational uses remain to be documented and demonstrated.

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PART I. INTRODUCTORY PART

I.1 Objectives and context of the study

The *overall* objective of this report is to present the capabilities of **space sensors** to provide environmental parameters relevant for **monitoring “quality” of coastal and inland waters**, and to assess improvements that can be expected from **future spaceborne sensors** and other advancements.

Nowadays, “water quality” is undoubtedly a subject of concern for politics, environment agencies, chemical industry, planners, and to the general public as well, because of its potential impact on human health, environment and quality of life.

Operational monitoring of water quality is performed at national level in almost all industrialised countries, although most of third countries have more recently started local programs to deal with this issue. International concerted actions and agreements/treaties are in progress, especially in Europe, to harmonise the techniques and methods of sampling and measurement of a number of key-parameters of crucial importance for an efficient monitoring of water quality at regional level.

During the last decade, “Earth observation industry” has exploded: an average of twenty new EO sensors are yearly launched worldwide, the former research-limited user community has been joined by operational users who want to exploit this source of information to improve their services, the limited access to EO data has been turned into a market place.

However, a gap still exists between operational users who required usable information, conformed to their tasks and “enablers” (value-added industry) who are in charge of receiving, processing and distributing EO data and derived information. This knowledge gap is described as: “on one side are the scientists and engineers who know how to measure variables in the Earth system from space, but have little, if any idea, of what the real information requirements of operational users with economic, social, strategic, political or environmental objectives may be, and on the other side are the operational users (information consumers), each of whom expresses their information requirements in different ways using the jargon of their particular discipline, and has little, if any, knowledge of what can be done to deliver information from spaceborne platforms, how it can benefit from them or what it is worth”, McDonald (1998).

This report intends to partially fill this gap by assessing how spaceborne observations can significantly contribute to water quality monitoring in the coastal zone, and in inland water bodies, and how EO techniques meet or could meet operational user requirements. The two Earth Observation (EO) applications considered here are, 1) monitoring of coastal waters, and 2) monitoring of inland waters (lakes and rivers). Spaceborne remote sensing is considered to have a large potential for future growth. EO data marketing surveys have shown a significant trend concerning the increase of the number of potential customers who might use satellite data products to meet their requirements in a variety of professional tasks related to coastal and inland waters. The user requirements for Earth Observation (EO) data have been at the centre of space agencies concern for ten years. The European Commission, through the Centre for Earth Observation (CEO) are funding many actions to sustain the development and the awareness about EO data capability and usefulness, including workshops with companies representing a large numbers of professional sector of activity. User requirements for data on coastal and inland waters are formulated in various documents, including EU legislation, directives, environmental

agreements, science programmes, reports of the European Environment Agency (EEA) and national programmes. However, the requirements are usually formulated at a high level and in most cases it is not clear exactly which parameters EO data can provide to meet the user requirements. This report will therefore analyse the gap between higher-level information requirements and the possibilities of spaceborne sensors to provide the needed parameters.

The focus of the study is therefore to review and specify the performance of the techniques and methods used to transform satellite-sensor data into geophysical parameters and information. In this report, the term geophysical parameter is used for all water environmental characteristics, whether physical, chemical, or biological that can be potentially derived from physical quantities measured by EO sensors. The study compares the satellite-derived parameters with application requirements identified from a variety of legislative, technical and scientific documents, with emphasis on the possibility to derive quantitative information. The report derived from this study is intended to be a document facilitating the search for references, which would be used by developers and planners to find state-of-the-art technology and available scientific and technical expertise. The *specific* objectives of the study are to

- identify the geophysical parameters that need to be measured for monitoring of the quality coastal zones and inland waters, and operational requirements for accuracy, range of measurements, and sampling
- describe the presently available methodologies (algorithms) for deriving the geophysical parameters from data acquired by space-based Earth observation (EO) sensors, and assess to which extent they meet operational requirements
- assess the improvements expected with the use of those sensors that have recently been launched or will be available in the next five years (hereafter referred to as “new sensors”), and related improved analysis methods
- give a prospective view on the improvements that could potentially be achieved with a dedicated sensor, optimised for the application, or advanced technology
- present the study results in a high-quality, easy-to-consult report and in the form of a database.

The report is intend to serve as a document that facilitates the search for references and information for scientists, project managers, planners, and decision makers who need an analysed overview of the present capability of EO regarding the assessment and monitoring of natural water quality, as well as those who look for trends and expected improvement in this domain.

I.2 Clarification of terminology

In order to avoid confusion and misinterpretation of the study results, it is necessary to define more precisely some key terms used in the report. One example of ambiguous term is “parameter” which can be used at least at three different levels:

- At high level (e.g., EU directives/ agreements), parameter is frequently used in reference to domains of application such as “water quality”, “coastal development”, “over-fishing”, “eutrophication”. In this study, we use the term “subject of concern” to address these higher level issues;
- At intermediate level, we use the term “geophysical parameter” in the same sense as in scientific disciplines, though for simplicity we generally consider physical, biological, chemical and other measurable parameters as “geophysical”, e.g., water temperature, water colour, and suspended sediment concentration;

- At technical level, “parameter” means energetic quantities measured by remote sensors such as radiance, backscatter. A sensor parameter can also mean sensor or instrument parameters such as frequency, polarisation, incidence angle and pixel size.

In addition the following terms are defined for the study.

Accuracy: Root mean square difference between the observed and the actual values

Algorithm: An algorithm is defined here as a specific set of data processing steps to solve a problem as part of a technique as a whole.

Retrieval algorithm: Those algorithms that are used to derive a geophysical parameter from remote sensor measurements.

Application: An application in general is the professional task, e.g., monitoring of coastal waters. A general application may have more specific sub-applications or *subjects of concern*, e.g., eutrophication / algae blooms.

Case I water: natural water body for which water-leaving radiance measured by remote sensors are only dependent on chlorophyllous pigments and derived products, i.e., the only significant optically-active water-column component is chlorophyllous pigments and derived products.

Case II water: natural water body for which water-leaving radiance measured by remote sensors is dependent upon chlorophyllous pigments and derived products and at least one other optically-active component (e.g., suspended sediment, coloured dissolved organic matter).

Coastal region/area/zone: See section I.1.3 for a detailed definition.

Coastal waters are those in the coastal zone and include bays, sounds, lagoons and inlets

Customer: A customer is any potential user of EO data for the applications considered here.

Delay of availability: time delay accepted between observation taking and availability of the raw data or value-added products to the customer.

EO data: Earth Observation (EO) data are remote sensing data acquired from spaceborne sensors.

EO system: The system includes all elements from platform, sensor, and data acquisition, data processing and distribution.

Inland waters are lakes (fresh or saline), reservoirs, ponds and rivers, including river deltas and estuaries

Maximum error outer limits: the maximum divergence to the true value that can be observed when using one particular algorithm in various conditions (different regions or environment).

Model: A model is a set of mathematical expressions that either describe biogeochemical and physical processes or relationship between various quantities.

Empirical model: Mathematical expression deduced from statistical fitting between a set of physical quantities measured by remote sensors, and a set of in-situ measurements.

Semi-analytical model: Model that is built up partly from the physical description of natural phenomena and partly from empirical relationship.

Monitoring is the repetitive observation and study of an area or phenomenon.

Observing cycle: required interval between two successive global coverages (including the equatorial regions).

Parameter: [see discussion above]

Resolution (horizontal): mean sampling distance

Subject of concern: topic or problem area (e.g., eutrophication / algae blooms) within a general application area.

Technique: A technique is the means or process by which information of geophysical parameters is derived. This includes all elements from space platform, sensor, algorithm(s) and ancillary data.

Temporal resolution: required interval of time between two successive views of the same region (repetitivity)

Water quality parameter: any geophysical parameter that give an information on the physical, biological, chemical, ecological, sanitary, geological or dynamic status of a water body.

I.3 Characterisation of coastal and inland waters

Behind the term "coastal and inland waters" lies many essential ecological functions, amenities, and human uses that link in multiple ways to regional and global environmental changes. Water in an ecological sense is arguably the most essential medium enabling the life processes of organisms and is crucially involved in other physical processes in the environment. Inland and coastal water bodies encompass a number of aquatic and shoreline habitats, some of which host rare species; water bodies often result from and affect local to regional climates; and as migration routes, water bodies, link distant habitats and environments. In terms of amenities and human uses, coastal and inland waters are closely linked with tourist and recreational activities, commercial and recreational fisheries, trade, transportation, the production of electricity, and industrial activities that require abundant water supplies. Water bodies are also connected with processes like liquid waste disposal and water pollution, flooding, and the breeding and spreading of bacterial and other diseases. Urbanisation, development, agriculture, transportation, and industrial activities like mining, nuclear power production, and paper production all depend on surface (and ground-) water. In some regions of the world, surface water even augments groundwater supplies for drinking water, emphasising the importance of maintaining high water quality. Because of essential role of water in all of these processes, some water resource and global change scientists believe that the most important feature in future discussions of global resource use and change will be water (Luterbacher & Serdar, 1996 [25]). Both types of media (coastal and inland waters) are characterised by small-scale processes and phenomena, high spatial and temporal variability of the main physical and biogeochemical properties of the water, hazards and unpredictable events. These have been particularly highlighted by large international projects such as LOICZ (Land-Ocean Interaction in the Coastal Zone) and ELOISE (European Land-Ocean Interaction Studies).

I.3.1 Characterisation of coastal waters

I.3.1.1 Definition and characteristics

According to the objectives of the study, which deals with water quality, the following definition of coastal waters is offered, taken from published works:

The coastal zone is that space in which terrestrial environments influence marine environments and vice versa. The coastal zone is of variable width and may also change in time. Delimitation of boundaries is not normally possible; more often, an environmental gradient or transition marks such limits. At any locality the coastal zone may be characterised according to physical, biological or cultural criteria. These need not, and in fact rarely do, coincide (Carter, 1998 [5]).

The general geographic definition of coastal waters is the area where the fluid elements (ocean, atmosphere) interact with the lithosphere. This area is further defined from an environmental point of view, to be where any hazard significantly impact on these fluid elements and the lithosphere. An impact is significant when the dilution processes are no longer efficient. It is admitted that water column depth less than 200 m does not offer efficient mixing and dilution capabilities. This definition is fully consistent with other approaches based on administrative, economical and geographical reasoning.

In a Coastal Zone Earth Watch study report by ESA from 1995 [9], the EO data requirements for the operational community were analysed. The main characteristics of the coastal zones of Europe regarding this issue can be summarised as follows:

- the climate conditions in the coastal zones vary extremely from wet, windy and icy in the north and west to drought conditions in the south, thus placing heavy demands on monitoring and forecasting systems
- cloud coverage is much more frequent in the north and west compared to the Mediterranean, which has implications for the types and usefulness of satellite data
- the tidal range and extent of tidal flats are limited in the Mediterranean and Baltic Sea, but of significant importance in many regions in the western part of Europe
- the coastal zones are generally highly populated (*ca.* 70% of the global population), including temporary overpopulation of tourists in some areas, which has various kinds of severe impact on the environment
- many coastal zone regions are highly industrialised (offshore industry, ship traffic, fishing, mariculture) with growing activities which increase the risk of pollution and accidents
- desertification due to agricultural and grazing practices as well as deforestation is a severe environmental issue in the Mediterranean basin
- coastal erosion and sediment transport have severe impact on bathymetry and coastline in many areas
- protection against extreme sea level height and river flooding is a matter of vital importance in countries such as The Netherlands, which requires extensive monitoring and forecasting systems

I.3.1.2 Application sectors for coastal waters

There are several application sectors with different roles and responsibilities related to coastal areas. The most important sectors needing environmental data, including remote sensing data, are:

- public health protection
- tourism and leisure areas
- coastal protection (external forcing, sea level rise, erosion)
- fisheries (policy enforcing, fleet monitoring, resource management)
- shellfish waters and water suitable for fish-breeding and mariculture
- integrated coastal zone management (planning/decision making, harbour management, environmental management)
- water quality and pollution (phytoplankton, water surface temperature (WST), oil spill detection, suspended matter)
- waste management, removal and disposal of disused offshore oil and gas
- water level and storm forecast (extreme sea level rise, erosion, risk assessment)
- coastal surveying including environmental monitoring (pollution and water quality surveillance)
- mapping including bathymetry (updated coastal maps and sea charts)
- meteorology (forecasting, hind-casting, modelling)
- shipping (routing and traffic monitoring)
- engineering (planning and construction)

- hinterland monitoring (land use, agriculture, vegetation, flood risk assessment)

In a specific region, as for example the coast of Ireland, data is needed by local authorities, policy makers and other customers for a wide range of activities (N. Connolly, UCC Cork, pers. comm.) such as:

1. *Aquaculture licensing*

- Position of operators; volume of equipment - estimates of production.

2. *Algal mapping*

3. *Habitat characterisation*

- Resource evaluation on the intertidal zone - key habitat types based on sediment and algal cover estimates.
- NB Natura 2000
- Coastal sensitivity mapping - oil spill, pollution, etc.

4. *Accretion, decretion, climate change*

- Sand cell movements, sedimentation
- Coastal zone hazard vulnerability zoning, mapping and analysis - e.g. Federal Emergency Mapping Agency (FEMA, USA).
- Sea level rises monitored using changes in vegetation patterns, expansion/decrease in salt marsh areas.
- Extraction: determine those areas vulnerable as a result of sand removal.

5. *Bathymetry*

- Sea bottom topography and changes- navigation, dredging, sea surface roughness.

6. *Modelling*

- Sediment transport - source of input data for sediment transport models, validating existing models.
- Storm patterns; predictions of storms and extreme weather situations.

7. *Coastal monitoring system*

- Potential users: weather service, local government authorities, fisheries and aquaculture, offshore industries, Naval Service, insurance companies.

8. *Sea Surface Temperature*

- Aid in determination of upwelling zones, front formations, and stratification within bays and estuaries.
- Fisheries - aid in tracking shoals of certain pelagic fishes e.g. blue finned tuna.

9. *Algal Blooms*

- Algal bloom detection and monitoring growth, transport and decay at specific and vulnerable areas.

10. *Oil slicks*

- Of particular interest in harbour and Bay.

11. *Human activity patterns*

- Recreation usage of coastal zone by patterns of shoreline disturbance, vessels per unit area for angling/boating/sailing etc.

12. *Wind/wave and associated parameters*

- Wind fronts, wind speed, wind direction maps
- Surface waves, internal waves, wave height map, wave length map, wave direction map, surface current velocity, -
 - all essential to shipping, leisure sailing, engineering for coastal protection and marina development. Agree that port authorities, engineers, shipping agencies, oil and gas companies are interested in bathymetric mapping and changes, and wave climate.

- Sea state guidelines for emergency response.

13. *Integration of marine and terrestrial maps*

- Of great importance - the problem of reconciliation between terrestrial maps and marine navigation charts.

1.3.2 Characterisation of inland waters

1.3.2.1 Definition and characteristics

For the purpose of this study, inland water is defined as represented by lakes, rivers, reservoirs, and ponds, but not wetlands. It also does not include glaciers or the coastal bays and inlets that are commonly classed as “inland water” by official territorial boundaries.

The surface areas of large lakes and inland seas are published in atlases and similar references such as the CIA's World fact-book (1990, [6]); accuracy and measurement methodologies change, however, so these data cannot be used for quantitative studies. The World Register of Dams lists surface areas of large reservoirs. Fairly complete hydrological data, including surface areas, are available for North America, Europe, parts of Asia, and Australia, but not the rest of the world (L'vovich, 1979, [23]). Although they comprise a significant area, data on small water bodies – natural and artificial – is not generally available (Nace, 1969 [28]; L'vovich, 1979 [23]).

Lakes:

Natural lakes comprise the largest inland surface-water area. In 1978, UNESCO estimated the area of the world's lakes at 2,058,700 km², or about 1.4% of the Earth's total land area; of this, 1,236,400 km² is fresh water and 822,300 km² is salt water. Globally, UNESCO identified 145 large (over 100 km²) lakes and estimated that they cover 1,300,000 km²; they are thought to contain over 95% of total inland water volume. Citing "USGS" as source, Botkin and Keller (1987, [3]) estimate the global surface area of freshwater lakes to be 855,000 km².

The significance of small water bodies is illustrated by a Soviet example. The American geographical society (1965, [2]) estimated that the former USSR had 2,850,000 lakes with a total surface area of about 500,000 km² which was about 2% of the country. More than 98% of these are small lakes less than 1 km²; the total area of the 17 largest lakes with a surface area over 1,000 km² is 173,000 km², but those lakes contain over 98% of water volume.

Reservoirs:

The most significant land use change affecting inland water is the building of reservoirs. Petts (1984, [30]) stated: "without doubt the damming of rivers has been one of the most dramatic and widespread, deliberate impacts of Man on the natural environment." As with lakes, global data are available for large dams and reservoirs – which hold most of the water – but the many small structures are not well documented (L'vovich, 1979, [23]).

The 1972 UNESCO approximation of reservoir surface area was based on an estimated 10,000 reservoirs, mostly in Europe, former USSR, and North America. UNESCO also reported a total of 143 reservoirs with a capacity greater than 5 km³ volume. A World Register of Large Dams - describing dams higher than 15 m - has been issued by the International Commission on Large Dams periodically since the early 1970's (van der Leeden, 1990, [37]).

Rivers:

No estimates of flowing water surface areas have been found in the literature; because the main interest is to measure volume and fluxes. In theory, surface area for streams, rivers, and canals could be calculated from existing width and length data (in well-inventoried regions).

For inland waters, the main problems are associated with fluctuating water levels and ephemeral water bodies. Most natural water bodies fluctuate so little in size that changes in measurement accuracy would probably exceed the natural variability. However, closed-basin lakes – which include some of the world's largest inland water bodies – may vary in area by a factor of 4 to 10. Many reservoirs fluctuate seasonally by as much as 40-60% in volume.

Remote sensing data on water body area is readily available in principle but lack of systematic data coverage means that quantitative data is difficult to derive.

Inland waters have some characteristics in common with coastal waters, as well as some important characteristics of their own:

- large lakes and reservoirs are substantial enough to influence the meso-scale climate, establishing a quasi-marine climate pattern in continental areas. Variability in the water body evaporation rate, water surface temperature and heat balance are subject to continuous monitoring for meso-scale weather forecast and climate change analysis
- riparian areas of inland water bodies are generally highly populated (particular in summer because they are popular recreation areas) resulting in pollution due to: a) urban disposal b) industrial effluents c) agricultural runoffs d) massive tourist misconduct; these factors increase the pollution rates and risks of environmental hazards and requires continuous surveillance on appropriate space/time scales
- inland waters are usually principal sources of drinking water for the riparian settlements (ranging from small settlements to large urban areas), and deterioration of water quality can have severe impact on the public health. This necessitates control of water quality.
- climate-induced variations in water level, heavy sediment transport, natural and anthropogenically driven current pattern variations, and shore erosion in inland water bodies present serious problems for navigation of ships and other activities in lakes and rivers
- many inland waters are subject to flooding events which require a system for monitoring water surface level and watershed hydrology dynamics as well as forecasting and warning systems
- many rivers transporting sediments, pollutants, heat, surfactants, garbage (including floating timber), etc., discharge into the oceans with significant impact on coastal and deep water environments.

1.3.2.2 Application sectors for inland waters

The most important sectors of inland waters that need environmental remote sensing data are:

- ecological quality of water: aquatic environment status dynamics assessment and prediction (eutrophication, anoxia, biodiversity, trophic status dynamics)
- recreation area protection and preservation (macrophytes and higher plants encroachment, beach littering and decaying algae depositions, water malodour)
- bathing water
- drinking water (quality, control, methods of measurements and analysis)
- community water policy
- use of river for dumping of waste water, for cooling plants and traffic
- fishery (dynamics of macrophyte stands as areas of fish spawning, monitoring of areas of high concentrations of phytoplankton as potential zones of fish school locations)

I.4 Specificity of water remote sensing

Before proceeding further in the technical aspects of the study, it seems necessary to give some background on the specificity of remote sensing of water bodies. In this section, an introduction to the physics behind EO of water bodies is given, with emphasis on optical remote sensing.

First, water optical properties are discussed, and basics on water optics are presented. Secondly, some general considerations are presented concerning the correction of EO optical data from atmospheric effects. Then, an introduction to hydro-optical models and inverse methods is given, since these concepts are used subsequently. Finally, a short description of water properties in respect to thermal infrared and microwave radiation is given.

I.4.1 Optics for the water medium

I.4.1.1 Optical properties of the water: definitions

A. Some relations useful in optics for water medium

Relation between radiant flux F and radiant intensity I : $dI = d^2F / d\omega$

Definition of irradiance E : $dE = d^2F / ds = dI \cos\theta / r^2$

Definition of radiance L : $L = d^2F / ds \cos\theta d\omega = dI / ds \cos\theta$

B. Terminology

Reflectance: the ratio of the radiant flux to the incident radiant flux: $\rho = F_r / F_0$

Transmittance: the ratio of the transmitted radiant flux to the incident radiant flux

$$T = F_t / F_0$$

Absorptance: the ratio of the radiant flux lost from a beam by the means of the absorption to the incident flux

$$A = F_a / F_0$$

Scatterance: the ratio of the radiant flux scattered from a beam, to the incident flux

$$B = F_b / F_0$$

Attenuance: the ratio of the radiant flux lost from a beam of infinitesimal width by the means of the absorption and scattering to the incident flux

$$C = F_c / F_0$$

$$1 - C = (1 - A)(1 - B) = T$$

Absorption coefficient: the internal absorptance of an infinitesimally thin layer of the medium normal to the beam, divided by the thickness (Δr) of the layer

$$a = -\Delta A / \Delta r$$

for an homogeneous medium: $ar = -\ln(1 - A)$

Scattering coefficient: the internal scatterance of an infinitesimally thin layer of the medium normal to the beam, divided by the thickness (Δr) of the layer

$$b = -\Delta B / \Delta r$$

for an homogeneous medium: $br = -\ln(1 - B)$

Attenuation coefficient: the internal attenuance of an infinitesimally thin layer of the medium normal to the beam, divided by the thickness (Δr) of the layer

$$c = -\Delta C / \Delta r$$

$$c = a + b$$

for an homogeneous medium: $cr = -\ln(1 - C) = -\ln(T)$

Together with the volume scattering function (i.e., the angular distribution of the light scattered by a unit volume), the absorption, scattering and attenuation coefficients are the inherent optical properties (IOPs) of the water. These quantities are independent of the light field distribution.

Irradiance ratio or volume reflectance: the ratio of the upward to the downward irradiance at a depth in the sea.

$$R = E_u / E_d$$

(Vertical/diffuse) Attenuation coefficient of a quantity H (e.g. radiance, irradiance): the vertical gradient of the logarithm of the quantity

$$K = -d(\ln H) / dz = -(1 / H)(dH / dz)$$

Volume reflectance and diffuse attenuation coefficient are apparent optical properties (AOPs) of the water. These quantities are dependent of the light field distribution.

Refractive index: the phase velocity of radiant energy in free space divided by the phase velocity of the same energy in a specified medium. It is equal to the sine of the angle of incidence (in vacuo) to the sine of the angle of refraction. Symbol: n

Optical length: The geometrical length of a path multiplied with the total attenuation coefficient associated with the path.

$$\tau = cr$$

1.4.1.2 Water surface optical properties

A. Global radiation incident

Radiative transfer in the water column of natural media such as oceans, lakes, etc is leaded by the primary energy source, *i.e.* the global radiation (from sun and sky) incident on the surface of the water. The alteration of the sun's radiation in the atmosphere is due chiefly to scattering, which removes an appreciable part of the short-wave component of sunlight. Thus two components of a different nature are formed, the direct (or beam) component of the radiation covers a large spectral range from 290 nm to 3000 nm, whereas skylight is diffuse and is dominant in the short-wave part of the spectrum. The spectral distribution of global radiation is only slightly affected by air turbidity, and it is little dependant on solar elevations above 15°. On the whole, clouds do not appreciably change the spectral composition in the range 350 nm - 800 nm. The radiance from most overcast skies can be roughly represented by a cardioidal distribution:

$$L(i) = L(\pi/2)(1 + 2 \cos i)$$

B. Reflection at sea surface

Reflectance for global radiation: when dealing with the reflectance of global radiation, we have to treat separately the reflectance of direct energy of solar radiation, ρ_s , and that of sky radiation, ρ_d . The total radiation is expressed as the sum:

$$\rho = E_x / E = \rho_s(1 - N) + \rho_d N$$

where E and E_x are the incident and reflected irradiance respectively, and N is the significant ratio of diffuse radiation to global radiation. Computational approaches of previous model for skylight, as well as semi-empirical approaches, as by Cox and Munk (1956, [8]), lead to typical values:

Reflectance (%) of the sea for skylight:

Sky	Sea		
	smooth	rough	
	Jerlov (1976, [19])	Burt (1954, [4])	Cox and Munk (1956)
Uniform	6.6	5.7	5.0 - 5.5
Overcast	5.2	4.8	4.3 - 4.7

The glitter is a phenomenon bearing upon the reflection of solar radiation. The direct component reflects onto the water surface and can be observed by a sensor/observer in the opposite direction. Increasing roughness of the water surface will enlarge the width of the glittering pattern.

C. Refraction at sea surface

The deviation of the direction of light propagation at the air-water interface is described by the laws of Al Hussein - Descartes - Snell. For a planar interface, the phenomenon occurs in a plane, and the relation between the incident angle i and the refraction angle j is given by:

$$\sin i = n \sin j$$

with n close to 4/3 for the water. From a practical point of view, variations of the refraction index n with respect to the temperature and salinity may be neglected.

This effect defines a limit cone for the refracted light, of half angle 48.5° , occasioning changes of the radiance and of the irradiance at the air-water interface. If L_a and L_w being respectively the radiances in the air and in the water:

$$L_w = n^2(1 - \rho) L_a$$

The downward irradiances in the air and in the water are respectively:

$$dE_a = L_a \cos i \, d\omega_a = L_a \cos i \sin i \, d\phi \, di$$

$$dE_w = L_w \cos j \, d\omega_w = L_w \cos j \sin j \, d\phi \, dj$$

where $d\omega$ are the infinitesimal solid angles including the irradiances. From there, it comes:

$$dE_w = (1 - \rho) \, dE_a$$

showing the obvious fact that the interface between air and water changes irradiance on a plane parallel to the interface by reflection only.

D. Water albedo

In order to scrutinise reflection events and secure adequate definitions, the following symbols are pertinent:

E_{ad} = downward irradiance in air

E_{au} = upward irradiance in air

E_{wd} = downward irradiance in water

E_{wu} = upward irradiance in water

The albedo A of the sea is defined as the ratio of the energy leaving the sea to that falling on it:

$$A = E_{au} / E_{ad}$$

which leads to:

$$E_{ad} - E_{au} = E_{wd} - E_{wu}$$

$$E_{au} = \rho_a E_{ad} + E_{wu} - \rho_w E_{wu}$$

$$A = \rho_a + (1 - \rho_w) E_{wu} / E_{ad}$$

I.4.1.3 Radiative transfer in water

A. The radiative transfer equation

The general equation for the radiative transfer is given by:

$$\cos\theta \frac{dL(z, \theta, \phi)}{dz} = cL(z, \theta, \phi) - \beta(\theta, \phi; \theta_0, \phi_0) E_i e^{cz \sec \theta_0} - \int_{\theta'=0}^{\pi} \int_{\phi'=0}^{2\pi} \beta(\theta, \phi; \theta', \phi') L(z, \theta, \phi) \sin \theta' d\theta' d\phi'$$

where E_i is the irradiance produced by the sunlight on a plane perpendicular to its propagation in the water (θ_0, ϕ_0) . The theory presumes a known law of scattering, through the scattering function β . Numerical methods for the development of this model are presented through the document.

B. Relation between upward and downward radiation

A great deal of emphasis has been placed on adequate derivation of the irradiance ratio (reflectance) $R = E_u / E_d$ from the theory. Gordon (1975, [12]) has shown, using Monte Carlo simulations of the transfer of radiant energy in the ocean, that the volume reflectance can be related to inherent optical properties – absorption and back-scattering coefficients- by the following equation:

$$R = C \frac{b_b}{a + b_b}$$

where C depends upon solar zenith angle, volume scattering function and water state, and varies from 0.32 to 0.37 for zenith and overcast sky respectively. Prieur and Morel (1975, [31]) found a theoretical value for 0.33 for clear water. The same relationship has been verified and used by Dekker (1993, [121]) for various inland water bodies.

C. Asymptotic state

For infinite depths, development of theoretical model leads, with the hypothesis of an isotropic scattering to:

$$L(\theta) = \frac{1}{4\pi} \frac{b}{c} \frac{E_0}{1 + \frac{k}{c} \cos \theta}$$

where k is the limit, at the infinity, for the radiance attenuation coefficient.

I.4.1.4 Optical water types

A scheme for optical classification of ocean and coastal waters was proposed by Jerlov (1976, [19]) in order to distinguish different water types in terms of spectral transmittance of downward irradiance at high solar altitudes (see Figure 1). Off shore waters, or open oceans are classified into three types I, II and III, going respectively from blue waters to yellow waters. Coastal waters are also classified into nine types, named 1 to 9.

Note that the clearest case for coastal waters (type 1) does not reach the less clear case for open ocean water type. This effect, reported by authors, is due to the limited number of cases of coastal water taken into account for the initial classification scheme.

This classification is certainly the most used, however other classification exists as the one proposed by Morel (1980, [27]), which has been adopted in this report: *Case I water*: natural water body for which water-leaving radiance measured by remote sensors are only dependent on chlorophyllous pigments and derived products; *Case II water*: natural water body for which water-leaving radiance measured by remote sensors is dependent upon chlorophyllous pigments

and derived products and at least one other optically-active component (e.g., suspended sediment, coloured dissolved organic matter).

The digest of water optics written in this section is extracted mostly from Jerlov (1976, [19]), especially for the definitions and for the figures.

Figure 1. Jerlov water types (see also text)

1.4.2 Atmospheric correction of ocean colour data

Atmospheric correction of ocean colour data is required if quantitative estimation of geophysical parameters such as chlorophyll concentration is to be derived.

1.4.2.1 The problem

When viewed from above the atmosphere (from a satellite) the ocean appears dark (low level signal). The colour and brightness variations in the image of the ocean, which (among other things) reveal the variation of the concentration of chlorophyll, is swamped by the sunlight scattering in the atmosphere. For mapping chlorophyll in the ocean the light purely originating from the atmosphere should be removed.

The atmosphere produces 80-90% of the radiance measured by a satellite when looking at the ocean, only 10-20% of the signal comes from the ocean (Figure 2).

1.4.2.2 Atmospheric correction methods

Removing atmospheric contribution from the signal measured by an EO sensor requires modelling the optical properties of the atmosphere at the time of acquisition of the image. In the visible part of the spectrum, three main processes cause atmospheric effects: Rayleigh (molecule) scattering, absorption by water vapour, ozone and other gas, and absorption and scattering by suspended particles (aerosols).

Modelling of Rayleigh scattering and gas absorption is well established. Gas absorption is highly variable in space and time but this effect is usually overcome by using spectral bands where this absorption can be neglected. The main problem in correcting from atmosphere effects comes

from the particles in suspension in the atmosphere (aerosol) because their size and distribution are highly variable in space and time.

Figure 2. Radiative transfer in the atmosphere. a) Light path of the water-leaving radiance. b) Attenuation of the water-leaving radiance. c) Scattering of the water-leaving radiance out of the sensor's Field-of-view (FOV). d) Sun glint (reflection from the water surface). e) Sky glint (scattered light reflecting from the surface). f) Scattering of reflected light out of the sensor FOV. g) Reflected light is also attenuated towards the sensor. h) Scattered light from the sun that is directed toward the sensor. i) Light that has already been scattered by the atmosphere, which is then scattered toward the sensor. j) Water-leaving radiance originating out of the sensor FOV, but scattered toward the sensor. k) Surface reflection out of the sensor FOV, which is then scattered toward the sensor. L_w : total water-leaving radiance. L_r : radiance above the sea surface due to all surface reflection effects within the FOV. L_p : atmospheric path radiance. (This figure is adapted from Robinson, 1983 [33])

Three main approaches are considered to estimate the aerosol optical thickness, which is a measure of the attenuation properties of aerosol, integrated over the atmospheric column:

- Sensor based algorithms (CZCS, SeaWiFS, Bright Pixel algorithm) use the sensor infrared bands to estimate aerosol concentration. The purpose of this report is not to detail atmospheric correction algorithms. Nevertheless we give hereafter some useful bibliographic references are given hereafter: André, 1991 [1]; Clark, 1997 [7]; Fraser, 1997 [11]; Gordon, 1978 [13]; Gordon and Castaño, 1987 [15]; Gordon, 1988 [16]; Gordon and Wang, 1992 [17]; Gordon and Wang, 1994 [18]; Gordon, 1997 [14]; Lavender, 1997 [24]; Richter, 1996

[32]; Sturm, 1980 [34]; Tanré, 1987 [35]; Tanré, 1997 [36]; Vermote, 1996 [38]; Zagolski, 1995 [40].

- Procedures based on computation of the radiative transfer in the atmosphere (e.g., MODTRAN, 6S). The atmospheric corrections to be applied on the images are assessed by simulation of the radiative transfer in the atmosphere, and calculation of the atmosphere and air/sea interface contributions to the total signal measured by the sensor. Radiative transfer models use standard gas and particles atmospheric profiles, as well as aerosol size distribution that are typical of maritime, continental or urban areas (e.g., mid-latitude summer standard atmosphere with aerosol of maritime type).
- Inverse modelling consider the aerosol parameters as an unknown, together with the water quality parameters to be retrieved (see part III section 2 and 3 for description of such approach, forms 15 to 17)

1.4.2.3 Air-sea interface contribution

Beside atmospheric correction, other factors that pollute the signal emerging from the water body may be taken into account:

- Sun Glint. Must be avoided. Corrections can be performed to some extent based on the modelling of the surface roughness. The most popular technique to accomplish this task makes use of wind speed to estimate surface roughness (Cox & Munk, 1956 [8]).
- White Caps. Wind blowing at a speed greater than 3 m.s^{-1} can generate white caps at the sea surface. An estimate of the percentage of the sea surface covered by white caps can be derived from wind speed, and then used to introduce a correcting factor to the measured signal (Koepke, 1984 [22]).

1.4.3 Hydro-optical models and inverse methods

Hydro-optical models describe the relationship between the measured or estimate inherent optical properties (IOPs) and apparent optical properties (AOPs), and the concentration of the optically-actives constituents (OAC) in the water column.

Forward (direct) models determine the optical properties of the water from the concentration of OAS. Inverse models allow retrieving the concentrations of OAC given IOPs or AOPs.

Most inverse methods in marine optics require such a model in order to link the optical quantity derived from EO data to water component. The approaches presently operational or under development follow the scheme describe hereafter:

- Use of a forward hydro-optical model to compile a database of volume reflectance or radiance (upwelling or water-leaving radiance) spectra for a wide range of OAS concentrations.
- Retrieval of the same optical quantities (reflectance or radiance) from the EO sensor data
- Search the best match between retrieved and simulated spectra using mathematical methods. Several mathematical approaches have been presented such as Simplex method (form 15), multivariate optimisation (form 17) and artificial neural network (form 16 and section 2.2.2)

The critical point when dealing with inverse modelling of the radiative transfer in the water is to solve the multiple solution problem that is encountered when attempting to derive water-column components from remotely sensed radiance or reflectance. This problem is due to the fact that multiple combinations of the optically-active components can give rise to the same subsurface reflectance, and leads to a mathematical dead-end. Thus, achieving a solution requires for example that relationships be found between the model parameters. Such relationships are

generally highly non-linear. This issue is presently under investigation by several scientific groups worldwide.

The correctness and robustness of the hydro-optical models, and its sensitivity to the observed parameters are obviously other critical points for achieving an efficient retrieval with inverse algorithms.

Introduction to artificial neural network

A short introduction to artificial neural network is given hereafter since this tool is rather new in the field of water quality assessment and because it seems to become one of the most popular techniques for solving highly non-linear inverse problem.

a) Background:

Since the range of concentrations of water constituents in the targeted water bodies is generally limited, the possible reflectance spectra can be computed in advance with one of the appropriate radiative models. Establishing an inverse relationship between the concentration vector \mathbf{C} and the corresponding computed reflectances, the results of such simulations can be stored in the form of a neural network and used for retrieval of remotely sensed data. For this specific application, a neural network is used only as a multiple non-linear regression technique to parameterise an inverse relationship between \mathbf{C} and the computed reflectances.

b) How does it work?

The most commonly used neural networks in remote sensing is the multi-layer perceptron generally consisting of an **input layer** where the neurones are the elements of a feature vector which might consist of, e.g., radiances at certain wavelengths or radiances subjected to a principal component transformation, internal or **“hidden” layer(s)**, and an **output layer**. The number of neurones in the output layer equals the number of parameters to be determined, e.g., concentration of chlorophyll, suspended sediment and yellow substance. Each neurone in the network is connected to all neurones in both the preceding and subsequent layers by connections with associated weights.

The input signals are transferred to the neurones in the next layer in a feed-forward manner. As the signal propagates from neurone to neurone, it is modified by the appropriate connection weight. The receiving neurone sums the weighted signals from all neurones, which it is connected to in the previous layer. The total input that a single neurone receives is weighted in the following way:

$$net_j = \omega_{ji} o_i,$$

where ω_{ji} is the weights between neurone i and neurone j , and o_i is the output from neurone i . The output from a given neurone j is then obtained from:

$$o_j = f(net_j).$$

The function f is usually a non-linear sigmoid function that is applied to the weighted sum of inputs before the signal reaches the next layer. When the signal reaches the output layer, the network output is produced. The created network should be first trained so that it could generalise and predict outputs from inputs that it has not processed before. A training pattern is fed into the neural network and the signals are fed-forwarded. Then, the network output is compared to the truth output, and the error is computed and back propagated through the network. As a result, the connection weights are modified following the generalised delta rule:

$$\Delta\omega_{ji}(n+1) = \eta(\delta_j o_i) + \alpha\Delta\omega_{ji}(n),$$

where η is the learning rate parameter, δ_j is an index of the error change rate, α is the momentum parameter. The training is conducted until the output error reaches a desired level. A software of neural network could be provided from the Internet web-site (SNNS, 1995 [218]).

1.4.4 Properties of water surface in the thermal infrared domain

Since the water emissivity is close to the unity in the thermal infrared domain, the water leaving radiance in the 3 μm – 12 μm band can be expressed through the blackbody theory. Due to the dielectric properties of water, electromagnetic radiation do not penetrate into water depths greater than typically 1 μm in this band. The mean temperature of the water interface corresponding to this depth is generally named Sea Surface Temperature (SST). Due to the fact that this layer is also the place where other energetic processes of exchanges with the atmosphere do occur, its thermal equilibrium is subject to many artefacts (wind, vertical mixing, or stratification...). So, this method for the measurement of the water surface temperature may lead to strong discrepancies with the results offered by other ways (*e.g.* bucket temperature).

Starting with the Planck's law which relates the blackbody radiance L to the absolute temperature SST at a given wavelength λ :

$$L = \frac{2\Pi hc^2}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{e^{\frac{hc}{\lambda k SST}} - 1}$$

The exponential dependency of the blackbody radiance from the temperature may be simplified for the needs of thermography algorithms. This may be achieved by two ways. In the microwave domain, where the water thermal emissivity is still significant, the Rayleigh-Jeans approximation permits to use a simplified relationship, which leads to a linear dependency between radiance and temperature. Expressed in this way, the radiance is also named brightness temperature. In the thermal infrared domain, the Rayleigh-Jeans is no longer valid but it is still possible to develop the Planck law in a Taylor series, and to only keep the linear term. This method may be used when the temperature variation is of the order of magnitude of 10 K, which is generally the case in satellite thermography of water surfaces on Earth. In that case, the previous equation leads to:

$$L = G \cdot SST + B$$

where G is the gain of the imaging system, and B is a bias. One may notice that in this case, L is sometimes improperly named as the brightness temperature.

1.4.5 Water imaging mechanisms in the microwave domain

From the most general point of view, the Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) imagery is defined by the ability of surface targets to reflect the radar signal toward the sensor, which may occur through two processes: the specular reflection, which covers mainly the domain of incidence angles between 0° to 20°, and the backscattering processes, which covers the incidence range between 10° to 70°. At sea surface, both phenomenon may occur, but in any case, the image intensity may be related to the reflecting ability of sea surface, through the backscattering coefficient σ :

$$\frac{P_s}{P_e} = \frac{G \cos \theta}{4\pi r^2} X_a X_r \sigma \frac{A}{4\pi r^2}$$

P_s and P_e are respectively the received and the transmitted power
 X_a and X_r the slant and the radial spatial resolution of the SAR system
 G is the antenna gain
 θ is the incidence angle

r is the range.

For SAR imaging the water surface over a range of incidence angles from about 20° to 70°, the radar backscatter is principally caused by a resonant mechanism, called Bragg scattering, where the radar energy is scattered by surface waves of approximately the same wavelength. The short surface waves are modulated by long waves and currents, causing sufficient variability that can be seen on radar imagery.

For SAR imaging surface waves, the modulation is caused by three principal processes, each of which varies in strength depending on the surface wave propagation direction with respect to the radar velocity vector. For range-travelling waves, image variability is mainly produced by surface tilt, which is the change in local incidence angle of the short waves present along the long wave and by hydrodynamic interactions (also called straining), where the long waves alters the amplitude of the surface waves by convergence and divergence and airflow variations (Figure 3). For azimuth travelling waves, the principal cause of image variability results from velocity bunching where the orbital motion of the long waves themselves produces an azimuthal displacement of the Bragg waves in the image plane (Figure 3). For ocean waves having a high-azimuth directional component, this mechanism also causes image smearing at higher azimuth wave numbers. Velocity bunching is linear for low-azimuth wave numbers (*i.e.* long and low swells), and when the altitude of the SAR platform is less than about 300 km.

Figure 3. SAR water imaging mechanisms (NASA, 1990 [29])

1.5 Current use of EO data in monitoring of coastal and inland waters

Data from different EO sensors are currently used to some extent to characterise coastal and inland waters. The main scientific or technical factors that have impacts on the use of EO data in these application sectors are those related to: 1) spatial and temporal sampling characteristics, and 2) the current ability of EO data algorithms to retrieve the geophysical parameters needed for particular application. These two factors are the focus of Part III of this report.

Currently operational information on the coastal water environment is derived largely from sparse *in situ* measurements, local models and in some cases from airborne remote sensing and occasionally from satellite sensor data such as AVHRR. *In situ* data and airborne observation are relatively expensive to collect and therefore limited temporally as well as spatially. Earth Observation data has been shown in many research projects to be able to provide temperature, turbidity and primary productivity information. In a few cases, satellite data are used for operational monitoring, e.g., AVHRR for Sea Surface Temperature, but cloud cover makes it difficult to get regular data from this system. Other EO data such as SeaWiFS is at the stage of being used operationally as an important additional source of information in local or regional operational monitoring systems. More use of EO data is expected to reduce the need for other and more expensive methods of data collection. EO data allow synoptic data coverage and provide an important supplement to *in situ*, airborne or model data. Many research programmes develop various applications of EO data for the coastal zones and inland water monitoring, in particular ocean colour data.

There is a strong consensus that EO data could play a major part in providing information on water quality parameters. Recent surveys (see part II), however, has shown there are several critical barriers to the effective use of EO data in operational management of inland and coastal waters, and that without additional capability it is unlikely that there will be much use of these data outside the research community. Each of these constraints is outlined in Table 1.

The spatial resolution and accuracy of EO data requires specific comment as to its usefulness. In the past some EO sensors have provided surface parameter values of only limited accuracy. These measurement values were often much more poor than that available from surface measurements. However, in the field of ocean colour, the science community is now confident that EO measurement accuracy is or will soon be within the error of standard *in situ* measurement.

Moreover, although measurements from water samples might be more accurate and allow deriving more variables, they have their limitation when extrapolated in time and space. Isolines drawn from samples are often less accurate than maps derived from satellites, thus, a comparison of the accuracy of both methods should be done on the level of spatio-temporal maps, not on the level of comparing the accuracy of a sample and the derived quantities from a pixel.

1.5.1 Spatial and temporal sampling

Regarding spatial resolution there is always a trade off between better resolution and data downlink volume. Higher resolution produces a greater quantities of data, which leads to a necessary reduction in swath width and therefore the period of sample. The inevitable compromise in achieving global coverage at periods adequate for oceanographic process studies means that spatial resolution cannot be as high as some would require. However, the spatial resolution of the current generation of ocean-application instruments (around 1 km: SeaWiFS,

AVHRR) is also quite adequate for the representation of certain water quality features, in particular in open ocean and coastal regions.

Regarding spatio-temporal sampling, many of the EO satellites used in meteorology and oceanography cover large areas, but at a resolution too coarse for studies of coastal zones and inland waters (altimeter, scatterometer, Meteosat). For example, wind, waves and current features are important for large- and regional-scale oceanography, but in the coastal zone, satellite observations of these features can be used mainly as background or boundary conditions for processes in the coastal zone.

The spatial scale of those processes and parameters important in coastal and inland waters vary from typically a few meters to a few kilometres. Figure 4 represents the smallest scales that need to be resolved to define the processes concerned. Some of the processes have a spatial and temporal extent far beyond the area denoted on the diagram. This is relevant because even where remote sensing lacks the resolution to define a process in detail, it has a valuable role in providing a spatial or temporal overview. For example, the Envisat-MERIS sensor with 300-meters spatial resolution has a high potential of applications in coastal zones because it is the optimal compromise with respect to spatial resolution and revisit period for coastal waters with present satellite technology.

Table 1. Constraints on the adoption of EO data for the operational provision of coastal water information

Constraint	Description
lack of operational ocean colour sensors	Although SST measurements using EO data have been possible for nearly 15 years, the loss of CZCS in 1986, meant that even the intermittent ocean-colour data that had been produced by this experimental sensor were no longer available; this severely limited the development of improved algorithms, and operational tests of its capability for routine monitoring.
appropriate algorithms with local and timely calibration	The interpretation of ocean colour imagery in coastal waters is complicated by the presence of coloured materials, which are neither of water nor of marine biogenic origin (termed Case II waters). The water quality algorithms that were developed for CZCS were derived for open waters that are free of such influence (Case I waters), and thus are of limited utility for adequate characterisation of water quality in coastal regions. Fortunately, new algorithms have recently been developed for Case II (see Part IV). Even with the availability of algorithms appropriate for the coastal regions, the practical application of EO data still requires local calibration and validation data to establish the absolute and relative accuracy of the measurements. There is a general recognition within coastal zones community that the application of EO data to the coastal zones must be in conjunction with <i>in situ</i> calibration/ validation measurements which are 'close' to the region being studied in time and space.
frequency of measurement	A single CZCS-like sensor cannot provide daily coverage over mid-latitude coastal zones. Although operational users did not request daily coverage in a recent survey, the high probability of cloud cover for some European waters requires that daily or twice daily coverage is available to provide approximately weekly updates on water quality.
access to data	EO data delivery mechanisms are still characterised by standard products and discrete data order models. This requires a significant piece of work for potential users: selecting useful data from all the data acquired and particularly transforming it into a form useful in the operational monitoring activity. It must not be necessary for end-users to invest in a major pre-processing facility before they can start to use the EO data.
integration with other data sources	The EO community has developed data structures and formats which are largely based on the needs of the academic research community. The needs of the operational user community are rather different. Perhaps the most urgent need is for data and tools to support integration with different data sources, especially grid models and point surface measurements.
information dissemination and end-user analysis tools	Even if an end-user invests the necessary resources and intellectual effort to get the EO data from the ground segment into a form in which it can be used routinely and reliably in operational monitoring, few cost-effective and functionally useful tools exist for the 3-D time series analysis of all the data sources used to derive the information content.

Figure 4. Diagram of the temporal and spatial scales of ocean and coastal zone parameters and processes (ESA, 1995 [9])

It is clear that satellite sensors such as high-resolution optical (e.g., SPOT, Landsat Thematic Mapper (TM)) and synthetic aperture radar sensors (e.g., ERS-SAR) are more appropriate than coarse-resolution sensors such as scatterometer and passive microwave radiometers or even medium resolution sensors such as SeaWiFS, AVHRR. Medium-resolution images with pixel size of about 1 km (e.g., AVHRR, SeaWiFS) are also important because the resolution is optimal for regional-scale observations and the possibility to obtain synoptic pictures of parameters such as temperature and water colour over large marine areas including the **coastal zones** and **large inland water bodies**. However, for small-scale processes in coastal and inland waters, 1 km resolution is not adequate. Table 2 summarises the scales of current satellite EO data and their applicability in coastal and inland waters.

The use of different satellite instruments for observation of oceanographic parameters on scale 1 is described more specifically in Table 3.1, while parameters for coastal and inland waters are described in Table 3.2. The same instruments applicable for the coastal zone may also be used for monitoring of larger ocean areas (Scale 1). A detailed description of sensor characteristics can be found in appendix V.3.

Table 2. Spatial scales and applicability of satellite EO data for coastal and inland waters.

Scale	Example of areas	Relevant available satellite data	Applicability for processes in coastal and inland waters
1. Global and large scale oceans > 1000 km	Atlantic Ocean, Greenland - Norwegian Seas	scatterometer, altimeter, passive microwave radiometer (PMW), Side-Side-looking Radar (SLR), SAR	Primary application is in oceanography: wind, waves, sea level, currents (see Table 2). For coastal and inland waters, the spatial scale is too large and the resolution is too coarse
2. Regional scale oceans and larger coastal areas: 1- 1000 km	Baltic Sea, North Sea, Mediterranean, large lakes	same as above, but with limitation near coasts: scatterometer: approx. 50 km altimeter: approx. 10 km PMW: approx. 20 km More important are optical and infrared radiometers (AVHRR, SeaWiFS) with 1 km resolution, SAR with 100 m resolution, and SLR with 1 km resolution	Wind, waves and currents observed on a regional scale will have impact on processes in the coastal zone. Water quality, oil spill, WST, waves, eddies, upwelling, fronts and bathymetry can be observed near the coast at 1 km resolution or better (see Table 3).
3. Local scale coastal areas and large lakes 1 m - 10 km and small lakes and rivers: 1 – 50 m	harbour areas, estuaries, rivers, small lakes, channels, wetlands, tidal flats, ponds, etc.	High resolution optical and microwave images (SPOT, Landsat, SAR) are most appropriate. New, very high-resolution images with 1 m resolution can potentially become important (e.g., IKONOS-I). AVHRR and SeaWiFS are useful in some cases to assess boundary conditions	Several parameters and processes near the coast and in inland waters can be observed by these satellite data: coastline, intra-tidal zone, water areas of rivers, shallow water topography, water colour, sediment transport, plumes, etc.

Table 3.1 The main currently available sensors for Scale 1 oceanographic parameters.

Type of Instrument	Sensors	Description
Radar altimeter (RA)	GeoSat ERS-RA Topex-Poseidon	A pencil beam microwave radar that measures the distance between the spacecraft and the ocean surface. Measurements yield the topography and surface roughness of the sea surface from which the surface current and average wave height can be estimated.
Scatterometer	ERS-AMI ADEOS	A microwave radar that measures the roughness of the sea surface in a broad swath on either side of the spacecraft with a spatial resolution of 50 km. Measurements yield the amplitude of short surface waves that are approximately in equilibrium with the local wind and from which the surface wind can be estimated.
Microwave radiometer	SSM/I	A radiometer that measures the intensity of radiation emitted from the sea surface in the microwave band in a broad swath beneath the spacecraft. Measurements yield microwave brightness temperatures, from which wind speed, water vapour, rain rate and ice cover can be estimated.

Table 3.2. The main currently available spaceborne sensors for Scales 2 and 3 coastal and inland water parameters.

Type of Instrument	Sensors	Description
Thermal radiometer	AVHRR ATSR OCTS	Radiometers that measure the intensity of infrared radiation emitted from the water surface in a broad swath beneath the spacecraft. Measurements yield estimates of sea surface temperature.
Low spatial resolution (1 km) ocean colour scanner (multispectral spectrometer).	CZCS OCTS POLDER SeaWiFS	Radiometers that measure the intensity of radiation reflected from the upper part of the water column in <i>the visible and near-infrared bands</i> in a broad swath beneath the spacecraft. Measurements yield ocean colour at high spectral resolution, from which chlorophyll pigment concentration and diffuse attenuation coefficients, and other bio-optical properties can be estimated.
Medium spatial resolution (500 m) ocean colour scanner (multispectral spectrometer).	MOS	Radiometers that measure the intensity of radiation reflected from the upper part of the water column in <i>the visible and near-infrared bands</i> in a small swath beneath the spacecraft. Measurements yield ocean colour at high spectral resolution, from which chlorophyll pigment concentration and diffuse attenuation coefficients, and other bio-optical properties can be estimated.
High spatial resolution optical radiometer	SPOT Landsat-TM IRS-C	Radiometers that measure the intensity of radiation reflected from the upper part of the water column in <i>the visible and near-infrared bands</i> in a small swath beneath the spacecraft, and at high spatial resolution. Measurements yield ocean colour at a few wavelengths, and at low spectral resolution.
High spatial resolution Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR)	ERS-SAR RadarSat-SAR	A microwave imaging radar that electronically synthesises the equivalent of an antenna large enough to achieve a spatial resolution of better than 100 m. Measurements yield information on features (wind, waves, swell, internal waves, fronts, current features, rain, oil slicks, etc.) that modulate the amplitude of the short surface waves; they also yield information on the position and character of sea ice and ice features.

In addition to the spatial scales, it is also essential to take into account the time scales of coastal zone and inland water features and processes, and how satellite data can resolve the temporal variability of the processes. Figure 4 gives an overview of the main coastal zone processes and parameters in a time-space diagram. The resolution in time and space for a number of relevant satellites is also indicated. The spatial resolution is defined as the pixel size, varying from 10-20 m for SPOT and SAR to several kilometres for Meteosat. On the other hand, Meteosat, which is a geostationary satellite, can observe much more frequently than polar orbiting satellites such as ERS with a repeat cycle of 35 days.

For processes with temporal resolution of a few days and spatial resolution of 1 km, several satellite optical sensors are useful. A severe limitation of many of these sensors is the cloud cover problem, which makes the effective observation frequency lower than a few days. In northern Europe, cloud cover can prevail for weeks, making data such as AVHRR, SeaWiFS, SPOT and Landsat practically useless for studies of processes that change within a few days such as flooding, algae blooms and ocean currents. This is extremely important for operational use of remote sensing. Possible solutions to this problem, e.g., synergy of instruments and use of numerical models, are discussed in Part IV.

The SAR instrument, which is cloud-independent, is limited by the repeat cycle of the satellites. During the three-days repeat cycles, and during the ERS-1/2 tandem operation with 1-day interval between two consecutive images of the same area, it has been demonstrated that some processes such as ocean fronts can be monitored. But many of the processes change much more rapidly than the SAR observation frequency. This is primarily the case for observations of waves, wind, estuarine tides/fronts, surface slicks and ship. Therefore, current spaceborne SAR data can

be useful supplement to other observations, but for monitoring purposes observations are required several times per day. Geostationary satellites such as Meteosat have the capability to observe processes almost continuously, but the spatial resolution of Meteosat (5 km) is too coarse for coastal zone monitoring.

For wave and wind climatology, it is clear that cloud independent microwave data from altimeter and scatterometer can provide valuable information since the data can be systematically collected over several years. Altimeter and scatterometer data are relevant to large-scale observation of the oceans. These instruments either have too coarse resolution for the coastal zone, or produce unreliable data near the shore because of the contribution of the land to the measured signal.

Figure 4 neither shows the requirements for geographical coverage nor the measurable parameters that are needed from satellite data. However, it illustrates the time-space scales for observation of the many important coastal zone processes and parameters, which must be considered in the design of satellite EO systems.

The spatio-temporal requirements for characterising inland waters are often different than for the coastal waters. The spatial scales are generally smaller, meaning that, nowadays, primarily “Scale 3” satellite sensors, as well as airborne sensors, are used for inland water applications.

Moreover, even when satellite EO data with appropriate spatial and temporal sampling characteristics are available, the range of value covered, and accuracy achieved by presently available sensors and retrieval algorithms may be insufficient for applications in highly variable and different environments, such as coastal and inland waters.

1.5.2 Ability of EO data algorithms

EO products are basically made of geo-located measurements of Earth surface physical and/or chemical properties regarding natural (passive remote sensing) or induced (active remote sensing) electromagnetic radiation. Active remote sensing with microwave only give information on the water surface since the radiation does not penetrate the water body. Information on in-water features can under certain condition be derived from the surface measurements (see section I.4).

We must stress here that optics of coastal and inland waters is very similar. Therefore, even if the nature of the processes and/or the order of magnitude of water quality parameters may be different, the parameters measurable by EO sensors and relevant for water quality monitoring are common to the two media.

A particular problem in passive remote sensing of water bodies is that the signal measured in the visible and near-infrared part of the spectrum by a spaceborne sensor is made of 90 to 98% of atmospheric and sea surface contributions. However only the visible radiation penetrates the water body and thus gives access to information of the upper layer the water column (the depth of penetration of the radiation depends upon the wavelength and the water column absorption properties).

Therefore any quantitative estimation of water constituents depends upon an adequate retrieval of that part of the signal emanating from the water column, namely the water-leaving radiance. In small inland water the problem is even more complicated because of adjacency effects e.g., contribution of vegetation around water bodies that pollutes the “purity” of water pixels. Let now suppose that the correction of the remotely sensed signal from the contributions of atmosphere and air-sea interface is perfectly achieved (see discussion on this issue in Part III). Then, the capability of deriving accurate quantity of a particular water quality parameter depends upon the complexity of the water column in term of the number and properties of the components that

interact with the electromagnetic radiation, and the efficiency of a particular algorithm to retrieve specifically this parameter.

According to the optical complexity of the water body, two types of water are defined, namely Case I and Case II waters, as introduced above.

Obviously, Case I waters are generally open-ocean oligotrophic waters, although major upwelling areas can be classified as Case I. This means that 95% of the world ocean is made of Case I waters. At the contrary, most of coastal waters, and all inland waters are Case II waters. As a matter of fact, sediment re-suspension through hydrodynamic processes, sediment transport, beach erosion, river runoff contributes in increasing the concentration of suspended sediment in coastal and inland waters. Likewise, coastal and inland waters are under land influence through river runoff, landslide, man-induced discharge and pollution, and undergo the contribution of various optically active substances such as humic and fulvic acids, which are classified as coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM), and highly contribute to the absorption of solar radiation in the blue part of the spectrum.

However we should at this point, remark that in the past thirty years, the majority of the EO missions dedicated to oceanography were focused on Case I waters and global ocean study (CZCS, SeaWiFS, OCTS). Therefore, the talent of oceanographers and limnologists interesting in EO data, worldwide has been concentrated either on the development of methods to derive water quality parameters in Case I waters from the above sensors, or on the development of algorithms to derive Case II water parameters from other sensors that are not dedicated to water study and therefore do not fulfil the requirements of sensitivity or band selection for quantitative retrieval of water signal with an acceptable accuracy (SPOT, Landsat, etc.).

It is only recently that EO missions specified for coastal water investigation, have been planned (IRS-P3/MOS, Envisat/MERIS, NEMO/COIS, etc.). Accompanying these programmes, new methods and algorithms are being developed that give the main trends of what will be possible in the near future regarding water quality monitoring of coastal and inland waters.

In parallel to the research conducted on EO of natural waters, airborne remote sensing of coastal and inland waters has drained many scientists who were frustrated by the too coarse resolution of available space technology, and/or the limitations of this technology regarding the complexity of the studied environment. Especially, applications related to the use of hyperspectral sensors and Lidar have shown a large development. The transfer of the know-how on hyperspectral remote sensing to spaceborne mission will be discussed in Part IV of this report.

I.6 Scope and tasks of the study

The scope of this study is to investigate which **geophysical parameters** can be derived from **spaceborne sensor** data that are directly relevant to two general applications that cover two water domains:

- **Monitoring of coastal water quality**, including algal blooms.
- **Monitoring of lakes and rivers**, primarily biological activity and pollution

Because there is such a wide range of geophysical parameters that are relevant and important in these applications, one must prioritise. In this study, the priority is to investigate algorithms for *water quality* environmental parameters. Parameters that are primarily related to water dynamics and meteorological conditions, such as wind, waves, currents, water level, precipitation and river run-off, are not covered or studied in detail in the study, although they are important for water quality.

Although the study concerns the capability of space sensors, the report will make reference to specific aspects of airborne technology when such methods of investigation and corresponding retrieval algorithms have a high potential for being transferred to spaceborne domain in the future. This is justified by the fact that airborne survey presently is the most commonly used remote sensing technique for inland water monitoring.

The main work tasks of the study are to:

- Task 1. Synthesise requirements to data for the two domains as formulated in studies conducted by the CEO, EU legislation and policy documents, environmental agreements signed by EU and other documents such as reports from the European Environmental Agency. The relevant geophysical parameters are identified, and their measurement quality is specified.
- Task 2. Provide inventory and description of **present space techniques** used to derive the geophysical parameters identified as relevant for water quality monitoring. Relevant algorithms are investigated to find measurement range, accuracy, required input data, validation references and operational status.
- Task 3. Assess improvements to be expected from satellite sensors that have recently been launched, and which validation process and algorithm development are still in progress (hereafter referred to as “**new sensors**”).
- Task 4. Provide a **prospective view** on possible improvements of satellite observation techniques with regards to requirements identified in task 1.
- Task 5. Deliver a **database** containing the bibliography, the list of algorithms, models, tools and ancillary data sets, using the CEO metadata standard.

I.7 Approach and methodology

1.7.1 How information has been collected and analysed

Information on requirements to data for coastal and inland waters has mainly been collected from a number of reports and other documents available on Internet. Documents related to EU policies, legislation and environmental agreements have provided fairly general and high level requirements, while the JRC reports “EU Geospatial and Environmental Information Needs”([34], [35]) address some high-level requirements more specifically, but not on parameter level. User requirements from the Customer Segment Studies have been investigated and so have a number of research projects under the Environment and Climate Programme (1994-1998) and the Marine Science and Technology Programme (MAST III, 1994-1998). Coastal zone data requirements from the operational community have also been investigated by ESA, as well as requirements collected by space agencies for future mission planning. A few international and national monitoring programmes have also been consulted.

In the analysis of the information, the approach has been the following, as illustrated in Figure 5:

1. First an overview is given of directives and agreements relevant for coastal and inland waters,
2. Then a number of subjects of concern is identified with reference to directives and agreements. The subjects of concern are formulated at a high level, using expressions such water quality, flooding, erosion, over-fishing, etc.
3. In the next step, “subjects of concern” are translated into environmental parameters, which are measurable, keeping the reference to the directives and agreements. The analysis indicates which measurement method is applicable and the possibility of using remote sensing. The parameters are grouped into physical, chemical, biological, ecological and sanitary parameters,
4. In the final step, only those parameters derivable from remote sensing methods are analysed. At this stage it is necessary to distinguish between the quantitative parameters required by the users (geophysical parameters) and the energetic quantity measured by remote sensors (sensor measurements). The role of algorithms, described in Part III, is to translate sensor-level parameters into geophysical parameters.

1.7.2 Structure and organisation of the report

The results of the study are presented in three Parts:

Part II. “Synthesis of the requirements for EO information in coastal and inland waters”

Part III. “Retrieval of geophysical parameters from space sensors: state-of-the-art and improvements expected from new sensors”

Part IV. “Prospective views on future improvements”

In Part II, we have adopted an objective approach that starts with a survey of high-level requirements, expressed as “subjects of concern” defined in general and political documents. Then a listing of all geophysical parameters relevant for monitoring of water quality in coastal and inland waters and mentioned in the analysed documents is drawn up. Finally, a reduced list of parameters is composed from those parameters that are known to presently or potentially be observable by remote sensing methods. Sixteen such parameters have been identified. The

requirements regarding the range and accuracy of each parameter for a number of applications are presented.

Figure 5. Illustration of the links between high-level requirements and low-level parameters from EO data. The role of remote sensing algorithms is to derive geophysical parameters from basic remote sensing data.

Part III contains results from both Task 2: Inventory and description of present techniques, and Task 3: Assessment of improvements to be expected from “new sensors”. These two tasks have been gathered in one part in order to give an ad-hoc access to both present algorithms and identified near-future improvements.

In a concern of completeness, Part III includes algorithms developed for both Case I and Case II waters, even if coastal and inland waters are rarely of Case I. This choice is justified by the fact that Case I water algorithms compose the major part of the state-of-the-art with regards to quantitative estimation of water quality.

Forty-six (46) types of algorithm are described, each in a one-page form containing the most important facts about the algorithms. The forms provide further references to literature and other information about the algorithms. The links between “subject of concern”, geophysical parameter, satellite sensors and algorithms are illustrated in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Flow-chart showing the link between a “subject of concern”, which in this example is eutrophication / algal bloom (top level), some of the geophysical parameters which need to be measured (second level) and the satellite sensors which can provide the parameters (third level), and algorithms that are used to derive the geophysical parameters from the satellite data. There are examples of references to pages in the report where the parameters and algorithms are described.

Part IV discussed possible improvements of EO systems for monitoring parameters in coastal and inland waters. It addresses issues related to satellite systems (repeat cycles, swath width, etc.), improved sensors, synergy between sensors, possibilities to transfer airborne technology to satellites, and theoretical limits for remote sensing.

The report is organised to facilitate easy navigation from top to bottom, or from bottom to top (Figure 6). This organisation should facilitate access to all essential information to quickly find how to derive a given geophysical parameter from satellite data. It is expected that here will be two main types of users who will read the report: 1) those who search for an immediate solutions to solve a particular problem and who need information on the present techniques, including near future improvements, in order to decide if they should integrate remote sensing techniques in their professional tasks; and 2) those who will refer to the report in order to establish plans for activities related to coastal and inland waters.

PART II. REVIEW OF REQUIREMENTS FOR EARTH OBSERVATION

II.1 Sources of information

Part II identifies the specific data requirements for environmental monitoring of coastal and inland waters. The present section describes the requirements based on several sources, namely surveys of: 1) reference documents for EU's legislation, directives and agreements; 2) the nine Customer Segment Studies conducted under contract with the CEO; 3) ongoing research and development projects that include use of EO data; and 4) ESA study of data requirements for the coastal zone. The information has been extracted from a number of documents, many of which are found on the Internet. Complete references to the information are given in Appendix.

II.1.1 Reference documents for International and European policy

II.1.1.1 International conventions and agreements

Several international conventions have been signed which relate to pollution of coastal and inland waters.

A. Marine pollution

- Convention of 1972 on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matters (London Convention)
- International Convention of 1973 for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL Convention)
- Convention of 1974 on the Prevention of Marine Pollution from Land-Based Sources (Paris Convention)
- Agreement of 1983 for Co-operation in Dealing with Pollution of the North Sea by Oil and Other Harmful Substances (Bonn Agreement)
- Convention of 1974 and 1992 for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea Area (Helsinki Convention, HELCOM)
- Convention of 1992 for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Northeast Atlantic (Oslo and Paris Conventions, OSPARCOM)

The European Union is a party to all these treaties except for the London Convention and the MARPOL Convention, which have been signed *inter alia* by France, Germany and The Netherlands. According to the Paris Convention (Article 10), the parties have agreed to establish programmes of scientific and technical research. The parties to the 1992 Helsinki Convention have undertaken to co-operate in the fields of science, technology and other research, and to exchange data and other scientific information for the purposes of this Convention. Furthermore, the parties are obliged to undertake programmes aimed at developing methods for assessing the nature and extent of pollution and risks in the Baltic Sea area (Article 24). Article 20 of the Helsinki Convention stipulates special obligations of the European Commission (*inter alia*): – to keep the implementation of the Convention under continuous observation – to make recommendations on measures relating to the purposes of the Convention – to promote scientific and technological research.

The Oslo and Paris Conventions also stipulate (Art. 8) that the parties must establish programmes of scientific or technical research, the results of which have to be transmitted to the other parties.

In general, all parties to the above-mentioned conventions are obliged to acquire data on the state of the sea and to operate a monitoring system to ensure the earliest possible assessment of current levels of marine pollution. Such monitoring can be achieved by exploiting data derived from satellite observations on water surface temperatures (i.e. AVHRR on NOAA 1-9; ATSR on ERS-1 and ERS-2; AATSR on Envisat), on chlorophyll levels (i.e. SeaWiFS on Seastar; MERIS on Envisat) and on oil spills (i.e. instruments on ERS-1, ERS-2 and Envisat; Radarsat; HRV on SPOT; TM on Landsat).

86/85 EEC Council Decision of 6 March 1986 Establishing a Community Information System for the Control and Reduction of Pollution caused by the Spillage of Hydrocarbons and Other Harmful Substances at Sea.

By this decision, the provision of an information system was established to provide competent authorities in the Member States with the data required for the control and reduction of the pollution caused by the spillage of hydrocarbons and other harmful substances at sea. In the case of accidents, the quantity of oil pollution can be assessed using remote sensing satellites (e.g. ERS-1 and ERS-2; Envisat; RADARSAT; SPOT; LANDSAT) though for this technique is not suitable for monitoring chronic pollution.

B. Inland water pollution

- Convention of 1992 on the Protection and Use of Transboundary Water Courses and International Lakes. The objective of this treaty, which the European Union has ratified, is to protect the environment from the adverse effects of human use of transboundary waters. There is a general obligation on the parties to take all appropriate measures to protect, control and reduce any transboundary input, which is defined as “any significant adverse effect on the environment resulting from a change in the conditions of transboundary waters caused by human activity”.
- Convention of 1976 for the Protection of the Rhine against Chemical Pollution The parties to this convention are France, Germany, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Switzerland and the European Union. The aim of this convention is to improve the quality of the waters of the Rhine by regulating discharges into it. The parties are required to monitor all discharges and to inform the other parties if a sudden increase in pollution is detected or an accident occurs which seriously threatens the quality of the Rhine’s water (Articles 8, 10 and 11).

II.1.1.2 EU Geospatial and Environmental Information Needs

Document 1: Policy Assessment [47], **Document 2: EO Contribution** [48].

Reports issued jointly by JRC-SAI and DGXII-D, 1998.

The report assesses the potential role of satellite data in fulfilling the information needs arising from the policies of the European Union. It also attempts to identify possible “pull effect” of EU policies on future EO missions, focusing on issues with strong geospatial or environmental components.

Five key-policy areas were investigated as Case Studies:

Case 1: Regional development prioritising Spatial Planning. Satellite data have started to have an impact on land-cover/land use and generation of urban statistics. The former topic affects inland waters and coastal zones. Subjects of concerns are environmental protection, shoreline

displacement, and other coastal processes. Human activities such as construction and water management are also affected.

Case 2: Land resources management prioritising Agriculture. DGVI is the most active user of satellite derived EO information within the Commission (crop yield, monitoring, fraud control). The coastal zone, rivers and lakes are affected by emission of nitrogen and other organic compounds from agriculture, causing water pollution.

Case 3: Environmental conventions. EU has endorsed a number of conventions related to pollution issues, conservation of biological diversity, energy and climate issues. Many of the conventions directly or indirectly affect coastal zones, marine habitat and freshwater resources. Climate change will have long-term impact on parameters such sea level, sea temperature and extreme wave height. Biological diversity requires protection of marine habitat, coastal ecosystems, river/lake ecosystems, and wetlands.

Case 4. Environmental indicators: tools to measure progress towards long-term sustainability. Directly measurable quantities are needed to establish statistics on ground- and surface water resources, waste water management, degradation of coastal zones due to pollutants from rivers, direct pollution of the sea such as oil spills, and coastal erosion. Biodiversity requires estimation of habitats and quantification of water quality. Specific indicators from Eurostat [33], relevant for the coastal zone are:

- eutrophication
- over-fishing
- development along shore
- discharges of heavy metals
- oil pollution
- halogenated organic compounds

For water pollution and water resources the following indicators are listed:

- use of nitrate and phosphate (N+P) (eutrophication equivalent)
- groundwater abstraction
- pesticides used per hectare of utilised agriculture area
- nitrogen used per hectare of utilised agriculture area
- water treated / water collected
- emissions of organic matter as BOD
- index of heavy metal emissions to water

Case 5: Security and Risks & Hazards. Impact of natural hazards can be very severe in coastal zones such as landslides, river floods and tsunamis. EO data can contribute in surveillance of oil spill pollution, monitoring and assessment of floods and flood damage including effects of extreme wave heights. EO-data can also contribute in the mitigation of effects of earthquakes, volcanoes and forest fires. These hazards can affect coastal zones and inland waters in specific cases. Remote sensing has a valuable role in defining the baseline conditions against which the impact of natural disasters can be evaluated, even if remote sensing cannot play a very helpful operational role during the evolution of the disaster.

Summary:

Information from EO data are primarily land cover maps, classification, and land cover changes of areas which include coastal zones or inland waters. Additionally, coastline and topographic changes, and areas covered by floods can be mapped by EO data. There are specification of requirements to spatial resolution, which is high: from 1-10 m and upwards, spatial coverage (local, regional, European) and repeat periods (e.g. monthly or yearly). Eutrophication (algal bloom) and oil spills are listed specifically as “parameters” which can be derived from EO data, but without quantitative requirement. For climate change issues, several global scale parameters will have long-term impact on the coasts such as sea level change (which includes extreme wave height), sea temperature, ocean circulation, biomass, winds and sea ice. No quantitative requirements are stated for these parameters.

II.1.1.3 Reports from EEA and related Topic Centres**A. EEA Topic Centre on Marine and Coastal Environment****Annual summary report 1996**, Guilio Izzo, 1996 [45]

The report lists the fifteen European directives and required monitoring parameter for marine and coastal environments. According to this list, the directives prescribe measuring salinity, oxygen, transparency, pH, temperature, colour, suspended material, hydrocarbons, organo-halogenated substances, organo-phosphoric compounds, carbon tetrachloride, DDT, PCP, aldrin, dieldrin, endrin, isodrin, saxitoxin, BOD, COD, total P, total N, NO₃, coliforms, thermo-tolerant coli bacteria, faecal streptococcus, and heavy metals. The major areas of concern: coastal pollution, eutrophication, over-exploitation of resources, long-term effects of climate change and sea-level rise. The urgent environmental issues: contaminants, nutrients and eutrophication, litter, fisheries, mariculture, habitats and health of ecosystems.

The report implicitly indicates that standardised data quality control procedure is not yet established in the EC/EEA. The data comparability is an unsolved problem in the EC/EEA. The report stresses the need for EC a harmonisation of measurable parameter nomenclature, analytical methods, data precision and time / space resolution.

Summary:

The annual report from the EEA Topic Centre on Marine and Coastal Environment indicates that along with defining major areas of concern and urgent environmental issues, the European community has identified through several directives a number of determinants characterising water quality in marine and coastal environments. However, the determinant nomenclature remains rather incomplete, and unharmonised among EU member countries. Requirements for data comparability, precision, and time/space resolution are still largely undefined. Data provision methods recommended by directives rely exclusively on analytical techniques and do not currently envisage any remote sensing involvement.

B. EEA's Topic Centre on Inland Waters**Surface water quality monitoring**, Kristensen and Bogestrand, 1996 [50]

This is an overview of water quality monitoring activities in rivers, lakes, reservoirs, coastal and open marine areas in the 15 European Union Member States and Iceland and Norway. Water quality variables are grouped into broad categories: basic variables, organic pollution indicators,

suspended particular matter, indicators of eutrophication, indicators of acidification, specific major ions, metals, organic micro-pollutants, indicators of radioactivity, microbiological indicator organism, and biological indicators. For each country monitoring programmes are specified reflecting directives, responsible institutions, broad categories of variables measured, sampling frequency, period of operation, and geographical coverage. The report explicitly illustrates that both the variety of variables and sampling frequency are far from being standardised for the EU countries, Iceland, and Norway: they dramatically differ and obviously are unharmonised. No scientifically justified criteria are mentioned regarding neither the nomenclature of monitored parameters, precision required nor spatial/temporal resolution of surveillance data.

Requirements for water monitoring, Nixon *et al.*, 1996 [53]

The Report encapsulates inventories of ongoing water monitoring activities in European countries and is intended to set up a baseline for EEA for a further developing European water policy. As prescribed by existing and proposed EU legislation and international agreements (cited in the report), requirements regarding nomenclature and collection procedures of water quality parameters (called determinants) for groundwater, surface, coastal and marine environments are tabulated along with the information on methodologies, monitoring frequency and sites location/density, data quality control. Issues of data treatment, data storage/organisation into data bases are equally detailed.

The report states that four types (i.e., use-related, industry sector, substance, product) of directives, are employed by the EU. European legislation requiring monitoring of inland water encompasses twenty directives/decisions the objectives of which are summarised in the Report. Additionally, more than forty international agreements (specified in the report) regulate practices of monitoring of inland waters. The requirements specified both in directives and agreements have been designed independently from each other, and hence are not only non-standardised but even unharmonised. The sampling frequency prescribed in various directives and international agreements is highly variable, and it is unclear whether any statistical/scientific considerations derived with appropriate reference to quantitatively assessed risk were at the basis of these prescriptions. In most cases, the requirements/agreements do not specify analytical quality control standards.

There are dramatic variations in requirements for sample location specified in directives/international agreements. In most cases they are as general as “near shore zone, designated areas, areas affected by discharge, fixed stations”. The same applies to the sample frequency: depending on a concrete directive/agreement, it varies between continuously/daily and once in a year or even, e.g., one year and then 4 or 8 years. In some instances, preferable timing/season information is complemented, such as “in the morning”, “August-September”, “winter” “late winter-early spring”, etc.

The report accommodates a tabulated summary of recommended analytical methods stipulated in directives. Almost all of them (with few exceptions) are laboratory-based, and many parameters are suggested to be measured by different methods depending on a concrete directive. None of the directives prescribes utilisation of remote sensing methods for this purpose.

The report reveals that there is a particularly unsatisfactory situation with the analytical precision requirements. It applies both to directives and international agreements. Frequently, they are not even defined. However, when defined, they are expressed as percentage of reference concentration in concrete directories which, as mentioned above, are generally not harmonised.

International water databases, France *et al.*, 1996 [44]

This report catalogues and summarises the data contained in databases associated with International monitoring programmes which are relevant to the EEA's needs, including those to support EC legislation, European and outside Europe conventions-related. Information is provided on each of the data sources together with the type of data included, countries and water bodies (generally, rivers, lakes, estuaries, marine and coastal waters, groundwater) covered and the determinants measured.

The report identified the programmes specifically focused on the issue of water quality: four for European rivers, seven for European lakes, two for estuaries, nine for coastal waters, two for groundwater. The following categorisation of determinants is used: aesthetic (colour, floating materials, surfactants), chemicals (acidity, calcium, chlorides, cyanides, fluorides, etc.), metals (aluminium, arsenic, boron, zinc, etc.), microbiological (coliforms, salmonella, total bacteria, etc.), nutrients (ammonia, nitrogen, etc.), organic pollution (BOD, COD, organic carbon, dissolved oxygen, etc.), physical and physicochemical (flow, level, pH, temperature, etc.), radioactive (alpha emission, caesium, strontium, etc.), synthetic organics (PCB, DDT, BHC, HCH, etc.).

The main output from this report is a searchable electronic database of the identified international databases for a rapid identification of geographical areas, type of sampling sites (lake station, sediment station, fish station, river gauging station, thermo-pluviometric station, water quality station, etc.) determinants measured and temporal coverage of the data.

This report explicitly illustrates a great diversity in the composition of data provided from different programmes (nomenclature of determinants, temporal coverage (the starting year of monitoring), and number of sites (i.e., spatial resolution of data). It could be concluded from the report that nothing definite could be said regarding the requirements on data precision, and temporal/spatial distribution. Moreover, obviously no harmonisation exists among the existing programmes in terms of nomenclature of water quality parameters to be measured.

European Freshwater monitoring design, Nixon, 1996 [55]

This publication is dedicated to design concepts and establishment of a European freshwater monitoring network to obtain timely, quantitative and comparable information on the status of inland waters (groundwater, lakes/reservoirs, rivers and estuaries) from all EEA Member States so that valid temporal and spatial comparisons can be made and so that key environmental problems associated with Europe's inland waters can be defined, quantified and monitored. Environmental problems are categorised:

- climate change: effects on hydrological cycle, sea level rise (salinisation of freshwaters), effects on aquatic ecosystems
- acidification
- freshwater management: water availability, water quality (groundwater pollution, eutrophication, organic pollution (including pathogens), acidification), physical changes

Existing national lake monitoring programmes include the most common variables: pH, conductivity, alkalinity, total organic carbon, nitrate, four major cations (potassium, calcium, magnesium, and sodium) and anions (sulphate and chloride), and various aluminium fractions. Some monitoring programmes also include measurements of total phosphorus, total nitrogen and ammoniac nitrogen. The extent of acidification is also assessed using of various biological indicators such as zoobenthos, phytoplankton, and fish. Bottom fauna (invertebrates), macrophytes and fish are also studied in some of the lake monitoring programmes. Groundwater quality parameters can be divided into following groups: descriptive parameters (e.g. conductivity, pH, turbidity, odour); major ions; additional parameters (e.g. DOC, boron, fluorine,

cyanide, hydrocarbon benzene); heavy metals; organic substances including chlorinated solvents (e.g. trichloroethene; tetrachloroethene; 1,1,1 trichloroethane; 1,1-dichloroethene); pesticides (herbicides, insecticides). No standardisation exists so far in the nomenclature of measurable parameters of fresh waters. No generalised conceptions are worked out so far for setting up spatial/temporal resolution requirements. However, some of the ideas about the number of sampling stations is suggested in the report. It is believed that the information required for characterising rivers, lakes and groundwater falls into the following items: ecological quality; acidification; nutrient status; pesticides; heavy metals; organic pollution; pathogens; water availability; physical intervention.

The report suggest a list of primary and secondary determinables required for river and lake monitoring networks: Biological indicators (macro-invertebrates, fish, phytoplankton, chlorophyll); Descriptive determinants (dissolved oxygen, pH, alkalinity, conductivity, temperature, suspended solids); Flow (flows, levels); Additional determinants (biochemical oxygen demand, chemical oxygen demand, total organic carbon, Secchi disc, aluminium fractions); Nutrients (total phosphorus, soluble reactive phosphorus, nitrate, nitrite, ammonia, organic nitrogen, total nitrogen), Major ions (calcium, sodium, potassium, magnesium, chloride, sulphate, bicarbonate), heavy metals (cadmium, mercury); pesticides; other synthetic organic substances (PAH, PCBs); microbes (total and faecal coliforms, faecal streptococci, salmonella, entero-viruses); radionuclides (total alpha and beta activity Caesium 137).

The report explicitly indicates that the range of measuring techniques does not include remote sensing means. These techniques are:

Physical: colour, turbidity, suspended solids, conductivity, pressure, depth, level, density, temperature, flow rate, volumetric flow,

Electrochemical: pH, ammonia, nitrate, bromide, calcium, carbon dioxide, chloride, chlorine, metals, cyanide, fluoride, REDOX, dissolved oxygen,

Colorimetry: ammonia, nitrate, nitrite, phosphate, chloride, fluoride, sulphate, metals, manganese, phenols,

High temperature and low temperature methods: organic carbon measurement.

Respirometry: BOD and toxicity.

Gas chromatography and HPLC: for phenols and organics.

The precision of the above analytical methods is basically 5-10 %, with occasional departure to lower and higher outer limits.

European freshwater monitoring: Summary of network design, Nixon *et al.*, 1996 [54]

The report identifies the subjects of concern: Management of freshwater in terms of availability and quality (for example, groundwater pollution, eutrophication and organic pollution including pathogens), and in terms of physical changes of water bodies. It also identifies the existing national monitoring networks, lays out in general terms the requirement for a pan-European monitoring system, enumerates the directives and international agreements bearing on the fresh surface waters monitoring, and cites the exchange of information decisions. The report outlines the concept of the proposed unified network, as well as the perspectives and work programmes of European co-operation in this area. The report does not contain any information on the measurable parameter nomenclature, analytical methods, data precision and time / space resolution.

Groundwater monitoring in Europe, Koreimann *et al.*, 1996 [49]

The report gives an overview of the current groundwater quality and quantity networks and monitoring procedures within the European Environment Agency (EEA) area. The information

for this overview was obtained through questionnaires. The number of measured water quality determinants varies from 15 to 106 between the monitoring networks. 'Basic' programmes often include between 14 and 51 determinants. The determinants appear to be adapted to national circumstances and at present cannot be readily compared at a European level. The parameters observed can be divided into 3 groups. The first group covers all substances necessary for a general characterisation of hydro-chemical properties (e.g., conductivity, pH, dissolved oxygen) or general pollution situations (nutrients, TOC, DOC). The second group provides an Austrian-wide survey (e.g. heavy metals, hydrocarbons, AOX). The third unit covers substances with high eco-toxicological relevance like pesticides, benzene, PAH. National networks are succinctly characterised, and this survey indicates a great discrepancy in the nomenclature of measured parameters, and practices sampling adopted in the EU.

Annual Summary Report 1996, Lack T.J., [52]

The report informs on the work programme, projects and tasks. It also describes the Topic Centre activity progress: workshop in Madrid (CEDEX), completion of a series of reports (Surface Water Quality Monitoring (1996), Requirements for Water Monitoring (1996), Water Quality of Large Rivers (1996), Surface Water Quality Monitoring (1995). A monograph on Groundwater Quality and Quantity was planned to be published in 1997. The report provides no concrete data on the nomenclature of parameters to be measured nor on the accuracy, time-spatial resolution, analytical methods, methods of observation.

Summary:

The reports from the EEA Topic Centres on Inland and Ground Waters clearly indicate that due to numerous directives and international agreements, EU countries have defined an extensive list of parameters prone to be measured on a regular basis and entered into a specialised database, whose architecture and design development is still underway. At the same time, the requirements for the data compatibility, precision, and time/space resolution are frequently vague, and in many cases non-existent. The precision requirements, when specified, are mostly the lowest detectable levels of concentrations of chemical substances/compounds achievable for analytical methods conducted in laboratories. As a result, the data provision methods recommended by directives rely almost exclusively on analytical techniques and do not currently envisage any remote sensing involvement. Moreover, it is obvious that remote sensing tools would not be able (neither presently nor in the future) to provide the assessment of many of the established parameters. In particular, the stringent precision requirements, which in some cases do not seem to be scientifically substantiated, cannot be met with any known remote sensing method.

II.1.2 Requirements from the CEO-funded Customer Segment Studies

A number of interests and requirements - some in common and some in particular - have been identified by assessing the reports from the customer segment workshops held in 1997 and 1998. These studies concerned insurance industries, travel and tourism, civil engineering, city development, environment protection, water companies, shipping and navigation and agricultural sector (sections 1.2.1-1.2.9). In general, one notes a lack of knowledge and information concerning the capability of remote sensing for, e.g., flooding risk assessment, for monitoring of suspended sediment (concentration and transport), for preventing and reacting against pollution by harmful substances (accidental and chronic), as well as for estimation of the trophic statute of water and ecosystems; this lack concerns the actors, products and service providers in the above fields. All reports focus on products (e.g., maps) directly derived from EO data and not in

terms of EO-derived parameters that can be merged with other information sources into decision systems.

II.1.2.1 Insurance companies

Z. Stott *et al.*, Logica ltd, UK [63]

In order to evaluate risks (natural hazards and pollution liability), to clean up litigation and to calculate insurance amount, insurance companies are interested in information on: 1) Sea state and weather which can delay ships and ease litigation, 2) Coastal flooding which is mostly caused by the wrong combination of tides, wind and waves, 3) Algal blooms and natural pollution that affect mariculture and fishery industries, 4) Human wastes such as oil spill, discharge of chemical substances. The information required consists mostly in statistics concerning environmental conditions for risk assessment, but also, in some case, in quasi real-time data for managing insurance contract after a disaster (e.g., flooding). For each application, relevant sensors have been identified (SAR, altimeter, ocean colour, high-resolution optical) as well as needs for real-time or archive data.

For marine insurance, the required information is: waves/wind statistics, monthly seasonal and inter-annual changes in SST, prevailing current stream and eddies, changes in sea level. Until custom-built clusters of satellites are launched to provide a reliable real-time warning of impending disasters at sea, satellites can make only a modest contribution to day-to-day surveillance operations. The strength of present-day EO is the database of information that is now available on average and extreme conditions (statistics on waves), high-resolution images of oil slicks and effluent discharges reveal a potential serious threat to all those who rely on clean beaches and uncontaminated seafood.

Relevant real-time information desired from EO data includes: storm centre from SST, detection of harmful algae blooms, ships illegally discharging oil, as well as monitoring of floods using SAR. The insurance company requirements for EO-derived information are summarised in Table 3 below.

II.1.2.2 Travel and tourism industry

D. Slogett, QW, Government Systems Division, UK [62]

One the main issue for travel and tourism industry is to reassure potential customers on the safety and state of pollution of leisure areas, as well as to identify new recreational sites. Five application areas for EO data have been identified: promotion, damage limitation, change detection, sustainable development of tourism, and supporting claims for compensation of travellers. Specific concerns are geomorphologic condition of a coast (e.g., change detection, beach profile, erosion), sanity of inter-tidal zones, change in water quality, exposure to climatic event, flooding risk. However the workshop report rapidly focuses on very high-resolution (VHR) satellite (KVR1000, SPOT, IRS-1C) and derived base map products for promotion and commercials. Two relevant products have been identified:

- Flood mapping product based on integrated SAR (ERS, RadarSat) and high resolution optical (SPOT, IRS-1C) data.
- Water quality monitoring product: weekly update of water quality from satellite (SeaWiFS, OCTS) during the summer season. Estimation of water clarity (diving clubs)

Other subjects of concern have been expressed but not answered in term of EO capability: aftermath of tidal waves, industrial accidents and man-made disasters, such as oil spills. Leisure and Tourism has not identified that satellite derived environmental information (e.g. surface

temperatures in a sea area adjacent to bathing beaches, information about wind and waves on surfing beaches, water quality and algal bloom images near coastal resorts) offers a potential route for advertising clean areas and providing a commercial pressure to protect the environment.

Table 4. Summary of the requirements to EO data identified in from insurance companies.

Hazard	EO product	Sensor type	Professional task
Floods	Flood footprint maps	SAR	Risk assessment (historical footprints for input to geographical risk management systems) Claims validation Logistics planning by loss adjusters (real time maps showing the extent of a flooded area within 12 hours of flood on a 1:25,000 map)
Coastal flooding	Snapshot of prevailing conditions	Altimeter, Scatterometer, SAR	Loss control/early warning Logistics planning/loss adjusting
	Sea level	Altimeter	Prediction Risk assessment
	Wind/wave atlases	Altimeter	Prediction Risk assessment (e.g. "once in century" events)
Challenges			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • frequent revisit and fast processing to meet real time requirement • improved vertical resolution of digital elevation models in key areas 			
Storms	Wind/wave atlases	Altimeter	Prediction Risk assessment (e.g. "once in century" events) Loss control
	Snapshot of prevailing wind / wave conditions	Altimeter, Scatterometer	Loss control (avoidance) Claims validation
Challenges			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to increase density of measurements for loss control and claims validation 			
Pollution	Oil spill maps	SAR	Predictions (long term statistics and trends) Short term forecasts/early warning Real time logistics planning Input to geographical risk assessment systems (historical footprints, hazard zoning maps) Claims validation
	Algal bloom maps	Ocean colour	Predictions (long term statistics and trends) Short term forecasts/early warning Real time logistics planning Input to geographical risk assessment systems (historical footprints, hazard zonation maps) Claims validation
Challenges			
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • to increase density of measurements (particularly for SAR data) 			

II.1.2.3 Environmental Protection of Land Resources

Whitelaw *et al.*, ESYS ltd [64]

The requirements expressed by this customer segment concern the estimation of the risk for pollution by harmful substances, monitoring of water quality in lakes, rivers and reservoirs including biological activity, eutrophication, sediment concentration, ecosystem health. Major lessons learned with respect to inland water state that EO data is both valuable and complementary to existing *in situ* measurements for monitoring quality and quantity. On the

other hand, there is no systematic collection doctrine and the resolution is too coarse. Also, future opportunities will not be achievable without the use of EO methods. There is an extensive analysis relating areas-of interest with scales of EO value and type of product for environmental monitoring, and they list examples of existing projects using EO instrumentation. Proposed product types are:

- National scale NDVI products with scale from 1:1,000,000 to 1:100,000; these should apply in developing bio-diversity indicators and monitoring desertification.
- Map updating facility to provide monitoring changes of ecosystems.
- Modelling product/service to allow assessment of environmental damage or changes of stream-flows and wetlands.
- Multi-scale products to identify distribution of ecosystems and monitoring effect of irrigation.
- Visualisation product to monitor soil erosion effects.

II.1.2.4 Water companies

Simpson, EOS ltd, UK [61]

This customer segment is composed of organisations involved in the provision and disposal of water, freshwater distribution, assessment of quality and volume and wastewater management. 25 professional tasks have been identified and EO-evaluated. Five tasks were selected as having most potential for use of EO-derived products, i.e., base maps, digital elevation models, subsidence, rural land cover and urban run-off. These five tasks require typically very high-resolution sensors, and stereoscopic or interferometric capabilities. They do not include direct evaluation of water quality by remote sensing. Other tasks are related to phytoplankton in lakes and reservoirs, suspended sediments and flood extent. However they were not selected because of the inadequacy between the sampling requirements and the temporal coverage of operating EO-satellite. Other tasks related to plume dispersion patterns, wetland extent and salt-marsh land cover have not been selected because of a limited market size or the unavailability of funding, although EO has an important role to play in monitoring such parameters. No prospective view have been developed to consider future sensors capability.

II.1.2.5 Maritime Industry

Graff *et al.*, British Maritime Technology, Ltd & ARGOOS [59]

For the shipping industry, two EO products were selected: Bathymetry mapping and an Integrated Global Wave Climate Database. The first for Port Engineering and Oil and Gas companies as potential leading customers and the second for Coastal Engineering in similar position. Several other products such as Global Digital Surface Currents Atlas, Ship Traffic Monitoring or Mapping of Inter Tidal Zones were identified but not selected because of various incompatibilities.

II.1.2.6 Land Navigation/Digital Mapping Industry

Rosenholm *et al.*, OM & M, UK [60]

Future, upgraded digital map should relate also to various hydrological features like rivers, lakes, waterways and coastline. However, to enable a smoother integration of Earth Observation based imagery into industrial products, there is still a need for further research in automatic extraction of map features from digital data.

II.1.2.7 Town/city/local government departments

Galaup *et al.*, Scot Conseil, France [58]

There is a chance for near-future utilisation of EO sensing with relevant map scale of 1:1000-1:5000. Two general classes of products are needed:

- *Thematic products*: Digital map in natural colour for support in specific information, e.g., monitoring environment, water bodies, civil protection
- *Standard products*: Standard maps for regular, long-term mapping

II.1.2.8 Civil Engineering Industry

Brucciani *et al.*, Smith System Engineering Ltd., UK [57]

For civil engineering, two example-products associated with water characterisation are proposed:

- *Very high resolution (VHR) map* of 1:5000 to 1:10000 scale for the following: water catchment modelling, water flux and flood risk modelling, dam planning, coastal zone management, etc.
- *Urban ground subsidence map* using radar interferometry for large-scale area assessment, e.g., earthquake, landslide, and sand dune migration.

Conclusions refer to the use of EO maps in Pre/Feasibility study and Concept design of a civil engineering project. Targeted scale should be of 1-meter resolution. Recommendations refer to marketing, educational and shared cost actions to be competent for this industry.

II.1.2.9 Agribusiness

No requirements are relevant for this study

Summary:

Five of the nine customer segment reports discuss issues related to coastal and inland waters. However, they mainly focus on final end-user remote sensing product, and thus reduce the scope of application of remote sensing techniques to mapping and map products, and the scope of sensors to high spatial resolution instruments. They do not consider remote sensing data as a complementary source of information to be cross-analysed with other type of environmental information. Nevertheless, they point out some useful geophysical parameters, such as chlorophyll concentration, suspended sediment and water level, and which satellite data could be used to obtain these parameters. However, no indication of quantitative requirements to the accuracy of measurements and the sampling strategy is provided.

II.1.3 Requirements from EU-funded research and development projects

II.1.3.1 Environment and Climate Programme 1994-1998.

Theme 3: Space Techniques Applied to Environmental Monitoring and Research

Section 3.1:

CLEAN SEAS - “European marginal seas - a study of pollution monitoring from space” [71]. The project identifies the subjects of concern: *marine pollution, environmental risk*. It also confines itself to the parameters that could be remotely measured: meteorological, oceanographic, chlorophyll concentration, surface reflectivity, surface thermal emission, surface brightness temperature, surface roughness. No information is available so far as to measurement precision, spatial/temporal resolution, etc., nor on the retrieval algorithms that are to be developed for inferring the above parameters from space data.

COASTIOOC - “Development of algorithms for the use of ocean colour data in coastal waters to detect optically active material and assess biological processes” [72]. The project identifies the subjects of concern: *ecological status* of coastal marine waters: the impact of *eutrophication* and anthropogenic *sediment transport*; study of *red tides*. It also confines itself to the parameters that could be remotely measured: water absorption, water scattering, water attenuation, and concentrations of chlorophyll, suspended matter, and coloured dissolved organics. No information is available so far as the measurement precision, spatial/temporal resolution, etc., nor on the retrieval algorithms that are to be developed for inferring the above parameters from space data.

SALMON - “Satellite Remote Sensing for Lake Monitoring” [97]. Major areas of concern: *lake pollution, maintenance of water quality*. The measurable parameters are to be identified as a result of the project implementation.

Section 3.2:

MMST - “Medium scale surface temperature mission” [86]. Major areas of concern: *soil and plant energy budget, drought- and illness-driven plant stress, frosted agricultural areas*. The measurable parameters: land and water surface temperature. No information is available so far as to precision measurements, spatial/temporal resolution, etc., either on the retrieval algorithms, which are to be developed for inferring the above parameters from space data.

“Multispectral high resolution system” [87].

The project identifies the subjects of concern: *environmental status and changes*. It also confines itself to the parameters that could be remotely measured: upwelling radiance, vegetation index, water quality parameters (unspecified). No information is available so far as to precision measurements, spatial/temporal resolution, etc., either on the retrieval algorithms, which are to be developed for inferring the above parameters from space data.

Section 3.3/CEO:

FLOODGEN - “Flood risk reduction by space-borne recognition of indicators of excess runoff generating areas” [81]. The project identifies the subjects of concern: *runoff-driven floods, soil erosion, spread of fertilisers and pollutants; forecast of runoff; water quality deterioration; permeability and crusting of soils; vegetation cover changes; human intervention*. It also

confines itself to the parameters which could be remotely measured: vegetation index, sub-basin shapes, basin morphometry, soil moisture Q_w . No information is available so far as to precision measurements, spatial/temporal resolution, etc.

RESSAC - “Remote sensing support for analysis of coasts” [96].

The project identifies the subjects of concern: *coast preservation and protection*. It also confines itself to the parameters which could be remotely measured: *metocean parameters*: sea surface state, wind; *morphological parameters*: bathymetry, suspended minerals concentration, delineation of shoreline dynamics, *watershed land use*: vegetation index, soil moisture. No information is available so far as to precision measurements, spatial/temporal resolution, etc., either on the retrieval algorithms, which are to be developed for inferring the above parameters from space data [C7].

COASTMON - “Metocean and coastal zone monitoring in harbour regions using satellite radar” [73]. The project identifies the subjects of concern: *harbour traffic, navigational safety, coastal management, pollution (oil spills) monitoring*. It also confines itself to the parameters which could be remotely measured: wind, waves, identification & delineation of current fronts, eddies, and shallow-water bathymetry. No information is available so far as to precision measurements, spatial/temporal resolution, etc., either on the retrieval algorithms, which are to be developed for inferring the above parameters from space data. The project held local user meetings in Ireland, Norway, and The Netherlands to discuss requirements for coastal monitoring data from microwave/SAR satellites. In these meetings users expressed interest for marine colour and temperature data. Where reference is made to temporal and spatial scale, these are generally consistent with other results.

ABDMAP - “Concerted action on algal boom detection, monitoring and prediction” [65]. The project identifies the subjects of concern: *eutrophication, detection, monitoring, prediction of algal blooms, and impact on shellfish production, health hazard, and tourism*. Although not explicitly cited, chlorophyll concentration is the basic remotely inferred parameter within this project. No information is available so far as to precision measurements, spatial/temporal resolution, etc., either on the retrieval algorithms, which are to be developed for inferring the above parameters from space data.

“**Oil spill detection** and monitoring in the European Union Mediterranean and South West Atlantic coastal areas” [92]. The project identifies the subjects of concern: *Environment damages, Oil spills, High-risk areas*. Within this project, identification and delineation of oil spills (scatterometer signal intensity - surface roughness) will be accomplished. No information is available on the measurement precision, spatial/temporal resolution, etc., nor on the retrieval algorithms that are to be developed for inferring the above parameters from space data.

EON2000 - “Earth observation for Natura 2000” [78]. The major area of concern: *Conservation of natural habitats*. Neither the parameter nor retrieval algorithms, spatial/temporal resolution are specified.

ASTIMwR - “Application of space techniques to the integrated management of a river basin water resources” [66]. Major areas of concern: *endangered water resources; over-exploitation of aquifer areas*. Parameters to be measured: evapo-transpiration, soil moisture, aquifer resources (groundwater quantity), wetland area status and dynamics, irrigation system maps. No information is available on the measurement precision, spatial/temporal resolution, etc., nor on

the retrieval algorithms that are to be developed for inferring the above parameters from space data.

NOAH - “New opportunities for altimetry in hydrology” [89]. Major areas of concern: *risk of flood, flood prevention*. The measurable parameters are relief, slopes, catchment area (land-use maps, soil moisture), risk maps. Again, no information is available so far as to measurement precision, spatial/temporal resolution, etc., either on the retrieval algorithms that are to be developed for inferring the above parameters from space data.

DESIMA – “Decision support for integrated coastal zone management” [76] The project aims to supporting Coastal Zone Management applications through an improved integration and use of various information sources and information providing tools. In this context, the project intends to increase and broaden the use of existing and future EO data by integration of EO and non-apce data and by enlarging the user & customer base of EO data.

ICAMS – “Integrated Coastal Analysis and Monitoring System” [83]. This project primary objective is to bridge the gap between the potential user community for information on water quality and the means for delivering that information from currently planned EO missions. This is achieved through developing, demonstrating, and evaluating, the Integrated Coastal Analysis and Monitoring System (ICAMS) which meets end user need and is based as far as possible on existing components and technologies. ICAMS will provide an integrated engineering and scientific system to monitor temperature, turbidity, chlorophyll concentration, and primary production from multiple EO data sources and coincident standard surface measurements. The resulting maps of water quality that will be produced by ICAMS will be used in comparison with maps and data of human exploitation of these same waters. Such a comparison will provide a decision aid for those end-users who are managing the often conflicting demands of human exploitation that affect coastal water quality.

II.1.3.2 Marine Science and Technology Programme 1994 - 1998

BIOGAP - “Biodiversity and genetics of algal populations” [69]. The major areas of concern: ecosystem stability/resilience, maintenance of sustainable biodiversity, of biota in coastal zones, in benthic communities; population genetics. The parameters are not specified, but presumably among others: remote sensing spectral reflectance, concentrations of phytoplankton chlorophyll, auxiliary pigments, bacterioplankton, zooplankton, macrophyte stands, vegetation index, wetland area. No information is available about the measurement precision, spatial/temporal resolution, etc. or about the retrieval algorithms that are to be developed for inferring the above parameters from EO data.

BIOCOLOR - “Ocean colour for the determination of water column biological processes” [68]. The major area of concern is status dynamics of marine phytoplankton community. It also confines itself to the parameters that could be remotely measured: water absorption, water scattering, water attenuation, concentrations of chlorophyll, suspended matter, coloured dissolved organics, remote sensing reflectance, spatial/temporal distributions of phytoplankton, water surface temperature, salinity, phytoplankton taxonomy. Again, no information is available about the measurement precision, spatial/temporal resolution, etc. or about the retrieval algorithms that are to be developed for inferring the above parameters from EO data.

C-star – “Coastal sediment transport assessment using synthetic aperture radar” [74]. The project aims at combining map the bottom topography of shallow seas derived from SAR imagery, with

morphological models in order to study sediment transport in morphologically very dynamic areas. An improved method is applied to generate dense time series of depth maps of selected, morphologically dynamic sites. Then, these depth time series are used to adjust sediment transport models. The results are evaluated to determine how this procedure can increase our knowledge of the morphological processes in these dynamic sites, and what its potential is for monitoring and predicting morphological changes local authorities managing coastal zones

DIADEM – “Development of advanced data assimilation systems for operational monitoring and forecasting of the north Atlantic and Nordic seas” [77]. In this project, assimilation of EO products such as altimeter, ocean colour and SST products is under concern.

EuroROSE – “European radar ocean sensing” [80]. The main objective of EuroROSE is the development of a transportable methodology for monitoring and forecasting winds, waves, water level and currents in limited areas (typical extent 40 by 40 km), such as coastal and port approach areas. The methodology is a combination of area covering remote sensed data and high resolution numerical forecast models including data assimilation, co-ordinated with the Vessel Traffic Services at ports and coastal monitoring centres. No user requirements is collected or explicitly mentioned in the project documents.

MFSPP – “Mediterranean forecasting system pilot project” [85]. The forecasting system designed in the project includes real-time assimilation of EO data. One of the objectives is to set up and test a near real time acquisition and processing system of remote sensing data such as altimeter, SST and ocean colour, for the Mediterranean sea. The system will be based on existing facilities and will serve as a prototype for a future operational system.

NICE – “Nitrogen cycling in estuaries” [88]. ELOISE project. The project study the fate of anthropogenic nitrogen discharged into estuaries and coastal waters. No quantitative user requirements is expressed in the project.

OIL-WATCH- “Oil spill detection and monitoring in the European Union Mediterranean and south west Atlantic coastal areas” [93].

Summary:

Analysis of general information presently available at web-sites on EU-funded projects that are being currently implemented in the area of space technique applications to environmental monitoring and research reveals several important features:

Firstly, they invariably address (although not completely cover) the topics of major concern identified by EEA for coastal zone, surface and groundwater environments. Secondly, the remotely sensed parameters relating to water environment parameters are not always explicitly specified the available documents.

Only few projects (e.g., ICAMS, COASTMON) give access to results of study on user requirements on their web-sites regarding the remotely assessed parameter precision and time/space resolution.

II.1.4 Requirements identified from ESA funded projects

II.1.4.1 Coastal Zones: A survey of data requirements of the operational community

ESA (European Space Agency), 1995 [42]

This document presents the results of the first ESA review of the potential requirements for remote sensing missions dedicated to the monitoring of natural processes and man-induced phenomena in the coastal zone and coastal waters, and in support of particular economic activities in these areas. The analysis of questionnaires centred around transport, environmental protection/preservation, mineral extraction, seafood, defence, building/construction/engineering, services, equipment sales, tourism and recreation, basic and strategic research, and hinterlands revealed the following statistically most significant requirements:

Time series: long and very long (one year to 20 and more)

Accuracy: mostly 1-10 %, but 0.1 % for biogeochemical parameters.

Spatial resolution: less than 500 m for shelf features, biogeochemical and hinterland parameters, 1-10 km for surface parameters.

Temporal resolution: 1-6 hours for sea surface fields, 1 day for biogeochemical and hinterland parameters.

Forecasting: 10-30 days.

Cross-relationship between spatial & temporal resolution: 10 km - \leq 1 day, <500 m - real-time and long-term off-line access

A schematic illustration of temporal and spatial characteristics of a variety of coastal zone parameters and processes (i.e., ocean damping, open ocean-shelf interactions, wave statistics, shelf current and circulation, waves and swells, storm surges, red tide and algae blooms, mesoscale fronts, eddies, pollution, estuarine tide, oil pollution, oil seepage, natural films, coral ecosystems, wetland biomass monitoring, coastal land use, estuarine fronts, marsh habitat, waterway status, long and short-term erosion, shallow water bathymetry, river marsh flooding) and orbital sensors feasibility (orbit cycle, revisiting and spatial resolution) is given.

II.1.4.2 The Earth Explorer Programme: The Science and Research Element of ESA

Future Earth Observation Programme, ESA, 1998 [43]

The report refers to environmental obligations of the European Union relevant for application of remote sensing. The conventions relevant for this study are within Marine Pollution, Water Courses and Conservation of Biodiversity. The report describes only the sensors and satellites can be useful within Marine Pollution. The need for higher resolution of EO data is pointed out as limitation in Conservation of Biodiversity. Monitoring of wetlands is described as theme where EO data can be useful. There is no specification of any parameters or measurement requirement.

II.1.4.3 Data User Programme

A. Pre-operational water and environment regional service

Contractor: IVM(NL), RSL (CH), MUMM (B), MD (NL)

Objectives: This project aims at preparing for the operational usage of MERIS onboard ENVISAT-1. Development of basic user-oriented tools for water quality assessment purposes, the products of which primarily will be based upon MOS data. The products will be specific to either of two regions: (1) the Belgian and Dutch coastal waters and (2) inland water-bodies in The Netherlands and Switzerland.

Deliverables: Algorithms and products definition, design of a regional service, demonstration products, generation of a demo Web site.

B. Bathymetry assessment demonstration

Contractor: ARGOSS (NL), UoG (B), WWK (B)

Objectives: To demonstrate the usefulness and cost effectiveness of SAR derived bathymetry for coastal management purposes and morphological studies. Collecting ERS SAR images and in-situ measurements and generation of depth maps on the target area off the Belgian coast. An existing Bathymetry Assessment System (BAS) implemented in the Netherlands will be used for data processing and map generation.

Deliverables: Depth maps of a selected site off Belgian coast, evaluation reports, dissemination material, implementation plan for future application.

Summary:

The statistical analysis performed by ESA based on the needs from the operational communities for remote sensing missions over the coastal zone and coastal waters reveals a broad framework for observation frequency, time series, accuracy, spatial and temporal resolution. The requirements to data are specified generally, as “sea surface fields”, “coast and shelf”, “biogeochemistry”, “hinterland”. In the Earth Explorer Programme, high-level issues relevant for the European Union are discussed and specific problem areas such as Marine Pollution are listed where EO data can become more important in the future. User requirement analysis can be found in the DUPs.

II.2 Synthesis of requirements to parameters from EO data

The information on requirements to environmental data in coastal and inland waters found in section 1 is organised in the following manner: In section 2.1, reference codes to directives, agreements and subjects of concern relevant for coastal zones and inland waters are defined. In section 2.2, the subjects of concern are then classified into categories. In section 2.3, the particular water quality and other environmental parameters are identified from the subjects of concern. The parameters are flagged according to their relevance in lakes/reservoirs, rivers and coastal waters, and according to the feasibility of remote sensing observation. The parameters are also linked to EU directives and agreements. In section 2.4, the water quality and environmental parameters which are derivable from remote sensing data are described more specifically.

II.2.1 Reference codes to directives and environmental agreements:

The reference codes for the most important directives are presented in Table 5.1 and 5.2. The codes for environmental agreements concerning the EU are shown in Table 5.3

Table 5.1 Directives addressing general issues.

Code	Themes	Directives
A	Conservation of wild birds	(79/409/EEC) (79/409/EEC)
B	Environmental impact assessment	(95/337/EEC) (95/337/EEC)
C	Protection of groundwater	(80/68/EEC) (80/68/EEC)
D	Habitats directive	(92/43/EEC) (92/43/EEC)
E	COMAH – Control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances	(96/82/EEC)

Table 5.2 Directives addressing specific issues.

Code	Themes	Directives
1	Surface water	(75/440/EEC)
2	Surface water	(79/869/EEC)
3	Exchange of information	(77/795/EEC) as amended by (86/574/EEC)
4	Freshwater Fish	(78/659/EEC) and (79/923/EEC) on shellfish
5	Drinking water	(80/778/EEC)
6	Bathing water	(76/160/EEC)
7	Dangerous Substances	(76/464/EEC) and daughter directives
8	Titanium dioxide	(82/883/EEC)
9	Urban Waste Water Treatment	(91/271/EEC)
10	Nitrates	(91/676/EEC)
11	Dichloroethane	(90/415/EEC)
12	Aldrin	(88/347/EEC)
13	Carbon tetrachloride	(86/280/EEC)
14	Cadmium	(83/513/EEC)
15	HCH	(84/491/EEC)
16	Mercury	(82/176/EEC)
17	Proposed Landfill Directive	(COM (93)275)
18	Sampling and analysis	(79/869/EEC)

Table 5.3 Agreements addressing general issues.

Code	Agreements	Code	Agreements
19	Moselle, 1961	30	Frontier waters (Au/SI), 1970
20	Rhine, 1976	31	Danube (Bucharest), 1985
21	Rhine (hydrology), 1976	32	Elbe, 1990
22	Trans-boundary waters, 1992	33	Technical Cupertino (Bu/Gr.), 1991
23	Meuse 1994	34	Agreement between Finland and USSR
24	Scheldt, 1994	35	Baltic Sea (1972/92)
25	Arctic (AMAP), 1991	36	Shellfish waters (79/923/EEC)
26	Mura, 1954	37	Baltic Sea (Helsinki) 1974/1992
27	Water economy (Au/Hu), 1958	38	Mediterranean (Barcelona), 1976
28	Lake Inari, 1958	39	North Sea (NSTF), 1987, 1990
29	Frontier rivers (Fi, S), 1971	40	Arctic Sea (AMAP), 1993

Other references for identifying subjects of concern:

CSS - Customer Segment Studies

RDP - EU-funded Research and Development Projects

GWAP - European Commission in its Groundwater Action Programme (EC 1995).

II.2.2 Identification of subjects of concern

The requirements for information found in the survey are usually described at a high level, without specifying the parameters, which need to be measured. In this section, we have compiled a list of subjects of concern and particular problem areas, with links to the directives and agreements shown in the previous section (2.1). These are summarised below in Table 5. For each subject of concern there are geophysical parameters which are discussed in section 2.3.

Table 6. Subjects of concern as identified in directives, international agreements (codes from Table 5.1 – 5.3) and EU-funded research and development projects

Subject of concern	Directive/international agreement	Other references
Anthropogenic hazards & pollution:		
eutrophication / algae bloom	4, 7, 9, 10, 20, 32, 37 - 39	
toxic/organic/pathogenic microbial & bacterial contamination	1- 4, 6- 8, 10-16, 20,25, 27, 29, 32, 33, 37 - 39, 40	
water turbidity;	1, 2, 4 -6 - 9, 20, 27, 31, 33, 39	
sediments & sediment transport	22, 25, 31, 32, 37, 38, 39	
civil engineering (bottom dragging)		CSS
surfactants (oil) contamination	1, 2, 4, 6, 38	
salinity & salinisation	4, 8, 37, 39	
water composition: taste, odour & colour	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 20,32	
trans-boundary pollution	20, 22, 29, 30, 31 -34	
radioactive contamination	7, 20, 25, 31, 33	
thermal pollution	1- 5, 8, 20, 32, 33, 37, 39	
atmospheric acidification	1-5, 6, 8, 20, 25, 31, 32, 35, 37, 38	
littering/timber floating & sinking		CSS

Table 6 cont.		
Natural hazards & hydrodynamics:		
surface water level/storms	22	CSS, RDP
sea level:		
climate changes		CSS, RDP
tides		CSS, RDP
sea-floor/water body topography		CSS, RDP
water depth		CSS, RDP
waves/ currents		CSS, RDP
coastline / river bank erosion		CSS, RDP
river flow	3, 20	
catchment: soil moisture / drainage		CSS, RDP
flood risk	22	CSS, RDP
drought risk		CSS, RDP
Ecological assessment		
ecosystem status	25, 32	
hydrobiota health & diversity	8, 25, 27, 37 - 39	
aquatic habitat		
recreational environments		CSS
benthos	27, 31	
wetlands		RDP
macrophyte, stands & mangroves		RDP
Natural resource & environmental management		
impact assessment	A, B	
environmental legislation		CSS
fisheries & mariculture	4, 25, 31, 39	CSS, RDP
forecasting		CSS, RDP
sustainable development	AGENDA 21	CSS, RDP
shipping/navigation		CSS
shore processes		CSS, RDP
Groundwater quality		
infiltration	C, 5, 10, 22	
toxic/organic contamination	C, 5, 8, 10, 17, 22	
ground water/aquifer resources		GWAP, CSS, RDP
salinisation	C, 5, 10, 17, 22	

II.2.3 Overview of water quality and environmental parameters

This section summarises the information collected on water quality parameters required for or related to the “subjects of concern” listed the previous tables. These parameters are characterised in terms of concern for monitoring of coastal and/or inland waters and of method of determination (conventional methods). The requirements to observation of these parameters are linked to directives and agreements in Tables 5.1 - 5.3). In some cases we have interpreted which parameters are needed based on the higher level formulations in the source material. We have attempted to include all parameters that are of importance in environmental monitoring, several of which are not mentioned in any of the EU policy documents. The parameters are organised in seven groups: physical, chemical, biological, ecological, sanitary, dynamic and geological/morphometric parameters, which are presented in the Tables 7.1 to 7.7 respectively.

Reference to present and expected capability of remote sensing to derive parameters is indicated for information and as a prognostic list. Detailed discussions on this issue lie in Part III and IV of the report. The indication of “future/potential capability” refers to the sensor and/or algorithm improvements that can be foreseen based on the present knowledge.

The following nomenclature is used to define remote sensing capability:

- yes: Algorithms exist that derive the parameter (see Part III of the report)
- partially: EO data give access to a subset of the parameter (e.g., CDOM as a subset of dissolved organic carbon)
- expected: improvement expected / potential (see Part IV of the report)
- no: nothing expected according to the present knowledge
- tbc: to be controlled, present knowledge do not permit to answer
- dyn: substance that are strongly related to suspended matter (by adsorption) and thus to the dynamics. Remote sensing provides relevant information on the spatial distribution of the parameter but not quantitative estimation.

II.2.3.1 Physical parameters

Table 7.1 Overview of water quality and other environmental parameters. Physical parameters

Physical parameters	Reference to Legislation, directives and agreements	Concern for		Conventional measurement method	Remote sensing capability	
		Inland waters	Coastal waters		present	future/potential
water temperature	1-5, 8, 18, 20, 27, 33, 36	yes	yes	In situ radiometer	yes	yes
water conductivity	1-3, 5, 8, 18, 20, 21, 25, 27, 31, 33	yes	yes	Radiometric reflective	no	expected
water density	35, 37	yes	yes	Calculated from temperature and salinity	no	expected
water radioactivity	20, 25	yes	yes	GM counter, proportional gas flow counter, scintillation counter	no	dyn
optical						
water transparency/turbidity	1, 2, 5, 6, 8, 39	yes	yes	Secchi disc, Turbidimeter	yes	yes
water colour	1, 2, 5, 36	yes	yes	Filtration, AS: spectral absorption at 254 nm	yes	yes
photic depth		yes	yes	Subsurface irradiance profile measurement	yes	yes

II.2.3.2 Chemical parameters

Table 7.2 Overview of water quality and other environmental parameters. Chemical parameters

Chemical parameters	Reference to legislation, directive and agreements	Concern for		Conventional measurement method	Remote sensing capability	
		Inland waters	Coastal waters		Present	Future/potential
water salinity	8, 36	yes	yes	Salinometer	no	expected
total phosphorus	1-4, 20, 27, 33, 37, 38, 39	yes	yes	Digestion; method inter-calibrated at the BIW; mineralisation, absorption photometry	no	expected
total nitrogen	27, 33, 37, 39	yes	yes	Persulphate oxidation, thermo-catalytic conversion	no	expected
dissolved organic carbon	1,2,20,21,32	yes	yes	IRS, catalytic oxidation	Partially CDOM	expected
total carbon	1,2, 20, 25, 32	yes	yes	Catalytic oxidation, IRS	no	expected
total silicon	20, 39	yes	yes	AAS, SM	no	no
water alkalinity	31, 32, 37	yes	yes	Titration	no	tbc
pH	1-6, 8, 20, 32, 36, 37	yes	yes		no	no
chemical oxygen demand (COD)	1-4, 27, 31, 38	yes	yes	Dichromate, Kubel, permanganate method	no	no
dissolved oxygen	4, 6, 8, 20, 27, 32, 36, 37	yes	yes	Winkler method	no	no
anoxia		yes	yes	Winkler method	partially	partially
ionic composition	1 – 3, –3, 5, 20, 37	yes	yes	EA, ISE	no	no
sulphurous compounds	1-2, 20, 27, 31, 32, 37	yes	yes	Ion chromatography	no	no
water mineralisation	1, 2	yes	no	Not specified	no	no
pesticides	1,2, 20, 21,33	yes	yes	Solid/solvent extraction, HPLC	no	no
heavy metals	1-3, 6, 8, 20, 25, 27, 36-39	yes	yes	AAS, neutron activation	no	dyn
surfactants/ oil spill area & thickness	1-3, 6	yes	yes	Not specified	yes	yes
oil type	4, 20, 35, 38	yes	yes	Solvent extraction	No	expected
chlorinated hydrocarbons	7, 20, 25, 27, 36, 38, 39	yes	yes	Solvent extraction	no	no

II.2.3.3 Biological parameters

Table 7.3 Overview of water quality and other environmental parameters. Biological parameters

Biological parameters	Reference to legislation, directives and agreements	Concern for		Conventional measurement method	Remote sensing capability	
		Inland waters	Coastal waters		Present	Future/potential
chlorophyllous pigments	32	yes	yes	HPLC, Extraction, spectrophometry (AS)	yes	yes
auxiliary pigments		yes	yes	as above	yes	yes
phaeopigments		yes	yes	AS	no	tbc
biological oxygen demand (BOD)	1-4, 27, 32, 38	yes	yes	dilution method	no	no
phytoplankton p. counts		yes	yes	microscope	no	no
p. biomass		yes	yes	FILTERING, WEIGHTING	no	expected
algal fungi: fungi counts		yes	yes	microscope	no	no
bacterioplankton: b. counts		yes	yes	microscope	no	no
b. biomass		yes	yes	models	no	expected
zooplankton: z. counts		yes	yes	microscope	no	no
z. biomass		yes	yes	calculations	no	tbc
detritus d. concentration	27	yes	yes	not specified	yes	yes

II.2.3.4 Ecological parameters

Table 7.4 Overview of water quality and other environmental parameters. Ecological parameters

Ecological parameters	Reference to legislation, directives and agreements	Concern for		Conventional measurement method	Remote sensing capability	
		Inland waters	Coastal waters		Present	Future/potential
Net organic matter production: primary production rate		yes	yes	incubation bottles	yes	yes
water body trophic status		yes	yes	trophic indices	no	expected
bacterial decomposition		yes	yes	not specified	no	no
phytoplankton grazing		yes	yes	as above	no	no
Biodiversity: phytoplankton		yes	yes	microscope	partially	expected
bacterioplankton		yes	yes	microscope	no	tbc
zooplankton		yes	yes	microscope	no	no
fungi	8	yes	yes	microscope	no	no
Biota habitat status: littoral zone	32, 37	no	yes	not identified, presumably by indices	no	expected
pelagic zone		no	yes		no	expected
benthos		yes	yes		partially	expected
macrophyte stands/ mangroves		yes	yes		yes	yes

II.2.3.5 Other parameters: sanitary, dynamic and geological/morphometric parameters

Table 7.5 Overview of water quality and other environmental parameters. Sanitary parameters

Sanitary parameters	Reference to legislation, directives and agreements	Concern for		Conventional measurement method	Remote sensing capability	
		Inland waters	Coastal waters		Present	Future/potential
water odour	1, 2, 5	yes	yes	not identified	no	no
water taste	5, 36	yes	no	as above	no	no
water saprobity		yes	yes	as above	no	no
water toxicity		yes	yes	as above	no	no
faecal forms	1-5, 27, 32, 33, 38	yes	yes	Endo-agar 43C, 24h count (red colonies only)	no	no
salmonella	1-5, 27, 32, 33, 38	yes	no	not identified	no	no

Table 7.6 Overview of water quality and other environmental parameters. Dynamic parameters

Dynamic parameters	Reference to legislation, directives and agreements	Concern for		Conventional measurement method	Remote sensing capability	
		Inland waters	Coastal waters		Present	Future/potential
suspended sediment	22, 25, 31, 32, 37, 38, 39	yes	yes	filter / weight	yes	yes
water level	20,21,33	yes	yes	not specified	yes	yes
water residence time		yes	no	calculations	no	tbc
river flow	20, 27,31,32	yes	yes	flow-metre	no	tbc
lake stratification		yes	no	not specified	no	no
current and waves		no	yes	current-meter	yes	yes

Table 7.7 Overview of water quality and other environmental parameters. Geological and morphometric parameters

Geological and morphometric parameters	Reference to legislation, directives and agreements	Concern for		Conventional measurement method	Remote sensing capability	
		Inland waters	Coastal waters		Present	Future/potential
water surface area		yes	yes	mapping	yes	yes
basin morphometry /bathymetry		yes	yes	geomorphologic measurements	yes	yes
shoreline		yes	yes	geographic measurements	yes	yes
water volume		yes	no	modelling	no	tbc

II.2.3.6 Comments to the parameters

The physical parameters include optical, thermohaline, dynamical as well as morphological parameters. This group of parameters is fundamental for the other parameters because the chemical, biological, ecological and sanitary conditions are heavily dependent on the physical conditions. The physical parameters are also most relevant for remote sensing observation. The group of chemical parameters represents the highest number of references to directives and agreements, whereas the biological and ecological groups apparently show only a few such references. Biology and ecology parameters are obviously important in many higher level requirements, but the interpretation of these requirements in terms of parameters has not been thoroughly analysed. Remote sensing can only be used to observe a few of the chemical, biological and ecological parameters. These parameters, such as chlorophyll, pigments, primary production rate, dissolved organic carbon, oil spill areas, and a few others are nevertheless very important and remote sensing offers a unique possibility to obtain synoptic surveys over large areas, which is not possible by any conventional method. The sanitary parameters, which are linked to many directives, cannot be observed by any remote sensing method.

II.2.4 Water quality and environmental parameters derivable from EO data

In this section, water quality and other parameters that can be derived from remote sensing data are extracted from Tables 7.1-7.7. The water quality parameters are usually derived via intermediate parameters, which are directly measured by remote sensing instruments. Models and other *a priori* information needed to derive the water quality parameter are also included.

The symbols for some of the key-parameters observable by remote sensing used here are:

a, b, c	are the coefficients of absorption, scattering and attenuation of light by bulk water
K_d	is the coefficient of downwelling irradiance attenuation
R	is the water volume reflectance
$C_{chl}, C_{sm}, C_y, C_{det}$	are the concentrations of chlorophyll, suspended minerals, coloured dissolved organic matter (yellow substance) and detritus, respectively
λ_{dom}	water colour in terms of dominant wavelength
S	is the oil spill area
h	is the oil spill thickness

In many cases these are intermediate parameters which need to be used in algorithms to derive the water quality parameter.

An overview of water quality, remote sensing parameters and other required information is given in the following Tables 8.1-8.6:

II.2.4.1 Physical parameters

Table 8.1. Basic physical parameters observable by remote sensing

Physical parameters	Intermediate parameter derivable by remote sensing	a priori information required
water temperature	water surface temperature	correlation between water surface temperature and temperature vertical profile
water transparency	a, b, c, K_d	hydro-optical model ⁽¹⁾ or statistically-significant correlation between an upwelling radiance ratio and K_d
water colour	R , colour coordinates, dominant wavelength, colour purity	hydro-optical model
photic depth	K_d	hydro-optical model, actual or at least statistically significant (for a given season and weather pattern) vertical profiles of major optically active components

(1): hydro-optical model is defined as *a priori* information as it is based on *a priori* knowledge of the inherent and apparent optical properties of the water.

II.2.4.2 Chemical parameters

Table 8.2 Chemical parameters observable by remote sensing

Chemical parameters	Intermediate parameter derivable by remote sensing	a priori information required
dissolved organic carbon	C_y	hydro-optical model
surfactants/oil: oil spill area oil spill thickness	S h	coefficient of absorption of spilled oil

II.2.4.3 Biological and ecological parameters

Table 8.3 Biological and ecological parameters derivable via remote sensing

Biological parameters	Intermediate parameter derivable by remote sensing	a priori information required
chlorophyllous pigments	a	hydro-optical model
auxiliary pigments	a	hydro-optical model
detritus concentration	C_{det}	hydro-optical model
Ecological parameters	Intermediate parameter derivable by remote sensing	a priori information required
primary production rate ⁽¹⁾	C_{chl}	vertical profiles of major optically active components, area specific primary production model parameters
phytoplankton diversity	a	hydro-optical model
habitats		
macrophyte stands & mangroves	macrophyte stands area dynamics	
benthos	bottom reflectance	shallow-water hydro-optical model

(1): mapping of primary production rate will be possible only very locally in coastal zones, with support of extensive sea truth data and empirical relationships (Ekstrand, 1998 personal communication)

II.2.4.4 Dynamical and geological/morphometric parameters

Table 8.4 Dynamical and geological/morphometric parameters observable by remote sensing

Dynamical parameters	Intermediate parameter observable by remote sensing	a priori information required
suspended sediments	C_{sm}	hydro-optical model
water level	water area dynamics	
Geological/morphometric parameters	Intermediate parameter observable by remote sensing	a priori information required
water surface area	pixel area	geo-located data / country border
basin morphometry	depth	hydro-optical model
shoreline	pixel number	geo-located data

II.3 Quantitative requirements for environmental parameters

The quantitative user requirements presented in this section have been collected from various sources including European- and ESA-funded projects. The main sources have shown representative of a wide variety of environment and applications, and are detailed hereafter. Other sources have been consulted that are not presented here since their results fall in the range of requirements compiled in the following study:

- The ICAMS project assessment on user needs for EO data for coastal zone management.
- The POWERS project assessment of end-user requirements for ocean colour derived products (e.g., MERIS)
- A compilation of scientific requirement for monitoring eutrophication in lakes
- A synthesis of the three sources above and taking into account our own experience.

II.3.1 ICAMS user requirements assessments

These surveys undertaken by the ICAMS project involved large numbers of potential users of coastal marine data acquired by satellites. A brief summarisation of key-issues is presented hereafter. In addition to identifying essential potential applications of coastal water quality data, these reports identify user issues related to data access (timelines, cost, etc.) of data.

Requirements from ICAMS user consultation

More than 60 people participated in the consultation process, and the following applications areas were represented during the meetings, including regulatory/planning interests, research interests, fisheries/mariculture, environmental protection, engineering; ports, coastal defence and mineral extraction.

Table 9 summarises the key-data and technology requirements from each group of users contacted. Table 10 provides an analysis of the requirements by user type.

Table 9. User requirements overview

Irish Region User Requirements	
Data Requirements	SST and chlorophyll maps. Derived maps of algal blooms and toxins. Surface current and other physical oceanographic data. Data at 1 km for the bay and offshore and higher resolution in harbour areas. Daily or weekly data as well as seasonal time-series.
Technology Requirements	Web access to data. GIS-compatibility for local analysis of data. Interest in advanced warning and forecast systems, which require modelling capability.
Adriatic Region User Requirements	
Data Requirements	Chlorophyll concentration, dissolved organic matter, transparency/Secchi depth, SST. Primary productivity and turbidity index. Data every 2-3 days. 1 km data to complement higher resolution local data.
Technology Requirements	Web and fax access to data. PC-based data analysis; interest in using ICAMS analysis tools.
Aegean Region User Requirements	
Data Requirements	Sediment, SST, chlorophyll. 1 km for N Aegean area of interest, higher resolution in test sites.
Technology Requirements	Web and fax access to data. PC- and workstation-based data analysis. Need to incorporate cruise data with EO products.
FAO User Requirements	
Data Requirements	Chlorophyll, SST and sediment. 1 km and higher. Access to archives of time-series data. Land-use and inland water quality data.
Technology Requirements	Stand-alone ICAMS archive and analysis systems for local use. PC-based data analysis.

Table 10. Analysed user requirements

User category	User Requirements
Institutional Users	Interested in data from all trial sites. 1 km scale data is adequate ¹ . “seasonal” time period of interest, no near real time requirement. Want limited interaction with an ICAMS system; want only to download data (or information products) via WWW to aid in decision making
Regional Product Users	Interested in data from individual site. 1 km and higher resolution. Daily and weekly data needed, with some interest in near real time when possible. Want subscription service or simple URL for most recent data.
Regional Expert Users (and collaborating users)	Interested in data from individual site. 1 km and higher resolution. Daily, near real time data (plus archives of data for research)

¹ These are defined as 1 km chlorophyll, SST, suspended matter for the 500 km “area of interest” for each trial site. Data are mapped to a lat/lon grid and have cloud mask applied. Data are provided daily and 7 day composites.

There were many requests for data, which is outside the scope of this study. Many users expressed some interest in coastline mapping from high-resolution data and coastal planners and for wind data, wave data, current data, meteorological data as well.

Requirements from Previous Studies

In assessing user requirements and data needs, the ICAMS team also reviewed the results of user requirements studies undertaken in support of other projects. Some of the key points from existing studies are presented below.

- CEO Pathfinder Study on the Coastal Zone: Final Report. ACRI, under contract to CEO, 1995. ACR-CEO-FR. 152pp.
- Market and benefit assessment of three Case studies: 1. Coastal zone management, 2. Monitoring of algal booms, 3. Spanish desertification project. CEO Report, 1995. CEO/174/1995. 29pp.

CEO Pathfinder Study

The CEO study surveyed ten coastal application areas: water quality/pollution, coastal protection, nature conservation, global change, observatories, ports and marines, urbanism, tourism and leisure, fishing and aquaculture, offshore structures. Over 560 users were surveyed during this activity. Most of the users were not familiar with the types of data which can be derived with remote sensing satellites. It was noted that many applications require data and surveys for particular areas, and these data are generally gathered at a local level, by commercial companies undertaking in-situ sampling. Where parameters can be derived from satellites, accuracy and sampling (re-visit times) were cited as potential problems.

User data requirements categorised as “most important” were wave data and physio-chemical parameters of seawater; SST was “very important” and chlorophyll and sediment were “important”. For SST, suspended matter, physio-chemical parameters (incl. transparency, pigments) and micro-organisms data the preferred spatial resolution was 100m-1km and the preferred temporal resolution was 1 day – 1 month. The current data, tides, wind and waves have higher spatial and/or temporal sampling requirements.

Based on survey responses it was apparent that in-situ data and modelling were critical features of user requirements in order to meet the spatial and temporal demands. This was important to provide both a predictive capability and to enable inferences over larger areas or to depth. It was noted that remote sensing data can be ideal to initialise models, follow boundary conditions, and validate output.

In addition, it was noted that there is currently considerable duplication of effort among many regional authorities gathering and analysing the same data. The ability to use and share common data sources would greatly improve the efficiency of coastal management for many groups.

CEO Market Benefit Assessment

This market assessment study looked at coastal management users (civil engineering, insurance and water companies) primarily in order to assess the potential monetary value of remote sensing data to industry. In reviewing the needs for data from these groups it was noted that civil engineering and insurance companies generally filled data requirements by performing site surveys. In the water industry, where monitoring effluent is a critical application, limited EO data was being used, however their requirement is for high-resolution visible and IR data and these are often gathered by aircraft surveys.

This same study looked at the potential for algae bloom monitoring from optical satellites. It was found that present data used in these applications are primarily provided from in-situ measurements and aircraft.

Others

The EuroGOOS project is also collecting user requirements via national surveys. Unpublished results from these studies indicate strong requirements for surface fields (including SST, Wind, Wave).

II.3.2 POWERS user requirement assessment

The POWERS project has investigated the user requirement on ocean colour sensor-derived water-quality information in three countries: Switzerland, Belgium and The Netherlands, with regards to MERIS sensor expected capability. The selected institutes per countries were all aware of the potential of remote sensing. Two groups of user were targeted, namely inland water management and research authorities in the Netherlands and Switzerland, and coastal management and research authorities in The Netherlands and Belgium.

Summaries of the collected information are presented in Table 11 and Table 12.

Table 11. End-user requirements for EO-derived “water quality” parameters within the POWERS project: range of value and accuracy (between brackets).

Water Management Authorities	Chl ($\mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$)	SM (mg.l^{-1})	Z_{SD} (m)	K_{dpar} (m^{-1})	Other pigments	CDOM (mg.l^{-1})	Macro-phytes
Coastal waters	0.1– 30 (10%)	1-1000 (10%)	Interested	Interested	Interested	01-10 (0.2)	Interested
Inland waters	1-300 (10 %)	1-200 (25 %)	0.1-9.0 (0.1)	0.3-10 (0.2)	Interested	-	interested

Table 12. Spatial and temporal requirements

Water Management Authorities	1200 m	300 m	< 300m	Current frequency using non-RS methods
Coastal waters	High interest	High interest	High interest	5 to 20 times per year
Inland waters	Low interest	High interest	High interest	12 to 24 times per year

For chlorophyll (Chl) there is not too much difference in both range and accuracy required between inland and coastal waters; although detailed information does show that for coastal areas

the focus lies, in general, in the concentration range of 1 to 50 ($\mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$) Chl. In shallow eutrophic inland waters concentrations may easily exceed 200 $\mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$ (with recorded maxima in The Netherlands of 1000 $\mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$). In general, at lower concentrations a higher accuracy is required; this is expressed efficiently as a percentage required accuracy: at 5 $\mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$ Chl the required accuracy is 0.5 $\mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$ but at 200 $\mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$ the required accuracy is 20 $\mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$. For water reservoirs and deep lakes, however the range in Chl concentration is between 0.1 and 10 $\mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$. Thus end-user requirements for these type of inland water are different and, in general, more difficult to realise with remote sensing, because a higher accuracy is required. According to POWERS, the main end-user requirement is for eutrophication assessment and algal blooms, although also aspects such as primary production are mentioned.

For total suspended matter (SM) the requirements are in fact, more relaxed than for Chl because SM is desired in units mg.l^{-1} . The range in coastal water is higher than for inland waters, due to wave and tidal effects. However, for coastal waters the average range of interest is 1 to 20 mg.l^{-1} . The demand for this type of information is either related to sedimentation rates and shipping lanes or to model the pollution dispersion. For inland waters the range lies between 1 and 90 mg.l^{-1} for shallow eutrophic lakes and between 0.1 and 20 mg.l^{-1} for deep lakes and reservoirs. Other subjects of concern expressed by POWERS end-user are related to sediment budget in coastal waters and river inflow in inland waters.

II.3.3 Quantitative requirements for large lakes monitoring

Table 13 presents assessment of requirements for lake monitoring. The literature used to define these requirements is listed in the References, section V.1.2.4.

Table 13. Quantitative requirements for identified geophysical parameters related to eutrophication and algae bloom in large lakes

Eutrophication / algal blooms	Units	Range of values	Accuracy	References
C_{chl}	mg/m^3	0.1 - 200	0.01	79, 83, 85
primary production	$\text{gC/m}^3\text{day}$	100-4000	10	88
total phosphorus	mg/m^3	1 -90	0.1	83, 84, 88
total carbon	mg/m^3	1-20	0.1	83, 84, 88
total nitrogen	mg/m^3	400-900	1	80, 84, 88
auxiliary pigments (ap)	chl/ap	0.9 - 5.0	0.01	90
C_v	mgC/m^3	1 - 15	0.1	82, 83, 86, 89, 91
C_{sm}	mg/m^3	1-50	0.1	82, 83, 86, 89, 91
C_{bac}	$\text{cells}10^6/l$	0.1 -20	0.01	82, 83, 86, 89, 91
C_{det}	$\%C_{chl}$	10-30	1	82, 83, 86, 89, 91
Absorption coef. a(560nm)	m^{-1}	0.05 - 3.0	0.01	80, 86, 89, 91
Scattering coef.: b(560nm)	m^{-1}	0.2 - 2.0	0.01	80, 86, 89, 91
Diffuse attenuation: $K_d(560)$	m^{-1}	0.2 - 4.5	0.01	80, 86, 89, 91
photic depth	m	<1 - 35	0.1	80, 88
Volume reflectance R(410 nm)	a.u.	0.01- 0.15	0.01	80
Water colour, λ_{dom}	nm	472 - 575	1	87
Turbidity/ Secchi disk depth	m	<1 - 35	0.1	80, 88
WST	$^{\circ}\text{C}$	3 - 25	0.1	82, 86, 88, 89

Note: the values in this table do not relate to extreme cases but to the most probable conditions under which eutrophication process usually occur.

II.3.4 Synthesis of quantitative requirements

Table 14 summarises the requirements for geophysical parameters within five subjects of concern:

1. **Anthropogenic hazards:** toxic/organic pollution, surfactants, trans-boundary and thermal pollution
2. **Eutrophication:** eutrophication process study, including algae bloom
3. **Natural hazards / hydrodynamics:** storms, water level changes, sea level, waves, river flow, flood risk
4. **Ecological assessment:** ecosystem status, biodiversity, aquatic habitats
5. **Environmental and natural resource management:** impact assessment, bathymetry, topography, environmental legislation, forecasting, sustainable development, shoreline/river banks modification, erosion, sedimentation, beach processes, sediment transport, fisheries, mariculture.

Table 14. Quantitative requirements for identified geophysical parameters.

Subject of concern and relevant parameters	Quantitative requirements			
1. Anthropogenic hazards (except eutrophication)	Spatial resolution: optimal: 100 m / minimal: 1 km Frequency of sampling: optimal: hourly to daily / minimal: weekly Permissible delay of availability: one day			
	Units	Range of value	Accuracy	
			Minimal	optimal
C_{chl} [Chl-a]	$mg.m^{-3}$	0.1 - 200	10 %	10 %
C_{sm}	$mg.l^{-1}$	1 - 1000	25 %	10 %
C_y / a_y (380 or 440nm)	$mgC.m^{-3} / m^{-1}$	1 - 15	0.5	0.1
C_{det}	$mg.m^{-3}$	10 - 30	0.5	10 %
Diffuse attenuation: $K_d(560)$	m^{-1}	2 - 20	0.5	0.1
Turbidity / Secchi depth	m	<1 - 35	< 1	0.1
Water colour, λ_{dom}	nm	472 - 575	5 %	1 %
WST	$^{\circ}C$	-2 - 40	0.5	0.1
Oil spill area	km^2	> 1	10 %	10 %
Oil spill thickness	mm	> 1	10 %	0.1
2. Eutrophication / algae blooms	Spatial resolution: <100 m for small water bodies; 500 m otherwise Frequency of sampling: optimal: daily; minimal: weekly Permissible delay of availability: one week			
	Units	Range of value	Accuracy	
			Minimal	optimal
C_{chl} [Chl-a]	$mg.m^{-3}$	0.1 - 300	30 %	0.05
Primary production	$gC.m^{-2}.d^{-1}$	100 - 4000	10 %	10
C_{sm}	$mg.l^{-1}$	1 - 50	10 %	0.1
C_y	$mgC.m^{-3}$	1 - 15	10 %	0.01
C_{det}	$mg.m^{-3}$	10 - 30	10 %	1
Absorption coef.: $a(560)$	m^{-1}	0.05 - 3.0	5 %	0.01
Scattering coef.: $b(560)$	m^{-1}	0.2 - 2.0	5 %	0.01
Diffuse attenuation: $K_d(560)$	m^{-1}	0.2 - 4.5	5 %	0.01
Photic depth	m	<1 - 50	10 %	0.1
Turbidity / Secchi depth	m	<1 - 35	5 %	0.1
Water colour, λ_{dom}	nm	472 - 575	1 %	1
WST	$^{\circ}C$	-2 - 25	0.5 (absolute)	0.1

Table 14 cont.

Subject of concern and relevant parameters	Quantitative requirements			
3. Natural hazards	Spatial resolution: 100 m (crisis); 1 km otherwise Frequency of sampling: hourly (storms, flooding); seasonal for climate and climate-driven water level dynamics Permissible delay of availability: real time (storms); hours (flooding); month (climate)			
	Units	Range of value	Accuracy	
			minimal	optimal
C_{sm}	mg.l ⁻¹	1 - 1000	25 %	10 %
WST	°C	-2 - 25	0.5	0.1
Water level	m	> 0.1	10 %	-
Bathymetry	m	1 - 30	1 (absolute)	0.1
Shoreline changes	m	0.1 - 10	1	0.1
4. Ecological assessment	Spatial resolution: < 100 m to 1 km Frequency of sampling: seasonal to annual Permissible delay of availability: one month			
	Units	Range of value	Accuracy	
			minimal	optimal
C_{chl} [Chl-a]	mg.m ⁻³	0.1 - 200	10 %	0.01
Primary production	gC.m ⁻² .d ⁻¹	100 - 4000	10 %	10
Auxiliary pigments (ap)	[Chl-a]/[ap]	0.9 - 5.0	50 %	0.01
C_{sm}	mg.l ⁻¹	1 - 5	25 %	0.1
C_y	mgC.m ⁻³	1 - 15	20 %	0.01
C_{det}	mg.m ⁻³	10 - 30	50 %	1
Diffuse attenuation: $K_d(560)$	m ⁻¹	0.2 - 4.5	5 %	0.01
Photic depth	m	<1 - 50	20 %	0.1
Turbidity / Secchi depth	m	<1 - 35	10 %	0.1
Water colour, λ_{dom}	nm	472 - 575	1 %	1
WST	°C	-2 - 25	0.5 (absolute)	0.1
Water level	m	0.1 - 3	10 %	-
Bathymetry	m	1 - 30	1 (absolute)	0.2
5. Natural resource & environmental management	Spatial resolution: <50m for small lakes and rivers, 100 m otherwise Frequency of sampling: from week to month Permissible delay of availability: from several days to a month			
	Units	Range of value	Accuracy	
			minimal	optimal
C_{chl} [Chl-a]	mg.m ⁻³	0.1 - 200	30 %	10 %
Primary production	gC.m ⁻² .d ⁻¹	100 - 4000	30 %	10 %
C_{sm}	mg.l ⁻¹	1 - 5	25 %	10 %
C_y	mgC.m ⁻³	1 - 15	10 %	0.01
Turbidity / Secchi depth	m	<1 - 35	10 %	1
Water colour, λ_{dom}	nm	472 - 575	5	1
WST	°C	-2 - 25	1 (absolute)	0.2
Water level	m	0.1 - 3	10 %	-
Bathymetry	m	1 - 200	0.5	0.1

II.4 Conclusions from the requirement survey

II.4.1 The main results of the survey

The main result of the search is that there is a limited number of specific requirements to quantitative measurements that EO data can provide directly. On the other hand, most of the requirements are discussed only at high level in the form of “subject of concern” where data requirements are specified only in a few cases. It appears that EO data can contribute with data within many “subjects of concern”, but use of EO data to extract useful parameters can only be done for about 15-20 parameters relevant for observation of “water quality”. It is also evident that there are few parameters, for example temperature and water colour that are derivable from EO data and that have impact on many “subjects of concern”.

II.4.2 Clarification of project scope

The search for requirements has shown that parameters related to “water quality” will have the highest priority in the study. This means that primarily optical and infrared satellite data and related algorithms will be examined. Algorithms for wave height, tidal range/sea level/water level, winds and currents are not reviewed in detail but discussed in the context of water quality and impact on coastal zones in general, e.g., there are cases such as oil spill monitoring where SAR is obviously important. Bathymetry from SAR is also included, as bathymetry is one of the user most cited parameters.

PART III. DERIVING GEOPHYSICAL PARAMETERS FROM EO DATA: AN ASSESSMENT

III.1 Introduction

The third part of the report is dedicated to a state-of-the-art and discussion on short-term expectations for improvements concerning the retrieval of geophysical parameters with space sensors. The present section introduces the sixteen environmental parameters identified in the user requirements and that are discussed in the rest of the report. These parameters have been selected according to both the various requirements expressed and synthesised in Part II, and the capability to be estimated by EO techniques. The parameters have been grouped into classes in order to improve the understanding and readability of the report. The following five classes are defined:

- water constituents
- optical properties of the water column
- surface temperature
- depth-related parameters
- morphometry

The first class, *water constituents*, includes the concentrations of the three main optically active components in the water column, namely chlorophyll-a (subscript *chl-a*), inorganic suspended sediment (subscript *sm*), coloured dissolved organic matter (subscript *y*) also known as yellow substance or *gelbstoff*. This class also includes those geophysical parameters that can indirectly be derived from EO data. As such, photic depth and primary production can be derived if an estimate of respectively K_d and chlorophyll pigment concentration is given. The latter can be estimated from EO data. Detritus has also been included, based on recent developments. Such parameters are commonly used for characterising the ecological state of water bodies.

The second class, *optical properties*, includes those parameters that describe the physical properties of the water-column constituents regarding sun light propagation in the water body (refer back to the tutorial (Part II, Section 1.4) for a description of these quantities). Such parameters (absorption and scattering coefficients of bulk water or of a particular water constituent, diffuse attenuation coefficient, volume reflectance, Secchi depth, water colour) are commonly used for characterising the physical-optical state of natural waters.

The third class consists of the water surface temperature (WST), a commonly used general descriptor of a water body.

The fourth class contains those parameters that are related to water depth, namely bathymetry (absolute water depth), bottom topography (variation of bathymetry due to bottom shape) and water level (variation of bathymetry due to surface shape). Such parameters can be seen as global descriptors of water bodies and are of great importance for coastal and inland waters management and hazard assessments.

The fifth class includes those parameters that are expressed in terms of length, area, and shape. Table 15 lists the parameters in each class, the measurements units, and the corresponding algorithms described in the report.

Section III.2 presents the algorithms and methods that have been developed for deriving the geophysical parameters from EO data. No *a priori* division has been made between coastal and inland waters, as it is the parameters *per se* that are under concerned. Most of the algorithms

have been developed to fit the characteristics of a particular sensor. Each algorithm or type of algorithm is presented in a standardised form that includes a reference number. All the forms have been gathered in section III.3.

Section III.4 is dedicated to the presentation of digested information. First, the main achievements obtain with space sensors for the characterisation of coastal and inland waters are summarised in form of tables. Then comparisons and analyses of EO achievements versus user requirements are discussed. The main conclusions on the capability of present and near-future EO regarding the requirements are then presented, and give the scope of Part IV of this report that is dedicated to the mid- and long-term expected improvement of EO.

Section III.5 presents standard EO data products and software related to the geophysical parameter under consideration. In this section we emphasise on the availability of end-products, as well as on free-, share-ware and commercial software and packages that integrate one or several of the algorithms detailed in section III.3.

III.2 Description of algorithms

For each parameter, we discuss the retrieval algorithms, which have been used in an operational context (section “present algorithms”) and those which are still under investigation (section “expected improvements”).

The methods presented are described in one-page standardised forms, which have been gathered in section 4 and are referred to by a number at the top right corner of the form. The form is composed of a header that gives information concerning the performance and domain of applicability of the method, and a short description of the algorithm itself. Required ancillary data and limitations of use are given when applicable.

Table 15 gives the links between parameters and algorithm form numbers. Details on the domain of applicability of the algorithms presented in the report are given in Table 16.

Table 15. Environmental parameters, and reference numbers of related algorithms description forms.

Environmental parameters	Units	References to Algorithm description form
Water constituents		
C_{chl} [Chl-a]	$mg.m^{-3}$	1 to 17
Primary production	$gC.m^{-3}.day^{-1}$	18 to 20
Auxiliary pigments	$mg.m^{-3}$	12
C_{sm}	$mg.l^{-1}$	15 to 17 and 21 to 26
$C_v / a_v(380)$	$mg.m^{-3} / m^{-1}$	15 to 17
C_{det}	%[Chl]	16
Optical properties		
Inherent properties: a, b	m^{-1}	27 to 29
Diffuse attenuation: K_d	m^{-1}	30 to 33
Photic depth	m	33
Turbidity/Secchi depth	m	34 & 35
Water colour, λ_{dom}	nm	36
Surface Temperature		
WST	$^{\circ}C$	37 to 39
Depth-related		
Bathymetry / topography	m	40 to 42
Water level	m	43
Morphometry		
Shoreline	m	44 & 45
Oil spill extent	km^2	46

Table 16. Domain of applicability of the algorithms

Form	Parameters	Type	Name	Sensors	Water type
1	Chl	Polynomial	TM	TM	Case II
2	Chl	Band ratio	Radiance ratio	CZCS	Case I & II
3	Chl	Band ratio	CZCS –NASA	CZCS	Case I & II
4	Chl	Band ratio	Reflectance ratio	CZCS	Case I & II
5	Chl	Band ratio	Cubic polynomial	CZCS, POLDER, SeaWiFS	Case I
6	Chl	Band ratio	OC-2	SeaWiFS	Case I
7	Chl	Band ratio	OC-4	SeaWiFS	Case I
8	Chl	Band ratio	Power	OCTS, SeaWiFS	Case I
9	Chl	Band ratio	Hyperbolic/power	OCTS, SeaWiFS	Case I
10	Chl	Band ratio	Multiple regression	OCTS, SeaWiFS	Case I
11	Chl, sm, CDOM	Band ratio	Multiple regression	SeaWiFS, MOS	Case II
12	Chl	Empirical	Spectral curvature	SeaWiFS	Case I
13	Chl	Band ratio	NDPI	POLDER	Case I & II
14	Chl	Semi-analytic	Bates & Watts	SeaWiFS	Case I
15	Chl, sm, CDOM	Multivariate optim.	Two-flow approx.	CZCS, MOS	Coastal - inland
16	Chl, sm, CDOM	Non linear regression	Neural network	SeaWiFS, MOS	Coastal – inland
17	Chl, sm, CDOM	Multivariate optim.	Levenberg-Macq.	SeaWiFS, MOS	Coastal – inland
18	P ^B	Band ratio/analytic	Bedford	CZCS, SeaWiFS	Case I
19	P ^B	Band ratio/ analytic	LPCM	CZCS, SeaWiFS	Case I
20	P ^B	Band ratio/empirical	VGPM	CZCS, SeaWiFS	Case I
21	sm	Reflectance ratio	SPOT – SM	HRV	Coastal - inland
22	sm	Reflectance ratio	TM – SM	TM	Coastal- inland
23	sm	Logarithm	Unified model	TM, MSS	Coastal - inland
24	sm	Normal. band sum	MSS – SM	MSS	Case II
25	sm	Single band	AVHRR – SM	AVHRR	Case II
26	sm	Band ratio	Seston algorithm	CZCS	Case II
27	a	Semi-analytic	Lee algorithm	SeaWiFS	Case I
28	a _{dm} , b _{bp}	Semi-analytic	Garver & Siegel	SeaWiFS	Case I
29	b _b / a	Semi-analytic	Cubic polynomial	SeaWiFS	Case I & II
30	K _d	Band ratio	K(PAR)	CASI, Caesar	Inland
31	K _d	Linear regression	MSS – K _d	MSS	Case I & II
32	K _d	Band ratio	“K” algorithm	CZCS	Case I
33	K _d	Band ratio	“K” algorithm	SeaWiFS	Case I
34	Z _{SD}	Band ratio	“SD” algorithm	CASI	Inland
35	Turbidity	Band ratio	Turbidity index	MSS, TM	Inland
36	Chromaticity	Semi-analytic	CIE algorithm	SeaWiFS	Coastal - inland
37	WST	Split-window	MCSST	AVHRR	Coastal – inland
38	WST	Dual view split-win	ATSR – WST	ATSR	Coastal – inland
39	WST	Single band	-	AVHRR, TM6	Coastal – inland
40	Water depth	Semi-empirical	Bierwirth	TM	Coastal – inland
41	Topography	Spectral analysis	Hydrodynamic	SAR	Coastal
42	Topography	Correlation method	Venturi	SAR	Coastal
43	Sea level	Dynamical modelling	ISSH	Altimeter	Coastal offshore
44	Shoreline	Morphometry	Directional mask	SAR	Coastal– inland
45	Shoreline	Statistical estimation	Semi-variogram	SAR, HRV, TM	Coastal – inland
46	Oil slick	Image processing	Threshold analysis	SAR	Coastal – inland

III.2.1 Water constituents

The water constituents considered in the study are chlorophyll pigment, suspended sediment (sm), coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM), and detritus, plus two additional parameters that require an estimate of chlorophyll-a concentration to be derived, namely daily primary production rate and trophic state index.

III.2.1.1 Algae chlorophyll concentration

Deriving chlorophyll concentration (C_{chl}) from space was the main goal of the former CZCS sensor onboard Nimbus-7 (1978 – 1986). CZCS was the first space sensor dedicated to ocean colour monitoring. Scientific teams all around the world have contributed to the development of algorithms dedicated to the exploitation of CZCS data, during the sensor lifetime, and long after it stopped functioning. Experience gained through CZCS data handling has opened a wide field of application for ocean colour from space.

After a gap of about ten years, new advanced ocean colour sensors have been developed, based on the experience gained from CZCS, and launched in the last three years: OCTS (1996 – 1997), POLDER (1996 – 1997), SeaWiFS (1998 – onwards), MOS (1996 – onwards). Improved capability of these sensors has led to new algorithmic development, in particular linked to the MOS sensor, which is the first ocean colour instrument designed for coastal zone applications.

The retrieval of chlorophyll (Chl) concentrations from EO data has been performed based on several approaches. Empirical and semi-analytical models have been implemented.

A. Present algorithms

In this section we present the algorithms considered as operational, and for which no further improvement is expected.

a) Empirical methods

Historically, empirical models relating a radiative quantity (water-leaving radiance, upwelling radiance, volume reflectance or remote sensing reflectance) derived from EO data and chlorophyll concentration have been developed. Numerous empirical formulations have been proposed that use more or less complex model. More recently other approaches have been investigated, including semi-analytical models based on water inherent optical properties, and inverse methods.

Empirical models used for the retrieval of chlorophyll concentration are presented in forms 1 to 13. Most of the algorithms have been set up based on fitting EO ocean colour derived quantities to extensive worldwide *in situ* data set. However algorithms presented in forms 1 and 11 have been developed for specific areas.

b) Inverse methods

The first inverse algorithm was proposed by Doerffer *et al.*, 1989, 1994 [169] and applied to the retrieval of chlorophyll, suspended sediment and gelbstoff in coastal water from CZCS data. This algorithm is presented in form 15.

B. Expected improvements

Algorithms developed based on SeaWiFS, OCTS, POLDER and MOS data are presented in forms 5 to 17.

a) Empirical methods

The main improvements of empirical approaches with new sensors concern a systematic use of non-linear models, including cubic polynomial, power and hyperbolic-power relationships, as well as multiple regression approach. Algorithms based on empirical relationships are presented in forms 5 to 13.

b) Semi-analytical methods

One semi-analytical model is presented form 14, and represents the latest development and trends for deriving chlorophyll concentration from EO data.

c) Inverse methods/multiple parameter retrieval

Forms 15 to 17 present three different inverse methods that focus on the simultaneous retrieval of concentrations of chlorophyll, suspended sediment and gelbstoff. These methods consider the water column as a whole and thus are well suited for processing Case II waters. The algorithms presented in the report are i) the two-flow approximation based on a simplex method for solving the system, ii) multivariate optimisation that uses the Levenberg-Macquardt method of optimisation, and iii) artificial neural network approach.

C. Other parameters based on C_{chl} *a) Primary production*

Three algorithms are presented (Forms 18 to 20), which represent the state-of-the-art and the future trends in deriving primary production rate from satellite-derived chlorophyll and surface temperature.

b) Trophic state index (TSI)

The trophic state index (Carlson, 1977 [164]) for lakes yields continuous values scaled between 0 and 100 based either on Secchi disk transparency, chlorophyll-a concentration, or total phosphorus content. A TSI between 40 and 50 can be assigned to mesotrophic state, whereas values of more than 80 correspond to hypertrophic conditions. The TSI permits the comparison of the trophic state of lakes where only one or another parameter was measured. The trophic state index based on chlorophyll-a (TSI_{chl}) is calculated using Carlson's formula:

$$TSI_{chl} = 10 \left(6 - \frac{2.04 - 0.68 \log[Chl - a]}{\log 2} \right)$$

Chlorophyll-a content of $7.25 \mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$ results in an intermediate TSI_{chl} of 50. The TSI_{chl} is very sensitive for low chlorophyll-a concentrations. The standard deviation for chlorophyll-a determination from field spectra is about $7 \mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$ (Thiemann & Kaufman, 1998 [225]). A variation of 1 to 7 chlorophyll-a results in a TSI_{chl} of 30.6 and $49.7 \mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$ respectively. On the contrary, at high concentrations of 90 to $97 \mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$, the TSI_{chl} varies only between 74.7 and 75.4. Thus, trophic state index based on chlorophyll-a gives more reliable results for eutrophic than for mesotrophic lakes.

III.2.1.2 Concentration of suspended matter

Coastal and inland waters are often characterised by a high load of suspended sediment arising from either land and river discharge or re-suspension of sedimented material through hydrodynamics processes. There have been many studies in which the total suspended matter

(TSM) concentration has been derived by remote sensing techniques using sensors such as SPOT-XS, Landsat-TM, Landsat-MSS, NOAA-AVHRR and CZCS.

One major problem in monitoring organic and inorganic trace substances including heavy metals is that some have a strong relationship to suspended particles. Due to this fact it is difficult to monitor these substances from ships because their distribution is much more inhomogeneous than the distribution of substances which are dissolved. Thus, it is of high interest to monitor suspended matter as a proxy for all substances, which are bounded to it. Suspended sediment as an important carrier for these micropollutants is a strong argument for remote sensing.

A. Present algorithms

Suspended sediment concentration retrieval can be particularly effective as an increase in sediment concentration results in an increase in the backscattering coefficient and hence an increase in the emergent flux. However the high concentrations of phytoplankton and dissolved organic matter found in coastal waters can complicate the signal received at the sensor. Usually the best waveband for extraction of suspended sediment concentration is in the red part of the spectrum as here absorption is due mainly to the water itself and therefore fluctuation in absorption from area to area is not large (Vos and Schuttelaar, 1995 [228]). Some suspended sediment algorithms use combinations of reflectances (forms 21, 22, 23 and 26) rather than the value in a single waveband (forms 23 and 25).

We may note that the algorithm presented in form 26, and that was developed for CZCS, can also be applied to other ocean colour data such as those from SeaWiFS, OCTS and MOS.

Xia (1993 [231]) has proposed an alternative method as an improved unified model (form 23).

B. Expected improvements

The expected improvements are linked to the development of multiple parameter retrieval algorithms.

III.2.1.3 Concentration of Coloured Dissolved Organic Matter

CDOM is used for characterising terrestrial discharge in coastal waters, as well as organic decomposition level. Presence of CDOM affects the entire spectral signature of a water body, as well as the accuracy of retrieval of other substances in coastal and inland waters, because of its specific optical properties (absorption in UV and blue part of the solar spectrum and inelastic scattering (fluorescence)). Multiple parameter retrieval algorithms have proved capable of deriving CDOM concentration by estimating the CDOM absorption properties at wavelength of 380 to 440 nm. Algorithms developed so far concerning this parameters are presented in forms 15 to 17, and 11.

III.2.1.4 Concentration of detritus

Recently, a first attempt for retrieving detritus concentration has been presented by Pozdnyakov *et al.* (1998 [212]) based on a neural network approach. This algorithm is described in form 16.

III.2.2 Optical properties

The water optical properties are fundamental parameters that define the physical characteristics of the water column, with regards to light. They are commonly divided in two categories.

The inherent optical properties are the basic physical properties of the water column optically-active components, i.e., water itself and water constituents, and are independent of the light field distribution in the water. These are the absorption, scattering and attenuation coefficients (a , b , $c = a+b$), which describe the capability of the water column to absorb, scatter and attenuate light,

respectively, and the volume scattering function, which describe the angular distribution of the scattering process. Only the three first can be derived from EO data.

The apparent optical properties referred to the global properties of the water column as one can measure them. They depend upon the light field distribution. Two of them are of concern in the study, namely the diffuse attenuation coefficient for downwelling irradiance, K_d , and the volume irradiance reflectance, R . Other parameters can be assimilated to apparent optical properties, e.g., Secchi disk depth, Z_{SD} , and chromaticity index. Besides, one important environmental parameter, the photic depth, can be derived from an estimate of K_d .

III.2.2.1 Inherent optical properties (a, b)

Even if absorption and scattering coefficient of bulk water are of minor interest for operational application, we chose to present two algorithms related to these parameters as they are the basis of other semi-analytical ocean colour models for water constituents retrieval, which will certainly become very important in the future.

A. Present algorithms

No operational or pre-operational algorithms have been proposed so far.

B. Expected improvements

Retrieval algorithms for deriving inherent optical properties (IOPs) of natural waters from EO data are being developed in the course of the SeaWiFS scientific programme. Forms 28 and 29 describe methods implemented for deriving either bulk or water-constituent-specific IOPs.

III.2.2.2 Diffuse attenuation coefficient

Diffuse attenuation coefficient is often mentioned as an important parameter as it is representative of the turbidity of the medium, as well as it gives access to other parameters such as the photic depth.

A. Present algorithms

Several empirical models have been proposed to correlate radiance/reflectance measured by EO sensors such as Landsat-MSS, CZCS, and SeaWiFS to the diffuse attenuation coefficient. Forms 32 and 33 give the regression coefficients obtained by several authors for different regions. Form 30 presents the relationships established by Dekker (1993 [167]) for lakes and rivers in the Netherlands. Form 31 briefly describes the Bierwith method (Bierwirth *et al.*, 1993 [157]) for retrieving bottom type and attenuation coefficient in clear water, based on Landsat data.

B. Expected improvements

The international scientific community does not support much effort on new algorithm and improved methods to derive this parameter. Thus no improvement is expected in the near future.

C. Derivable parameter: photic depth

In form 33, we describe the most common and simple way of deriving the photic depth from the diffuse attenuation coefficient.

III.2.2.3 Turbidity / Secchi disk depth

Depth estimated by Secchi depth measurement is a very popular field method as it is very simple and cheap to carry out. For this reason, models have been developed for deriving an equivalent quantity from EO data. As examples two such models are presented in forms 34 and 35.

III.2.2.4 Water colour

The CIE-algorithm described in form 36 is an experimental algorithm, presently under development. It aims at characterising the water colour by its radiometric colour as defined by chromaticity co-ordinates.

III.2.3 Surface Temperature

The surface temperature as measured by space sensor is representative of the water/atmosphere interface. Remote sensed temperature may be more or less representative of the skin (most frequent case), or the bulk, or the air near to surface, depending on sea wind/roughness and on the spectral band used to perform the observation (IR or microwave).

A. Present algorithms

The most popular algorithm for surface temperature retrieval from EO sensor is based on the so-called Split-window method, which use two bands in the thermal infrared for correcting for varying atmospheric emission and transmission when retrieving temperature. This type of algorithm is fully operational and used with both NOAA-AVHRR and ERS-ATSR data (form 37 and 38). Single band algorithms are also available such as the one presented in form 39 and based on Landsat-TM band 6.

B. Expected improvements

The main expected improvements should lead to an accuracy of 0.1 K.

It is recognised that the spatial resolution of surface temperature sensors (1 km) is not adequate for coastal and inland applications. This should be a major realm of improvement in the near future while higher spatial resolution (up to 60 m) is required.

III.2.4 Depth-related parameters

III.2.4.1 Water depth & bottom topography

A. Present algorithms

The state-of-the-art in deriving bathymetric and bottom topography maps is presented in forms 40 to 42. Both optical and radar remote sensing can be used to achieve the retrieval of depth related parameters, although very different approaches are implemented. Optical remote sensing assessment of bathymetry is based on light attenuation in the water column, whereas SAR algorithms use the change of sea surface roughness due to bottom topography, and information on local currents for deriving the bathymetry.

B. Expected improvements

No improvement is expected related to presently launched sensors capabilities. Nevertheless, improvements may be achieved, in particular on optical algorithms, by developing more complex reflectance models and more robust mathematical approaches (see discussion on future improvements presented in Part IV of this report).

III.2.4.2 Water level

Water level is derived from averaging of wave heights as measured by altimeters, and with regards to a reference surface, generally taken as the geoid. One algorithm is shortly described in

form 43. However, altimeter does not give accurate measurements inland and close to the shore, because of the influence of the land on the signal.

III.2.5 Morphometry

Morphometry is a generic term that relates to parameters that can be quantified in term of distance, length, or area surface. Shoreline and oil spills are such parameters. Algorithms developed for shoreline detection and tracing, and for the determination of oil slick extent are presented in the next section.

III.2.5.1 Shoreline detection and tracing

Two algorithms are described in forms 44 and 45. One is only applicable to SAR images, whereas as the others can be used based either on optical or microwave images.

III.2.5.2 Oil spill detection and tracking

For information we have included the description of one algorithm for oil slick detection from SAR images (form 46).

III.3 Algorithm forms

Parameter: Concentration of chlorophyll ($C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}$) ($\mu\text{g/l}$)						Form: I		
Algorithm type: Polynomial		Algorithm name: TM		Range of pigments concentration values: 0.3 - 2 $\mu\text{g/l}$		Error (rms.) 0.14	References Forster <i>et al.</i> , 1993	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
Landsat TM	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1985 onwards	0.03	ca 18 day
Ancillary data:								
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>The algorithm applies to the radiance measured by the sensor Landsat TM. It defines the polynomial function of these radiances, which should be adjusted to existing measurements of total pigments.</p> $(C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}) = a_0 + a_1\text{TM1} + a_2\text{TM2} + a_3\text{TM3} + a_4\text{TM4} + a_5\text{TM1}^2 + a_6\text{TM2}^2$ <p>where TM_i are the TM spectral bands: TM1 (450-520 nm), TM2 (520-600 nm), TM3 (630-690 nm), TM4 (760-900 nm).</p> <p>The coefficients a_i are to be determined by e.g., a least-squares regression analysis. They are site dependent as well as time dependent.</p> <p>For a sewage out-fall site off the Case II waters of North Head of Sydney Harbour, Australia, the following values were found for June 13, 1989:</p> <p>$a_0=361.26$ $a_1=-18.43$ $a_2=-2.85$ $a_3=-0.43$ $a_4=-0.14$ $a_5=0.25$ $a_6=0.15$</p>								

Parameter: Concentration of chlorophyll ($C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}$) ($\mu\text{g/l}$)						Form: 2		
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: Radiance ratio		Range of pigments concentration values: 0.02 -20		Accuracy: $\pm 40\%$	References Gordon & Morel, 1983	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
CZCS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	1978- 1986	1	ca 1 day
<p><u>Ancillary data</u>: requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)</p>								
<p><u>Algorithm description</u>:</p> <p>$(C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}) = AR_{ij}^B$, where</p> <p>$R_{ij} = L_u(\lambda_1) / L_u(\lambda_2)$, $L_u(\lambda)$ is the radiance coming up from beneath the water surface</p> <p>The regressions presented in the table hereafter have been computed using extended worldwide <i>in situ</i> data sets. "Case I & II" flag refers to regression performed including <i>in situ</i> data of both Case I and Case II waters.</p> <p>The band 443 nm should be avoided in case of high turbidity or high chlorophyll concentration (i.e., $C > 1.5 \mu\text{g/l}$).</p>								
	λ_1	λ_2	A	B	r^2	Case	Authors	
(1)	443	550	0.50	-1.27	0.98	I	Gordon & Clark, 1980	
(2)	443	550	0.78	-2.12	0.94	I	Smith, 1981	
(3)	443	550	0.765	-1.329	0.91	I & II	Clark, 1981	
(4)	443	520	0.550	-1.806	0.87	I & II	Clark, 1981	
(5)	520	550	1.694	-4.449	0.91	I & II	Clark, 1981	
(6)	520	670	43.853	-1.372	0.87	I & II	Clark, 1981	
<p>These algorithms have a wide range of applications but perform poorly in coastal and inland waters</p>								

Parameter: Concentration of chlorophyll ($C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}$) ($\mu g/l$)							Form: 3
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: CZCS - NASA		Range of pigments concentration values: 0.029 - 77.7		Accuracy: $\pm 40\%$	References Gordon <i>et al.</i> , 1983
Sensor name CZCS	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)
	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	1978- 1986	1
temporal resolution (at 45° N) ca 1 day							
<u>Ancillary data</u> : requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)							
<p>Algorithm description:</p> <p>The Gordon radiance ratio empirical algorithm has been determined using worldwide data set acquired in both Case I & II waters. It is used and recommended by the NASA for CZCS data processing and is part of the SeaDAS software freely available from the SeaWiFS web site at NASA/GSFC.</p> <p>$\log (C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}) = \log A - B \log R_{ij}$,</p> <p>where $R_{ij} = L_w(\lambda_1) / L_w(\lambda_2)$, and $L_w(\lambda)$ is the water-leaving radiance,</p> <p>can be applied to Case I and Case II waters depending on the choice of tuning coefficients values and the bands used.</p> <p>The regressions presented in the table hereafter have been computed using extended worldwide in situ data sets. Case I & II flag refers to regression performed including data of both Case I and Case II waters.</p>							
	λ_1	λ_2	log A	B	r^2	Case	Range of concentration
(1)	443	550	0.053	1.71	0.96	I	$0.029 < (C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}) < 5.4$
(2)	443	550	-0.116	-1.33	0.91	I & II	$0.029 < (C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}) < 77.7$
(3)	520	550	0.229	4.45	0.91	I & II	$0.029 < (C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}) < 77.7$
(4)	520	550	0.522	2.44	0.93	I & II	$1.5 < (C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}) < 21.3$
These algorithms have a wide range of applications but perform poorly in coastal and inland waters.							

Parameter: Concentration of chlorophyll ($C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}$) ($\mu\text{g/l}$)						Form: 4			
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: Reflectance ratio		Range of pigments concentration values: 0.03 - 22		Maximum error outer-limits: likely > 100 %		References Morel, 1980 Sturm, 1982	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
CZCS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	1978- 1986	1	ca 1 day	
<u>Ancillary data:</u> requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)									
<u>Algorithm description:</u> This algorithm is actually a compilation of several ones, which have all the same form. Inputs are reflectances. It is applicable to open waters and coastal waters. The band 443 nm should be avoided in case of high turbidity. $(C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}) = A R_{ij}^B$, where $R_{ij} = R(\lambda_1) / R(\lambda_2)$, $R(\lambda)$ is the volume reflectance at zero depth, just beneath the surface.									
	λ_1	λ_2	A	B	r^2	Case	Authors		
(1)	440	560	1.62	-1.40	0.76	I & II	Morel, 1980		
(2)	440	560	1.92	-1.80	0.97	I	Morel, 1980		
(3)	443	550	1.92	-1.80	-	I & II	Sturm, 1982 $C_{chl} < 1.5 \text{ mg.m}^{-3}$		
(4)	520	550	0.729	-3.37	-	I & II	Sturm, 1982 $C_{chl} > 1.5 \text{ mg.m}^{-3}$		
(4)	443	550	1.73	-2.04	0.939	I	Bricaud & Morel, 1987 $C_{chl} < 1.5 \text{ mg.m}^{-3}$		
(5)	520	550	2.51	-6.38	0.909	I	Bricaud & Morel, 1987 $C_{chl} > 1.5 \text{ mg.m}^{-3}$		
These algorithms have a wide range of applications but perform poorly in coastal and inland waters.									

Parameter: Concentration of chlorophyll C_{chl} ($\mu\text{g/l}$)							Form: 5																																																																																
Algorithm type: Band ratio	Algorithm name: Cubic polynomial		Range of pigments concentration values: 0.019 - 32.79		Maximum error outer-limits: - 20 - + 300%		References O'Reilly <i>et al.</i> , 1998 Sturm, 1993																																																																																
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)																																																																															
CZCS POLDER SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	1996- 1997	1 - 5	ca 3 days																																																																															
<u>Ancillary data</u> : requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)																																																																																							
<p>Algorithm description:</p> <p>These algorithms can be confidently applied only to coastal which could be qualified as Case I waters. The European algorithm was proposed for retrievals of C_{chl} pertaining to case-I waters with, respectively, moderate and high phytoplankton chlorophyll concentrations.</p> <p>Exponential form used for CZCS: $C_{chl} = \exp(a + bR + cR^2 + dR^3)$ where $R = \log R_{rs}(\lambda_1) / R_{rs}(\lambda_2)$, $R_{rs}(\lambda)$ is the remote sensing reflectance.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Name</th> <th>λ_1</th> <th>λ_2</th> <th>a</th> <th>b</th> <th>c</th> <th>d</th> <th>Authors</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>André-1</td> <td>443</td> <td>550</td> <td>0.347</td> <td>-2.73</td> <td>2.14</td> <td>-2.04</td> <td>André & Morel, 1991 $C_{chl} < 2 \text{ mg.m}^{-3}$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>André-2</td> <td>520</td> <td>550</td> <td>0.661</td> <td>-8.48</td> <td>11.52</td> <td>-88.38</td> <td>André & Morel, 1991 $C_{chl} > 1 \text{ mg.m}^{-3}$</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sturm-1</td> <td>443</td> <td>550</td> <td>0.768</td> <td>-2.611</td> <td>0.79</td> <td>-0.388</td> <td>Sturm, 1993</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Sturm-2</td> <td>520</td> <td>550</td> <td>1.395</td> <td>-8.739</td> <td>5.7286</td> <td>-27.950</td> <td>Sturm, 1993</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>The value of $R_{rs}(443)$ was used as a criterion for the transition from Sturm-1 to Sturm-2: if it becomes very small approaching a predefined threshold (= 0.4), then a transition from Eq.(1) to Eq.(2) should be done.</p> <p>Power form used for SeaWiFS and POLDER: $C_{chl} = 10^{(a + bR + cR^2 + dR^3)}$ where $R = \log R_{rs}(\lambda_1) / R_{rs}(\lambda_2)$, $R_{rs}(\lambda)$ is the remote sensing reflectance.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Name</th> <th>λ_1</th> <th>λ_2</th> <th>a</th> <th>b</th> <th>c</th> <th>d</th> <th>Authors</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>POLDER</td> <td>443</td> <td>555</td> <td>0.438</td> <td>-2.114</td> <td>0.916</td> <td>0.851</td> <td>NASDA(unpubl.)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CalCOFI Two-bands</td> <td>490</td> <td>555</td> <td>0.450</td> <td>-2.860</td> <td>0.996</td> <td>0.3674</td> <td>Mitchell & Kahru, 1998</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Morel-3</td> <td>443</td> <td>555</td> <td>0.20766</td> <td>-1.82878</td> <td>0.75885</td> <td>0.73979</td> <td>Morel (unpubl.)</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Morel-4</td> <td>490</td> <td>555</td> <td>1.03117</td> <td>-2.40134</td> <td>0.3219897</td> <td>0.291066</td> <td>Morel (unpubl.)</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>The validation of the Morel-3 algorithm revealed that its intercept is 0.040, the slope 0.970, $r^2 = 0.915$, $rms = 0.183$ for the entire range of chlorophyll concentrations (0.019 - $33 \mu\text{g/l}$). Its application will give better results for waters with $C_{chl} \leq 5 \mu\text{g/l}$.</p>								Name	λ_1	λ_2	a	b	c	d	Authors	André-1	443	550	0.347	-2.73	2.14	-2.04	André & Morel, 1991 $C_{chl} < 2 \text{ mg.m}^{-3}$	André-2	520	550	0.661	-8.48	11.52	-88.38	André & Morel, 1991 $C_{chl} > 1 \text{ mg.m}^{-3}$	Sturm-1	443	550	0.768	-2.611	0.79	-0.388	Sturm, 1993	Sturm-2	520	550	1.395	-8.739	5.7286	-27.950	Sturm, 1993	Name	λ_1	λ_2	a	b	c	d	Authors	POLDER	443	555	0.438	-2.114	0.916	0.851	NASDA(unpubl.)	CalCOFI Two-bands	490	555	0.450	-2.860	0.996	0.3674	Mitchell & Kahru, 1998	Morel-3	443	555	0.20766	-1.82878	0.75885	0.73979	Morel (unpubl.)	Morel-4	490	555	1.03117	-2.40134	0.3219897	0.291066	Morel (unpubl.)
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Parameter: Concentration of chlorophyll C_{chl} ($\mu\text{g/l}$)						Form: 6		
Algorithm type: Band ratio	Algorithm name: ocean chlorophyll 2 (OC2)- cubic polynomial		Range of C_{chl} values: 0.019-33		Maximum error outer-limits: 100 - 200% $\in C_{chl} \leq 1$ 50 - 400% $\in C_{chl} \geq 10$		References O'Reilly <i>et al.</i> , 1998	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1997 onwards	1.1	ca 1 day
<u>Ancillary data:</u> requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)								
<u>Algorithm description:</u> The OC-2 algorithm can be applied for such coastal waters which qualify as Case I waters with the trophic status ranging from <i>oceanic</i> oligotrophic to eutrophic (oligotrophic ($< 0.3 \mu\text{g/l}$), mesotrophic ($0.3 - 1.5 \mu\text{g/l}$) and eutrophic ($> 1.5 \mu\text{g/l}$)). The updated coefficients (summer 1998) in the operational OC-2 that are available at the time of this report give the following relationship: $C_{chl} = 10^{(0.2974 - 2.2429R + 0.8358R^2 - 0.0077R^3)} - 0.0929, \quad (1)$ where $R = \log(R_{rs}(490\text{nm}) / R_{rs}(555\text{nm}))$ When tested against ground truth data (extended NASA SeaBAM data set), it yielded very good statistical results ($r^2 = 0.918$, $rms = 0.172$), and it revealed an ideal slope (1.000) and intercept (0.000). Being good as a sole algorithm for a wide spectrum of chlorophyll concentrations, it nevertheless determines relatively less successfully low concentrations of chlorophyll (which occurs in clear oligotrophic and ultra-oligotrophic waters). The OC-2 algorithm can be used after application of atmospheric correction to the values of the radiance signal captured by SeaWiFS. It also implies the use of remote sensing reflectances $R_{rs} = L_w / E_d$, where L_w is the water leaving radiance, and E_d is the incident irradiance at the air/water interface. This, in turn, necessitates elimination of the water surface reflection-driven component L_{ws} from L_w .								

Parameter: Concentration of chlorophyll C_{chl} ($\mu\text{g/l}$)						Form: 7			
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of C_{chl} values:		Maximum error outer-limits:		References	
Maximum band ratio		ocean chlorophyll (OC4)-modified cubic polynomial		0.019-33		- 40 - + 100 % $\in C_{chl} \leq 1$ - 30 - + 300 % $\in C_{chl} \geq 10$		O'Reilly <i>et al.</i> , 1998	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1997 onwards	1.1	ca 1 day	
<p><u>Ancillary data</u>: requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)</p>									
<p><u>Algorithm description</u>:</p> <p>The maximum band ratio (MBR) algorithm (OC4) is a new approach in empirical ocean colour regression algorithms. It has the potential advantage of maintaining the highest possible satellite sensor signal: noise reflectance ratio over a broad range of chlorophyll concentrations. The OC4 algorithm is only applicable to such <i>coastal waters</i> which qualify as Case I waters, in within this area the OC4 might be useful to define operationally three realms with respect to <i>oceanic</i> trophic status: oligotrophic (< 0.3 $\mu\text{g/l}$), mesotrophic (0.3 - 1.5 $\mu\text{g/l}$) and eutrophic (> 1.5 $\mu\text{g/l}$) depending on whether radiances in 443 nm, 490 nm, or 510 nm bands dominate:</p> $C_{chl} = 10^{(0.4708 - 3.8469R + 4.5338R^2 - 2.444R^3)} - 0.041,$ <p>where $R = (\log(R_{rs}(443\text{nm}) > R_{rs}(490\text{nm}) > R_{rs}(510\text{nm}) / R_{rs}(555\text{nm})))$.</p> <p>The OC4 algorithm validation against ground truth data yielded very high values of r^2 (= 0.932) and low values of rms (= 0.156), and it revealed an ideal slope (1.000) and intercept (0.000). Of the three band ratios considered, $R_{rs}(443) / R_{rs}(555)$ was maximal for oligotrophic waters, $R_{rs}(490) / R_{rs}(555)$ generally dominated for mesotrophic waters and $R_{rs}(510) / R_{rs}(555)$ - for eutrophic waters. The ranges of dominant band ratios overlap by approximately 10-30%, so there is a smooth transition from $R_{rs}(443) / R_{rs}(555)$ to $R_{rs}(510) / R_{rs}(555)$ and to $R_{rs}(510) / R_{rs}(555)$ with decreasing band ratio. This overlap is a desirable property as it implies that the discontinuities in chlorophyll concentration estimations are unlikely.</p> <p>The OC-4 algorithm can be used after application of atmospheric correction to the values of the radiance signal captured by SeaWiFS. It also implies the use of remote sensing reflectances $R_{rs} = L_w / E_d$, where L_w is the water leaving radiance, and E_d is the incident irradiance at the air/water interface. This, in turn, necessitates elimination of the water surface reflection-driven component L_{ws} from L_w.</p>									

Parameter: Concentration of chlorophyll C_{chl} ($\mu\text{g/l}$)						Form: 8			
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: power		Range of pigments concentration values: 0.019 - 32.79		Maximum error outer-limits: - 20 - + 300%		References O'Reilly <i>et al.</i> , 1998	
Sensor name		Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
OCTS SeaWiFS		airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	1996- 1997	1	ca 3 days
<u>Ancillary data</u> : requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)									
<u>Algorithm description</u> :									
These algorithms can be confidently applied only to coastal which could be qualified as Case I waters .									
General forms:									
$C_{chl} = 10^{(a+bR)}$ in OCTS-C, CalCOFI and Morel-1									
$C_{chl} = \exp^{(a+bR)}$ in Morel-2									
OCTS-C power radiance ratio empirical algorithm a = -.55006; b = 3.497 and $R = \log L_w(520 + 565 \text{ nm}) / L_w(490 \text{ nm})$, and $L_w(\lambda)$ is the water leaving radiance. The validation of the OCTS-C algorithm revealed that the intercept is 0.054, slope = 1.148, $r^2 = 0.933$, $rms = 0.190$. Besides, it is a non-linear retrieval tool.									
SeaWiFS power radiance ratio empirical algorithm									
<u>CalCOFI two-bands</u> (Mitchell & Kahru, 1998): a = 0.444; b = -2.431 and $R = \log L_w(490 \text{ nm}) / L_w(555 \text{ nm})$									
<u>Morel-1</u> : a = 0.2492; b = -1.768, and $R = \log R_{rs}(443 \text{ nm}) / R_{rs}(555 \text{ nm})$									
<u>Morel -2</u> uses an exponential relationship: a = 1.077835; b = -2.542605 and $R = \ln R_{rs}(490 \text{ nm}) / R_{rs}(555 \text{ nm})$									

Parameter: Concentration of chlorophyll C_{chl} ($\mu\text{g/l}$) or ($C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}$) ($\mu\text{g/l}$)					Form: 9				
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: Hyperbolic + power		Range of pigments concentration values: 0.019 - 32.79		Maximum error outer-limits: - 20 - + 300%		References Aiken <i>et al.</i> , 1995	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
OCTS SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	1996- 1997	1	ca 3 days	
<u>Ancillary data</u> : requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)									
<p><u>Algorithm description</u>:</p> <p>These algorithms can be confidently applied only to coastal which could be qualified as Case I waters.</p> <p>General forms:</p> $C_{chl} \text{ or } (C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}) = \exp^{(a+b \ln R)} \text{ if } C_{chl} < 2.0 \mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$ $C_{chl} \text{ or } (C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}) = (R + c)/(d + e R) \text{ otherwise}$ <p>where $R = L_w(490\text{nm})/L_w(555\text{nm})$</p> <p>Aiken-C C_{chl} algorithm:</p> <p>a = 0.464; b = -1.989; c = -5.290; d = 0.719; e = -4.230</p> <p>Aiken-P ($C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}$) algorithm:</p> <p>a = 0.696; b = -2.085; c = -5.290; d = 0.592; e = -3.48</p>									

Parameter: Concentration of chlorophyll ($C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}$) ($\mu\text{g/l}$)						Form: 10			
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: Multiple regression		Range of pigments concentration values: 0.019 - 32		Maximum error outer-limits: -20 - +300%		References O'Reilly <i>et al.</i> , 1998	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
OCTS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	1978- 1986	1	ca 1 day	
SeaWiFS									
<u>Ancillary data</u> : requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)									
<p><u>Algorithm description</u>:</p> <p>These algorithms can be confidently applied only to coastal waters that could be qualified as Case I waters.</p> <p>General forms:</p> $(C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}) = 10^{(a+bR_1+cR_2)}$ $C_{chl} = \exp^{(a+bR_1+cR_2)}$ <p>OCTS-P multi-regression algorithm</p> $(C_{chl} + C_{phaeo}) = 10^{(0.19535 - 2.079R_1 - 3.497R_2)}$ <p>where $R_1 = \log(L_w(443)/L_w(520))$ and $R_2 = \log(L_w(490)/L_w(520))$ $L_w(\lambda)$ is the water-leaving radiance.</p> <p>SeaWiFS multi-regression algorithms (Mitchell & Kahru, 1998)</p> <p><u>CalCOFI three-bands</u></p> $C_{chl} = \exp^{(1.025 - 1.622R_1 - 1.238R_2)}$ <p>where $R_1 = \log(R_{rs}(490)/R_{rs}(555))$ and $R_2 = \log(R_{rs}(510)/R_{rs}(555))$ $R_{rs}(\lambda)$ is the remote sensing reflectance.</p> <p><u>CalCOFI four-bands</u></p> $C_{chl} = \exp^{(0.753 - 2.583R_1 + 1.389R_2)}$ <p>where $R_1 = \ln(R_{rs}(443)/R_{rs}(555))$ and $R_2 = \ln(R_{rs}(412)/R_{rs}(510))$ $R_{rs}(\lambda)$ is the remote sensing reflectance.</p>									

Parameter: C_{chl} ($\mu\text{g/l}$), C_{sm} (mg.l^{-1}), $a_y(440)$ (m^{-1})					Form: 11				
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: Tassan, multi-regression		Range of values: C_{chl} : 1-40 C_{sm} : 0.5 – 5.0 $a_y(440)$: 0.05 – 0.3		Accuracy: Site specific C_{chl} : $\pm 20\text{-}30\%$ C_{sm} : not specified $a_y(440)$: not specified		References Tassan, 1994	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1997 onwards	1.1	ca 1 day	
<u>Ancillary data</u> : requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)									
Algorithm description: Applying a hydro-optical water model based on specific inherent hydro-optical coefficients of phytoplankton and suspended minerals as well as on the Morel model (Morel, 1988) in the part concerning the scattering properties of water constituents, Tassan (1994) suggested a system of algorithms for the retrieval of optically active components (OAC). The author claims that he established steady regression relationships between major OAC for Case II waters . The following relationships allegedly hold for the Gulf of Naples and the northern margins of the Adriatic Sea: $\log C_{sm} = -A_1 + B_1 \lg C_{chl}, \quad (1) \quad \log[a_y(440)] = -A_2 + B_2 \lg C_{chl} \quad (2)$ where A_1, A_2, B_1, B_2 are the regression coefficients equal to 0.25; 0.026; 1.20; 1.28 for the waters of the Gulf of Naples; and 0.57; 0.59; 0.47; 0.38 for the Adriatic Sea, $a_y(440)$ is the <i>coloured dissolved organic matter</i> (CDOM) absorption coefficient at $\lambda = 440$ nm (spectral variations in a_y were assumed exponential with $S = -0.014 \text{ nm}^{-1}$: $a_y = a_y(\lambda_0) \exp[S(\lambda - \lambda_0)]$). The retrieval algorithm was developed in the form: $\log C_{chl} = 0.0664 + 0.0462 \lg(X_{chl}) - 4.144 \lg(X_{chl})^2 \quad (0.025 \leq C_{chl} (\mu\text{g/l}) \leq 1.0), \quad (3)$ where $X_{chl} = [R(443) / R(555)] [R(412) / R(490)]^{-1.2}$, R is the volume reflectance. For rich waters (chlorophyll $\in [1 - 40 \text{ mg/m}^3]$, suspended minerals $\in]0.56 - 4.6 \text{ g/m}^3]$ and CDOM ($a_y(440) \sim 0,2 \text{ m}^{-1}$), expression (4) should be used: $\log C_{chl} = 0.36 - 4.38 \lg(X_{chl}), \text{ where } X_{chl} = [R(443) / R(555)] [R(412) / R(490)]^{-0.5} \quad (4)$ Direct relationships for C_{sm} and $a_y(440)$ have been established for the same rich waters: $\log C_{sm} = 1.82 + 1.23 \cdot \lg(X_{sm}), \text{ where } X_{sm} = [R(555) / R(670)] [R(490) / R(555)]^{-1.2} \quad (5)$ $\log a_y(440) = -4.36 - 6.081 \cdot \log(X_y), \text{ where } X_y = [R(412) / R(555)] [R(490)]^{0.25} \quad (6)$ Assessment of sensitivity of algorithms (Eqs. 3-4) to fluctuations in concentrations of CDOM and suspended minerals relative to the respective values specified by regressions (Eqs. 1-2), indicate that the retrieval errors do not exceed 20 - 30%. However, regardless of such optimistic assertions, it appears clear that the application of retrieval algorithms (Eqs. 3 - 4) to arbitrarily chosen water areas belonging to Case-II waters will unavoidably require a fine tuning of regression coefficients to local conditions.									

Parameter: Concentration of chlorophyllous pigments C_{Σ} ($\mu\text{g/l}$)						Form: 12			
Algorithm type: Empirical correlation		Algorithm name: Campbell & Asaias spectral curvature algorithm		Range of values: 7 - 16		Maximum error outer-limits: less than $\pm 50\%$ (mean error - 23%)		References Habbane <i>et al.</i> , 1998	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
	SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared				microwave

Ancillary data: requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)

Algorithm description:

The Campbell & Asaias (**C&A**) spectral curvature algorithm is adjusted for the SeaWiFS bands by Habbane *et al.* (1998) to retrieve chlorophyll pigment concentrations (chlorophyll *a*, *b*, *c*) in coastal waters which qualify as strictly **Case I waters**:

$$\log C_{\Sigma} = 0.92 - 0.46\Delta^2 \log R(555), \quad (1)$$

where

$$\Delta^2 \log R(555) = \log R(670) - 2\log R(555) + \log R(443), \quad (2)$$

R is a subsurface volume reflectance which could be converted into its above surface counterpart:

$$R_w = \frac{0.52R(\lambda)}{(1 - 0.48R(\lambda))} \quad (3)$$

The field validation measurements revealed that the correlation coefficient for the **C&A** algorithm is about 0.47. The algorithm is thought to be immune to solar zenith θ_0 variations within a wide range of θ_0 .

The **C&A** algorithm can be used after application of atmospheric correction to the values of the radiance signal captured by SeaWiFS. It also implies both the necessity of transforming this algorithm into a function of remote sensing reflectance (Zaneveld, 1995, Shimwell *et al.*, 1996) and elimination of the water surface reflection-driven component L_{ws} from L_w .

Parameter: Concentration of chlorophyll C_{chl} ($\mu\text{g/l}$)						Form: 13		
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: NDPI		Range of C_{chl} values: 0.03 - 21.3 $\mu\text{g/l}$		Relative error (rms.)	References Frouin <i>et al.</i> , 1998	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
POLDER	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	1997 -1998	7	ca 1 day
<p><u>Ancillary data</u>: requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)</p>								
<p><u>Algorithm description</u>:</p> <p>This algorithm calls upon the Normalised Difference Phytoplankton Index (NDPI), which is defined as</p> $\text{NDPI} = (R_{rs}(443\text{nm}) - R_{rs}(565\text{nm})) / R_{rs}(490\text{nm})$ <p>and</p> $\log C_{chl} (\mu\text{g/l}) = 0.31847 - 1.05511 \text{ NDPI}$ <p>The algorithm applies to the water leaving reflectance R_{rs}, computed from: $R_{rs} = L_{rs}(+0) / E_d(+0)$, where $L_{rs}(+0)$ is the water leaving radiance, and $E_d(+0)$ is the incident (or downwelling) irradiance at the air/water interface.</p>								

Parameter: Concentration of chlorophyll C_{chl} ($\mu\text{g/l}$)						Form: 14			
Algorithm type: Semi-analytical		Algorithm name: Bates & Watts		Range of C_{chl} values: 0.019 - 10		Maximum error outer-limits: - 60 - +50% $\in C_{chl} \leq 1$ -100 - +100% \in 10 $\geq C_{chl} \geq 1$		References Garver & Siegel, 1997	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
	SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared				microwave
<u>Ancillary data:</u> requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)									
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>The Garver/Siegel model was initially developed for strictly oligotrophic oceanic waters (Case I waters) with C_{chl} under $0.4\mu\text{g/l}$. Further it was tested against oceanic meso-and eutrophic waters (also case I waters) for which the model showed its workability, but water with low range of C_{chl} waters are still the realm where it proves more efficient.</p> <p>This is a semi-analytic algorithm based on the quadratic form of the $b_b / a + b_b$ to R_{rs} :</p> $R_{rs} = \zeta \frac{L_u(\lambda)}{E_d(\lambda)} = \zeta \prod_{i=1}^2 \left[\frac{b_b(\lambda)}{b_b(\lambda) + a(\lambda)} \right]^i, \text{ where } \zeta = 0.48, l_1 = 0.0949\text{sr}^{-1}, l_2 = 0.0794 \text{sr}^{-1};$ <p>$b_b(\lambda) = b_{bw}(\lambda) + b_{bp}(\lambda)$,</p> <p>$b_{bw}$ is the backscatter due to pure seawater, $b_{bp}(\lambda)$ is the backscatter due to suspended particular matter,</p> <p>$a(\lambda) = a_w(\lambda) + a_{ph}(\lambda) + a_{dm}(\lambda)$,</p> <p>$a_w(\lambda)$ is the absorption due to seawater, $a_{ph}(\lambda)$ is the absorption due to phytoplankton, and $a_{dm}(\lambda)$ is the absorption due to the combined effects of coloured dissolved and detrital materials (CDM).</p> <p>The Garver/Siegel model uses pre-defined shapes for specific absorption $a(\lambda)$ and backscattering $b_b(\lambda)$ coefficients.</p> <p>$a_w(\lambda)$ and b_{bw} are suggested to be taken respectively from Pope and Fry (1997) and Morel (1974),</p> <p>$a_{dm}(\lambda) = a_{dm}(\lambda_0 = 440\text{nm}) \exp[S(\lambda - \lambda_0)]$, $S = -0.02 \text{ nm}^{-1}$, $b_{bp}(\lambda) = b_{bp}(\lambda_0) b_{bp}^*(\lambda)$, $b_{ph}^*(\lambda)$ being modelled as $(\lambda / \lambda_0)^{-1}$, $a_{ph}(\lambda) = C_{chl} a_{ph}^*(\lambda)$, $a_{ph}^*(\lambda)$ is the specific absorption coefficient to be taken from Bricaud <i>et al.</i>, 1995.</p> <p>The model inversion (through a non-linear statistical method, Bates and Watts, 1988) results in determination of $b_{bp}(\lambda_0), C_{chl}, a_{dm}(\lambda_0)$. The Garver/Siegel algorithm verification revealed that its intercept is 0.141, the slope is 0.776, $r^2 = 0.896$, $rms = 0.345$ for the chlorophyll concentration region extending from 0.01 to 33 $\mu\text{g/l}$.</p>									

Parameter: Concentration of C_{chl} ($\mu\text{g.l}^{-1}$), C_{sm} (mg.l^{-1}) and a_y (380) (m^{-1})					Form: 15			
Algorithm type:	Algorithm name:		Range of values:		Accuracy		References	
Multivariate optimisation	Two-flow approximation		C_{chl} : 0.02 - 50 C_{sm} : 0.1 - 30 a_y : 0.05 - 5.0		C_{chl} : ± 30 % C_{sm} : ± 50 % a_y : ± 30 %		Fischer & Doerffer, 1987 Doerffer & Fischer, 1994	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
CZCS MOS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	1978-1986	0.5 - 1	ca 1 day
<u>Ancillary data:</u> requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)								
<u>Algorithm description:</u>								
<p>This method of Doerffer & Fischer is applicable to both Case I and Case II waters. It has been developed for the CZCS sensor, but is applicable to other ocean colour data (SeaWiFS, OCTS, and future sensors). The algorithm is composed of four parts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ processing the CZCS data to calculate the “Rayleigh-corrected radiances” using Sturm, 1980 ➤ calibrating a two-flow approximation with a full radiative transfer forward model: $R = (k - a) / (k + a)$ $k_{tot} = k_{water} + C_{chl} k_{chl}^* + C_{sup} k_{sm}^* + k_{gelb}^*$ $a_{tot} = a_{water} + C_{chl} a_{chl}^* + C_{sup} a_{sm}^* + a_{gelb}^*$ <p>k_{tot} values (attenuation of the upward direct irradiance) is simulated for all four CZCS bands and for a large range of concentrations of chlorophyll-a, suspended matter and gelbstoff. Specific absorption for the three optically active components are taken from the literature (Prieur & Sathyendranath, 1981; Doerffer, 1979).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ modelling the Rayleigh-corrected radiance with a simple ocean-atmosphere radiative transfer model which includes the calibrated two-flow approximation ➤ minimising the χ^2 of the modelled and measured Rayleigh-corrected radiances with an optimisation algorithm (simplex method from Nelder & Mead, 1965) by searching within the four-dimensional space for an optimal combination of the concentrations of chlorophyll, suspended matter, and gelbstoff and the aerosol path radiance in the model. The convergence value chosen for χ^2 is 0.3. <p>The algorithm retrieves simultaneously the concentrations of chlorophyll-a, suspended matter, gelbstoff and the aerosol path radiance. This algorithm can be extremely time consuming. Thus a complementary approach has been proposed by Schiller & Doerffer (1993) in order to reduce the computing time. The two authors applied a parameterisation of the inverse two-flow approximation model through a Chebyshev expansion. By this method, a straightforward calculation of the parameters in question replaces the optimisation loop in the retrieval procedure for each pixel.</p>								

Parameter: C_{chl} ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$), C_{sm} ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$), $a_y(440)$ (m^{-1}), C_{det} ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)						Form: 16			
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of values:		Accuracy		References	
Multiple non linear regression		Neural networks (NN)		C_{chl} : 0.1 - 50 C_{sm} : 0.1 - 15 $a_y(440)$: 0.1 - 20 C_{det} : 10 - 15 % C_{chl}		C_{chl} : ± 50 % C_{sm} : ± 50 % $a_y(440)$: ± 30 % C_{det} : unknown yet		Pozdnyakov <i>et al.</i> , 1998 Schiller & Doerffer, 1997	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
SeaWiFS MOS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1997 onwards	1.1	ca 1 day	
Ancillary data:									
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>A general presentation of artificial neural network is given in Part I, section 1.4.</p> <p>The NN algorithm reported by Pozdnyakov <i>et al.</i> (1998) for the retrieval of Case-I and Case II water quality parameters, is a fed-forward network with the back propagation function. It comprises 6 neurones in the input layer, 12 - in the first hidden layer, 15 in the second hidden layer and 3 - in the output layer.</p> <p>The input values for the NN algorithm are the remote sensing reflectance R_{rs} at the SeaWiFS wavelengths in the visible spectrum. The output values are the concentrations in phytoplankton chlorophyll, suspended sediments and coloured dissolved organic matter.</p> <p>An important <u>advantage</u> of this technique is that it provides for retrieving <i>contemporaneously</i> the concentrations of <i>all</i> optically active water constituents (OAC) included into the hydro-optical model used to calculate the remote sensing reflectance $R(0,\lambda)$. Besides, this approach is applicable to a wide range of the OAC concentrations, including hydro-optical situations when C_{doc} is in excess of 5-10 gC/m^3. It is also an important advantage of this technique that it does not require the existence of correlation between the concentrations of major OAC whereas many case I water quality retrieval algorithms do.</p> <p>The NN algorithm is believed to be particularly efficient in the case of sounding waters rich in OAC. It has been chosen as the best candidate water constituent retrieval algorithm in Case II water for MERIS (Doerffer and Schiller, 1997). Algorithm validation is in progress using MOS data (Doerffer, 1998).</p> <p>Substantiated estimations of retrieval accuracy are determined by the actual applicability of the hydro-optical model to the water body/water mass targeted by the remote sensor.</p>									

Parameter: C_{chl} ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$), C_{sm} ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$) and $a_y(440)$ (m^{-1})						Form: 17			
Algorithm type: Multivariate optimisation		Algorithm name: Levenberg-Marquardt (L-M)		Range of values: C_{chl} : 0.02 - 50 C_{sm} : 0.1 - 15 a_y : 0.1 - 20		Accuracy ± 50 %		References Kondratyev <i>et al.</i> , 1990	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
	SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared				microwave
MOS									
<p><u>Ancillary data:</u> requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)</p>									
<p>Algorithm description:</p> <p>The L-M algorithm, which is applicable both to Case I and Case II waters, is a multidimensional least-square solution to the inverse (i.e., water quality retrieval) problem (at the SeaWiFS wavelengths) that is sought through minimising over the concentration vector $\mathbf{C} = (1, C_{chl}, C_{sm}, C_y)$ the function of residuals</p> $f(\mathbf{C}) = \sum_j g_j^2(\mathbf{C}), \text{ where } g_j(\mathbf{C}) = \{R_{rs}(\lambda_j) - R[\mathbf{a}_j^*, \mathbf{b}_j^*, \mathbf{C}]\} / R_{rs}(\lambda_j), \quad (1)$ <p>$R_{rs}(\lambda_j)$ is the remote sensing reflectance as measured by the space sensor at a wavelength λ_j, $R[\mathbf{a}_j^*, \mathbf{b}_j^*, \mathbf{C}]$ is the remote sensing reflectance modelled as a function of \mathbf{C}, absorption, and backscattering cross sections (at λ_j) of major optically active components which are encompassed by the model. As such is used the model suggested for Lake Ladoga (Kondratyev <i>et al.</i>, 1990), which is a set of tabulated values of \mathbf{a}_j^* and \mathbf{b}_j^* for phytoplankton (<i>Chl</i>), suspended matter (<i>sm</i>), and CDOM. at the SeaWiFS wavelength:</p> $\mathbf{a}^*(\lambda) = [a_w(\lambda), a_{chl}^*(\lambda), a_{sm}^*(\lambda), a_y^*(\lambda), \dots];$ $\mathbf{b}_b^*(\lambda) = [b_{b_w}(\lambda), b_{b_{chl}}^*(\lambda), b_{b_{sm}}^*(\lambda), 0, \dots];$ $\mathbf{C} = (1, C_{chl}, C_{sm}, C_y, \dots).$ <p>The parameterisation $R[\mathbf{a}_j^*, \mathbf{b}_j^*, \mathbf{C}]$ is taken from Bukata <i>et al.</i> (1995) for Lake Ontario. A search for the function $f(\mathbf{C})$ absolute minimum is further carried out utilising the finite difference calculation algorithm appropriate for such multivariate non-linear least-squares optimisation applications. The result thus obtained can be then interpreted as the desired concentration vector \mathbf{C} for the location where the spectrum R_{rs} has been recorded (the method of searching for the absolute minimum of $f(\mathbf{C})$ could be found in Kondratyev <i>et al.</i> (1990). A very important advantage of this technique is that it provides for retrieving <i>contemporaneously</i> the concentrations of <i>all</i> OAC included into the hydro-optical model used to calculate the remote sensing reflectance. Besides, this approach is applicable to a wide range of the OAC concentrations, including hydro-optical situations when C_y is in excess of 5-10 gC/m^3. This technique does not prerequisite the existence of correlation between the concentrations of major OAC whereas many Case I water retrieval algorithms do. The L-M algorithm has not gone through a thorough ground truth validation, and consequently lacks substantiated estimations of retrieval accuracy, which greatly is determined by the actual applicability of the hydro-optical model to the water body/water mass targeted by the remote sensor. The L-M algorithm is believed to be efficient in the case of sounding waters rich in OAC.</p>									

Parameter: Primary production P^B ($\text{mgC}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$)					Form: 18			
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of P^B values:		Accuracy:	Reference	
Radiance ratio & analytic		Bedford		0.5 - 3.0		about 15%	Platt & Sathyendranath, 1988	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
	CZCS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared			
<p>Ancillary data: Those of the chlorophyll algorithm used, plus cloud coverage, surface chlorophyll, parameters describing the water-column distribution of biomass (depth-profile) and parameters describing the photosynthetic response of phytoplankton to light</p>								
<p>Algorithm description:</p> <p>This algorithm applies to such coastal waters that qualify as Case I waters. Bedford model is an analytical model that uses sea-surface chlorophyll concentration derived from EO sensors in order to: first, estimate the vertical distribution of chlorophyll; secondly, use these modelled chlorophyll profiles and either measurements of surface irradiance or modelled irradiance based on location and date to calculate, from physical principles of light attenuation, the vertical distribution of spectral irradiance; and thirdly, calculate depth-dependent primary production using modelled chlorophyll normalised photosynthesis (P^B) and irradiance (I) distributions, and empirical relationships describing variability in light-saturated and light-limited carbon fixation (i.e., the P^B vs. I relationship).</p> <p>Bedford model requires four classes of information: cloud coverage, surface chlorophyll, parameters describing the water-column distribution of biomass (depth-profile) and parameters describing the photosynthetic response of phytoplankton to light. Typically, these data would be organised so that the appropriate values can be retrieved as functions of location and date. The spatial and temporal resolution required of the data will depend on the task.</p> <p>For the purpose of computing an annual estimate, production values for the 15th day of each month can be generated using CZCS- and cloud-coverage data sets provided as monthly means. The latitude and day number dictate the zenith angle of the sun, which in turn determines surface irradiance.</p> <p>Depth-profiles for photosynthetically active biomass, $B(z)$ are required. $B(z)$ is then used to compute the diffuse attenuation coefficient at any depth. Using the attenuation coefficient and surface irradiance, irradiance available at each depth throughout the photic zone can be determined. Then, only parameters describing the photosynthetic response of chlorophyll biomass to light for a region and season are needed to estimate primary production at any depth. The latter relation is provided through production models that use two parameters as input: the initial slope α^B of the relationship between photosynthesis and irradiance and assimilation number P_m^B that is the maximum photosynthesis per unit chlorophyll.</p> $P^B = P_m^B \left(1 - \exp \left[-\alpha^B \frac{I}{P_m^B} \right] \right)$ <p>The calculation of daily water column production requires a triple integration of P^B values over visible wavelength (PAR: Photosynthesis Available Radiation), photic depth and daytime (from dawn to dusk).</p>								

Parameter: Primary production P^B ($\text{mgC}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$)						Form: 19			
Algorithm type: Radiance ratio & semi-analytic		Algorithm name: LPCM		Range of P ($\text{mgC}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{d}$) values: 0.05 - 10		Accuracy: 100%		References Antoine <i>et al.</i> , 1996	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
CZCS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	1978- 1986	1	ca 1 day	
<p><u>Ancillary data</u>: requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)</p>									
<p><u>Algorithm description</u>:</p> <p>This algorithm applies to such coastal waters that qualify as Case I waters. It is based on the Morel global equation:</p> $P = (1/J_C) <C_{chl}>_{tot} E_d(PAR,0+)dt \cdot \psi^*$ <p>where $<C_{chl}>_{tot}$ represents the column integrated chlorophyll content, $E_d(PAR,0+)dt$ is the photosynthetically available radiant energy (within the spectral range 400 - 700 nm) incident at the sea level per unit area and for a given lap of time (e.g., one day); the factor ψ^* has the dimension of a cross section of algae for photosynthesis per unit of areal chlorophyll biomass. Its value is calculated from the date, latitude, cloudiness, temperature and surface chlorophyll concentration as input parameters, J_C is the energetic equivalent of photosynthetic assimilation = $39 \text{ kJ}\cdot(\text{gC})^{-1}$.</p> <p>Given a chlorophyll concentration field, derived from space observations, it should be converted in to $<C_{chl}>_{tot}$ according to the algorithm described in Morel and Berthon (1989). The photosynthetically available radiation should be either directly measured for the time interval chosen, calculated from models (e.g., Bishop and Rossow, 1991), or assessed from EO data (e.g., Cano <i>et al.</i>, 1986).</p>									

Parameter: Primary production P^B ($\text{mgC}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$)						Form:20			
Algorithm type: Radiance ratio & empirical		Algorithm name: VGPM		Range of P ($\text{mgC}/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{d}$) values: 0.5 - 3.0		Accuracy: 15 %		References Behrenfeld & Falkowski, 1997	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
CZCS SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	1978- 1986	1	ca 1 day	
<u>Ancillary data:</u> requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)									
<u>Algorithm description:</u> This algorithm applies to such coastal waters that qualify as Case I waters . In the approach developed in the Vertical Generalised Production Model, VGPM, the core equation describing the relationship between surface chlorophyll and daily depth-integrated primary production (PP_{eu} in $\text{mgC}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{d}^{-1}$) is expressed as: $PP_{eu} = 0.66125 P_{opt}^B \frac{I}{I + 4.1} C_{sat} \times Z_{eu} \times D_{irr}$ where C_{sat} is the satellite surface chlorophyll concentration (e.g., monthly average images). P_{opt}^B is the optimal rate of daily carbon fixation within the water column that is modelled according to various temperature-dependent relationships. We may notice that P_{opt}^B may conveniently be estimated from remote sensing measurements of sea surface temperature (SST). Nevertheless P_{opt}^B is the source of the largest error in VGPM estimates. Less than half of the observed variability in P_{opt}^B is explained by the temperature-dependent model. Z_{eu} is the euphotic depth; I (or $E_d(PAR,0+)dt$) is the photosynthetically available radiant energy (within the spectral range 400 - 700 nm) incident at the sea level per unit area and for a given lap of time (e.g., one day); D_{irr} is the daily photoperiod.									

Parameter: Concentration of suspended matter C_{sm} ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$)						Form: 21			
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of values:		Maximum error outer-limits:		References	
Reflectance ratio		SPOT - SM		$> 1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$		relative: 30 - 50%		Lathrop & Lillesand, 1989	
Sensor name	Sensor type		Spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
	SPOT HRV	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared				microwave
Ancillary data:									
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>This algorithm applies to such waters, which qualify as Case II and inland waters (Green Bay, Michigan Lake).</p> <p>Inputs are reflectances. Radiances are corrected from atmospheric effects, using the dark pixel technique. Reflectances are computed by dividing these radiances by the extraterrestrial irradiance for the day of concern and the corresponding solar zenith angle, and multiplying by π.</p> $\log [C_{sm}] = -3.27 + 4.74 [\text{Rrs}(\text{XS2}) / \text{Rrs}(\text{XS1})] + 68.1 \text{ Rrs}(\text{XS3})$ <p>Spectral band: XS1: 500 - 590 nm XS2: 610 - 680 nm XS3: 790 - 890 nm</p> <p>This algorithm is empirical. It should be adapted to apply to other situations. This is stated by the authors as well as others (e.g. Curran, Novo, 1988).</p>									

Parameter: Concentration of suspended matter C_{sm} (mg.l^{-1})						Form: 22		
Algorithm type: Reflectance ratio		Algorithm name: TM - SM		Range of values: > 1 mg/l		Maximum error outer-limits: relative: 30 - 50%	References Lathrop <i>et al.</i> , 1991	
Sensor name	Sensor type		Spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
Landsat TM	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1981 onwards	0.03	ca 18 days
Ancillary data:								
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>The following algorithms are applicable to Case I & II ocean waters, as well as to lake water. Inputs are reflectances. Radiances are corrected from atmospheric effects, using the dark pixel technique. Reflectances are computed by dividing these radiances by the extraterrestrial irradiance for the day of concern and the corresponding solar zenith angle, and multiplying by π.</p> <p>$C_{sm} = 0.34 e^{[1.96 \text{ Rrs(TM3)} / \text{Rrs(TM1)}]}$ (validated for lake Michigan and Green Bay.)</p> <p>Spectral band: TM1: 450 - 520 nm TM3: 630 - 690 nm</p> <p>$C_{sm} = a [\text{Rrs(TM3)} / \text{Rrs(TM1)}]^b$</p> <p>with a = 113 b = 2.74 Green Bay, and Michigan Lake a = 21.6 b = 3.61 Yellowstone Lakes</p> <p>These algorithms are empirical. They should be adapted to apply to other situations. This is stated by the authors as well as others (e.g. Curran, Novo, 1988). The above equations illustrate that sediment grain sizes have an influence on the assessment of the water reflectance from space.</p>								

Parameter: Total suspended matter C_{sm} ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$)						Form: 23			
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of values:		Relative error:		References	
Logarithm		Improved unified model		60 - 100 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$		better than 10 %		Xia, 1993	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
	Landsat TM - MSS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared				
						from 1985 onwards	0.03 – 0.08	ca 18 day	
Ancillary data:									
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>This algorithm provides the generic form of the relationship between the radiances and C_{sm}.</p> <p>$TM3' = TM3 - La_3$, where $TM3$ is the radiance in band 3, and La_3 is the atmospheric path radiance $TM5' = TM5 - La_5$, where $TM5$ is the radiance in band 5, and La_5 is the atmospheric path radiance</p> $TM3' / TM5' = A + B/(G + C_{sm}) + F e^{-D C_{sm}} / (G + C_{sm})$ <p>Spectral band: $TM3$: 630 - 690 nm $TM5$: 1550 - 1750 nm</p> <p>Application to the Pearl River in South China leads to the following values for the coefficients A, B, C, D and G: $A = 500562.875$; $B = 446099.4375$; $C = 430.0950$; $D = 0.001$; $G = 130$.</p> <p>A single band form of the algorithm has been proposed:</p> $TM3 = A + B/(C_{sm}/(G + C_{sm})) + F(C_{sm}/(G + C_{sm}))e^{-D C_{sm}}$ <p>This algorithm offers better results than previously published algorithms, such as linear model, logarithm model, Gordon model (Gordon, Brown, 1973), and negative index model (Li Jing, 1986).</p> <p>This algorithm may also apply to Landsat MSS data, using bands MSS5 and MSS7 SPOT XS data, using bands XS2 and XS3 NOAA AVHRR data, using bands AVHRR1 and AVHRR2 and other sensors offering a band around 650 nm and another in which the signal mostly originates from the atmosphere The higher the wavelength of the second band in the near infrared, the better the results.</p>									

Parameter: Concentration of suspended matter C_{sm} (mg/l)					Form: 24				
Algorithm type: normalised band sum		Algorithm name: MSS - SM		Range of C_{sm} (mg/l) values: > 3 mg/l		Maximum error outer-limits: relative: 30 - 50%		References Stumpf, 1988	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
Landsat MSS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1972 onwards	0.08	ca 18 days	
Ancillary data:									
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>This algorithm is applicable to Case II waters.</p> <p>Inputs are reflectances.</p> $C_{SM} = 10^{[R_{rs}(\text{Landsat}) / 11.7]} + 1.2$ <p>The coefficients [117, 1.2] have been obtained for the Chesapeake Bay during floods.</p> <p>The water leaving reflectance $R_{rs}(\text{Landsat})$ is computed from the summation of the radiances of bands MSS 4, 5 and 6 (from 500 to 800 nm) divided by the summation of the incident (or downwelling) irradiance at the air/water interface E_d for each band.</p> <p>Summing up several bands permits to overcome the fairly low sensitivity of the sensor, hence, leading to greater precision and details.</p>									

Parameter: Concentration of suspended matter C_{sm} ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$)						Form: 25		
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of values:		Accuracy	References	
Single band		AVHRR - SM		0.1 - 25		not specified	Vos & Schuttelaar, 1997	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
	AVHRR	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared			
Ancillary data:								
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>This algorithm is applicable to Case II waters. Input is reflectance of NOAA-channel 1.</p> $R_{rs} = R_{back} + 0.178 \left[\frac{C_{sm}}{a'_w / b_b^* + C_{sm}} \right]$ <p>R_{rs} is the remote sensing reflectance; R_{back} is the contribution of water surface and atmosphere to R_{rs}; C is the average concentration (mg/l) of sediment particles; a'_w is the constant absorption coefficient of sea water (m^{-1}), possible including a correction for algae or silt (at high silt concentration); b_b^* is the average specific backscattering coefficient ($\text{m}^{-1}\cdot\text{l}/\text{mg}$) of sediment particles.</p> <p>The model satisfies a saturation law for higher levels of C. For not too large concentrations of scattering material, it may be assumed that $(a'_w / b_b^*) \gg C$ and this leads to a linear relation:</p> $R_{rs} = R_{back} + a' C_{sm}$ <p>An application of log-linear form of the above model in Mobile Bay Alabama (Stumpf, 1991) gave:</p> $\log [C_{sm}] = [R_{rs}(\text{AVHRR1}) - 0.0030] / 0.0275$ <p>The algorithm applies to the water leaving (remote sensing) reflectance R_{rs}, computed from: $R_{rs} = L_w / E_d$, where L_w is the water leaving radiance, and E_d is the incident (or downwelling) irradiance at the air/water interface. R_{rs} may be determined using the technique described by Stumpf and Pennock (1989).</p>								

Parameter: Seston concentration C_{seston} ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$)						Form: 26			
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: CZCS seston algorithms		Range of C_{seston} values: 0.02 -20		Accuracy: not specified, presumably $\pm 40\%$		References Gordon & Morel, 1983 Sturm, 1982	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
CZCS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	1978- 1986	1	ca 1 day	
<u>Ancillary data</u> : requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)									
<u>Algorithm description</u> : These algorithms are appropriate for such coastal waters, which qualify as Case I waters in which the suspended matter originates from photosynthetic and biological activity. The regressions presented hereafter have been computed using extended worldwide <i>in situ</i> data sets. The band 443 nm should be avoided in case of high turbidity or high chlorophyll concentration (i.e., $C > 1.5 \mu\text{g/l}$). <u>General form</u> : $C_{seston} = A(R_{ij})^B, \quad (1)$ A and B are regression coefficients. Upwelling radiance ratio (Clark, 1981): $R_{ij} = L_u(\lambda_i) / L_u(\lambda_j)$, $L_u(\lambda)$ is the radiance coming up from beneath the water surface. The following combinations of the CZCS spectral channels are employed for (1): 443/550: $A = 0.24$ $B = - 0.98$; $r^2 = 0.86$ 520/550: $A = 0.45$ $B = - 3.30$; $r^2 = 0.86$ 520/670: $A = 5.30$ $B = - 1.04$; $r^2 = 0.85$ The Clark & Baker algorithm (unpublished) can be used after application of atmospheric correction to the values of the radiance signal captured by CZCS. Water-leaving radiance ratio (Clark <i>et al.</i> , 1981) $R_{ij} = L_w(\lambda_i) / L_w(\lambda_j)$, $L_w(\lambda)$ is the water-leaving radiance above the surface. 443/550: $A = 0.4$ $B = - 0.88$; 520/550: $A = 0.76$ $B = - 4.38$; 443/520: $A = 0.33$ $B = - 1.09$; The algorithm applies to the water leaving radiance. Remote sensing reflectance ratio (Sturm, 1982) Range of value: 0.1 - 30 $R_{ij} = R_{rs}(\lambda_i) / R_{rs}(\lambda_j)$, $R_{rs}(\lambda)$ is the remote sensing reflectance. 443/550: $A = 2.61$ $B = -1.30$; 520/550: $A = 4.48$ $B = -2.53$;									

Parameter: bulk water absorption coefficient a (m^{-1})						Form: 27		
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of a values:		Accuracy	References	
Semi-analytical		Lee algorithm		not specified		not specified	Lee <i>et al.</i> , 1996	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
	SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared			

Ancillary data: requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)

Algorithm description:

Strictly speaking, the algorithm is applicable to such coastal waters that can qualify as **Case I waters**. To retrieve the bulk water absorption coefficient, a relationship between the ratio $E_u(z = +0, \lambda) / E_d(z = +0, \lambda)$, and inherent water properties was used:

$$R_{rs}(\lambda) \approx \frac{0.17}{a_w(\lambda) + a_y(\lambda) + a_{chl}(\lambda)} \cdot \left[\frac{b_{b_w}(\lambda)}{3.4} + X \left(\frac{400}{\lambda} \right)^Y \right], \quad (1)$$

where X , Y are coefficients, b_{b_w} is the water backscattering coefficient.

The application of this algorithm implies the availability of water *per se* absorption and backscattering coefficients (Pope and Fry, 1997; Morel, 1974). The use of the exponential dependence of a_y on λ ($a_y(\lambda) = a_y(\lambda_0) \exp(-0.0014(\lambda - \lambda_0))$, where λ_0 is the reference wavelength (e.g., 380 nm). The values of $a_y(\lambda_0)$, $a_{ph}(\lambda)$ and the coefficients X , Y are to be determined from Eq. 1 for measured values of R_{rs} at the SeaWiFS wavelengths. Summation of $a_w(\lambda) + a_y(\lambda) + a_{chl}(\lambda)$ would result in the bulk water absorption coefficient.

This algorithm is experimental and no extensive validation measurements have been conducted. The algorithm can be used after application of atmospheric correction to the values of the radiance signal captured by SeaWiFS. It also implies the use of remote sensing reflectances $R_{rs} = L_w / E_d$, where L_w is the water leaving radiance, and E_d is the incident irradiance at the air/water interface.

Parameter: Dissolved and detrital materials absorption coefficient $a_{dm}(m^{-1})$ Backscattering coefficient due to suspended matter $b_{bp}(m^{-1})$						Form: 28			
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of a_{dm} values:		Accuracy		References	
Semi-analytical		Garver/Siegel		0.01 - 0.015		not specified		Garver & Siegel, 1997	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1997 onwards	1.1	ca 1 day	
<u>Ancillary data:</u> requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)									
<u>Algorithm description:</u>									
<p>The Garver/Siegel model was initially developed for strictly oligotrophic oceanic waters (Case I waters) with C_{chl} lower than $0.4\mu g/l$. Further it was tested against oceanic meso-and eutrophic waters (also case I waters) for which the model showed its workability, but the low range C_{chl} waters are still the realm where it proves more efficient.</p> <p>This is a semi-analytic algorithm based on the quadratic form of the $b_b / a + b_b$ to R_{rs}:</p> $R_{rs} = \zeta \frac{L_u(\lambda)}{E_d(\lambda)} = \zeta^2 \prod_{i=1}^i \left[\frac{b_b(\lambda)}{b_b(\lambda) + a(\lambda)} \right]^i, \text{ where } \zeta = 0.48, l_1 = 0.0949 \text{sr}^{-1}, l_2 = 0.0794 \text{sr}^{-1};$ $b_b(\lambda) = b_{bw}(\lambda) + b_{bp}(\lambda),$ <p>b_{bw} is the backscatter due to pure seawater, $b_{bp}(\lambda)$ is the backscatter due to suspended particular matter,</p> $a(\lambda) = a_w(\lambda) + a_{ph}(\lambda) + a_{dm}(\lambda),$ <p>$a_w(\lambda)$ is the absorption due to seawater, $a_{ph}(\lambda)$ is the absorption due to phytoplankton, and $a_{dm}(\lambda)$ is the absorption due to the combined effects of coloured dissolved and detrital materials (CDM).</p> <p>The Garver/Siegel model uses pre-defined shapes for specific absorption $a(\lambda)$ and backscattering $b_b(\lambda)$ coefficients.</p> <p>$a_w(\lambda)$ and b_{bw} are suggested to be taken respectively from Pope and Fry (1997) and Morel (1974),</p> $a_{dm}(\lambda) = a_{dm}(\lambda_0 = 440nm) \exp[S(\lambda - \lambda_0)], S = -0.02 \text{ nm}^{-1}, b_{bp}(\lambda) = b_{bp}(\lambda_0) b_{bp}^*(\lambda), b_{ph}^*(\lambda) \text{ being modelled as } (\lambda / \lambda_0)^{-1}, a_{ph}(\lambda) = C_{chl} a_{ph}^*(\lambda), a_{ph}^*(\lambda) \text{ is the specific absorption coefficient to be taken from Bricaud } et al., 1995.$ <p>The model inversion (through a non-linear statistical method, Bates and Watts, 1988) results in determination of $b_{bp}(\lambda_0), C_{chl}, a_{dm}(\lambda_0)$.</p> <p>The Garver/Siegel algorithm application in the Sargasso Sea indicates that even in case I waters the coloured dissolved and suspended detrital materials can contribute in winter-spring season up to 35 %, and in summer time up to 10% of the bulk water absorption at $\lambda = 441 \text{ nm}$. Bacteria can contribute up to 10% to the total light scattering. Thus such inversion-type algorithms, which are capable of simultaneously retrieving not only one absorber and scatterer (<i>phytoplankton</i>), but all the major co-existing absorbers (<i>phytoplankton</i>, coloured dissolved organic and detritus), and scatters (<i>phytoplankton</i>, <i>bacterioplankton</i>) are likely to improve the accuracy of water quality parameters. The Garver/Siegel algorithm is experimental, it has not gone through a thorough ground truth validation, and consequently lacks substantiated estimations of retrieval accuracy.</p>									

Parameter: bulk water scattering to absorption ratio b_b/a						Form: 29		
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of b_b/a values:		Accuracy	References	
Semi-analytical		Polynomial		not specified		not specified	Jerome <i>et al.</i> , 1996	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
	SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared			
<p><u>Ancillary data</u>: requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)</p>								
<p><u>Algorithm description</u>:</p> <p>This algorithm is based on the relationship established between the remote sensing reflectance and bulk water coefficients of backscattering and absorption and applicable to a large variety of waters ranging from Case I to Case II waters:</p> $(b_b / a) = 0.0027 + 5.53R_{rs} - 10.82(R_{rs})^2 + 269.4(R_{rs})^3 \quad (r = 0.99).$ <p>Determined for the SeaWiFS wavelengths, the remote sensing reflectance is then used for assessing the ratio backscattering to absorption coefficients of the water.</p> <p>This algorithm is experimental and no extensive validation measurements have been conducted. The algorithm can be used after application of atmospheric correction to the values of the radiance signal captured by SeaWiFS. It also implies the use of remote sensing reflectances $R_{rs} = L_w / E_d$, where L_w is the water leaving radiance, and E_d is the incident irradiance at the air/water interface. This, in turn, necessitates elimination of the water surface reflection-driven component L_{ws} from L_w.</p>								

Parameter: Diffuse attenuation K_d (m^{-1})						Form: 30			
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: Dekker "K(PAR)"- algorithms for lakes		Range of pigments concentration values: 0.6 - 4.6		Maximum error outer-limits: not specified		References Dekker, 1993	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
CASI, CAESAR	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave		0.02	airborne	
<u>Ancillary data:</u> requirement for atmospheric correction									
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>The Dekker "K" algorithms are appropriate for lakes and river waters. This reflectance ratio type algorithm has been developed to determine the vertical attenuation coefficient for downwelling irradiance within the <i>penetration depth</i>:</p> $K_d(PAR) = A + B(R_{ij}), \quad (1)$ <p>where $R_{ij} = R(\lambda_i) / R(\lambda_j)$, $R(\lambda)$ is the volume reflectance just below the water surface</p> <p>For CAESAR and CASI sensors: $\lambda_i = 705$ nm; $\lambda_j = 676$ nm;</p> <p>$A = -0.6256$; $B = 1.9187$ $r^2 = 0.89$ average of several types of lake;</p> <p>$A = 0.0492$; $B = 1.5950$ $r^2 = 0.89$ shallow lakes;</p> <p>$A = -0.4045$; $B = 1.3600$ $r^2 = 0.99$ deep lakes;</p> <p>The Dekker "K" algorithm can be used after application of atmospheric correction to the values of the radiance signal captured by hyperspectral sensors. Estimates of the atmosphere column content above the scene is then required. Radiative transfer models as 6S and Modtran can be used for that purpose. Then estimates of the horizontal visibility or of the aerosol optical depth must be provided.</p>									

Parameter: Diffuse attenuation K_d (m^{-1})						Form: 31		
Algorithm type: Linear regression		Algorithm name: MSS- K_d		Range of K_d values: all		Accuracy not specified	References Lyzenga, 1981	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
Landsat MSS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1972 onwards	0.08	ca 18 day
Ancillary data:								
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>This algorithm does not provide the diffuse attenuation coefficient K_d but only the ratio of this coefficient for two different wavelengths. It is computed from the radiances measured by the sensor, and is applicable to a large variety of waters ranging from Case I to Case II waters:</p> <p>Let $X_i = \log(L_i - L_{si})$, where L_i is the measured radiance in band i and L_{si} the measured radiance over the deep-water.</p> <p>Over areas of constant bottom reflectances, the ratio of diffuse attenuation coefficients is equal to</p> $K_{di} / K_{dj} = a + \sqrt{a^2 + 1}$ <p>where $a = (\sigma_{ii} - \sigma_{jj}) / 2 \sigma_{ij}$, where σ_{ii} is the variance of the X_i measurements, σ_{jj} is the variance of the X_j measurements and σ_{ij} is the covariance of X_i and X_j.</p> <p>This algorithm has been applied to Landsat MSS-4 (500 - 600 nm) and MSS-5 (600 - 700 nm).</p>								

Parameter: Diffuse attenuation K_d (m^{-1})						Form: 32																																												
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: CZCS “K”- algorithms		Range of K_d values: 0.2 - 6.0		Maximum error outer-limits: not specified	References Austin, Petzold, 1981 Sturm, 1982																																											
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)																																										
CZCS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	1978- 1986	1	ca 1 day																																										
<u>Ancillary data:</u> requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)																																																		
<u>Algorithm description:</u>																																																		
<p>The Austin/Petzold (1981) “K” algorithm is appropriate for such coastal waters, which qualify as Case I waters in which the light attenuation is solely controlled by phytoplankton chlorophyllous pigments optical impact. This is a radiance ratio type algorithm, developed to determine the vertical attenuation coefficient for downwelling irradiance within the <i>penetration depth</i>:</p> $K_d(\lambda) - K_{dw}(\lambda) = A(R_{ij})^B, \quad (1)$ <p>$K_{dw}(\lambda)$ is the pure sea water vertical attenuation coefficient at a wavelength λ, A and B are the regression coefficients.</p> <p>Upwelling radiance ratio (Clark, 1981): Austin & Petzold, 1981 proposed the following algorithm, which has been implemented by NASA as the standard “K “ algorithm for CZCS. $R_{ij} = L_u(\lambda_i) / L_u(\lambda_j)$, $L_u(\lambda)$ is the radiance coming up from beneath the water surface The following combinations of the CZCS spectral channels are employed for Eq. (1):</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>$K_d(\lambda)$</th> <th>λ_i</th> <th>λ_j</th> <th>A</th> <th>B</th> <th>r^2</th> <th>$K_{dw}(\lambda)$</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>$K_d(490)$</td> <td>443</td> <td>550</td> <td>0.088</td> <td>-1.491</td> <td>0.90</td> <td>0.022</td> </tr> <tr> <td>$K_d(520)$</td> <td>443</td> <td>550</td> <td>0.066</td> <td>-1.398</td> <td>0.99</td> <td>0.044</td> </tr> </tbody> </table> <p>For $K(490)$ varying from 0.03 to 0.4 m^{-1} and $K(520)$ from 0.05 to 0.4 m^{-1}, the values of $K(490)$ and $K(520)$ can be equally retrieved from remotely measured $C_{chl+phaeo}$ in Case I waters:</p> $K(490) - 0.0217 = 0.069C_{chl+phaeo}^{0.702} \quad (r^2 = 0.95) \quad K(520) - 0.0489 = 0.050C_{chl+phaeo}^{0.681} \quad (r^2 = 0.94)$ <p>The Austin/Petzold “K” algorithm can be used after application of atmospheric correction to the values of the radiance signal captured by CZCS. It also necessitates elimination of the water surface reflection-driven component L_{ws} from the water surface radiance L_w.</p> <p>Remote sensing reflectance ratio Sturm, 1982 proposed the following algorithms that depends upon the chlorophyll concentration in the water column. $R_{ij} = R_{rs}(\lambda_i) / R_{rs}(\lambda_j)$, $R_{rs}(\lambda)$ is the remote sensing reflectance.</p> <table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>$K_d(\lambda)$</th> <th>λ_i</th> <th>λ_j</th> <th>A</th> <th>B</th> <th>r^2</th> <th>$K_{dw}(\lambda)$</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>$K_d(550)$ ($C_{chl} < 3 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)</td> <td>443</td> <td>550</td> <td>0.053</td> <td>-1.740</td> <td>0.90</td> <td>0.063</td> </tr> <tr> <td>$K_d(550)$ ($C_{chl} > 3 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)</td> <td>520</td> <td>550</td> <td>0.085</td> <td>-4.683</td> <td>0.99</td> <td>0.063</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>									$K_d(\lambda)$	λ_i	λ_j	A	B	r^2	$K_{dw}(\lambda)$	$K_d(490)$	443	550	0.088	-1.491	0.90	0.022	$K_d(520)$	443	550	0.066	-1.398	0.99	0.044	$K_d(\lambda)$	λ_i	λ_j	A	B	r^2	$K_{dw}(\lambda)$	$K_d(550)$ ($C_{chl} < 3 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	443	550	0.053	-1.740	0.90	0.063	$K_d(550)$ ($C_{chl} > 3 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)	520	550	0.085	-4.683	0.99	0.063
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Parameter: Diffuse attenuation $K(490) (m^{-1})$ and photic depth $Z_{phd} (m)$						Form: 33		
Algorithm type: Band ratio	Algorithm name: SeaWiFS "K"- algorithm		Range of K_d values: 0.2 - 6.4		Maximum error outer-limits: 0.1 %	References Gordon & Morel, 1983		
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1997- onwards	1.1	ca 1 day
<u>Ancillary data:</u> requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)								
<u>Algorithm description:</u> This algorithm is the Austin/Petzold "K" algorithm tuned for SeaWiFS data, and is available in SeaDAS, the NASA SeaWiFS data processing freeware. It is appropriate for such coastal waters, which qualify as Case I waters in which the light attenuation is solely controlled by phytoplankton chlorophyllous pigments optical impact. This is a radiance ratio type algorithm, developed to determine the vertical attenuation coefficient for downwelling irradiance within the <i>penetration depth</i> : $K_d(\lambda) - K_{dw}(\lambda) = A(R_{ij})^B, \quad (1)$ where $R_{ij} = L_u(\lambda_i) / L_u(\lambda_j)$, $L_u(\lambda)$ is the radiance coming up from beneath the water surface, $K_{dw}(\lambda)$ is the pure sea water vertical attenuation coefficient at a wavelength λ .								
$K_d(\lambda)$	λ_i	λ_j	A	B	r^2	$K_{dw}(\lambda)$		
$K_d(490)$	443	550	0.1	-1.2996	0.90	0.022		
The photic depth z_{phd} is the depth at which the downwelling irradiance equals 1% of the incident irradiance: $E_d(z_{phd}, \lambda) = E_d(0, \lambda)0.01$. Assuming that the attenuation coefficient for downwelling irradiance is <i>depth invariant</i> , the photic depth then may be determined from the following equation: $0.001 = \exp(-K(\lambda) \cdot z_{phd}).$ Two values of K should be used ($K(490)$ and $K(520)$, see CZCS "K" algorithms) for calculating z_{phd} and the averaged value can be taken as the looked for photic depth.								

Parameter: Turbidity / Secchi depth (Z_{sd}) (m)						Form: 34		
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: "SD" algorithm		Range of Secchi depth values: 0.25 - 10.0		Accuracy not specified	References Dekker, 1993	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
CASI	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave		0.02	airborne
CAESAR								
<u>Ancillary data:</u> requirement for atmospheric correction								
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>The "SD" algorithm is based on direct statistical relationship between reflectance ratios and the Secchi depth, and is appropriate for lakes and river waters.</p> <p>The relationships are appropriate for a wide range of lakes and river waters.</p> $\log(SD) = A + B \cdot \log(R_{ij}), \quad (1)$ <p>where $R_{ij} = R(\lambda_i) / R(\lambda_j)$, $R(\lambda)$ is the volume reflectance just below the water surface</p> <p><u>For</u> CAESAR and CASI sensors: $\lambda_i = 705$ nm; $\lambda_j = 676$ nm;</p> <p>$A = 5.05$; $B = 1.615$ $r^2 = 0.67$ average of several types of lake; $A = 4.89$; $B = 1.464$ $r^2 = 0.96$ shallow lakes; $A = 5.51$; $B = 2.038$ $r^2 = 0.96$ deep lakes;</p> <p>The "SD" algorithm can be used after application of atmospheric correction to the values of the radiance signal captured by hyperspectral sensors. Estimates of the atmosphere column content above the scene is then required. Radiative transfer models as 6S and Modtran can be used for that purpose. Then estimates of the horizontal visibility or of the aerosol optical depth must be provided.</p>								

Parameter: Turbidity / light extinction (m^{-1})						Form: 35		
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of values:		Accuracy	References	
Band ratio		Turbidity index		0.55 - 1.15		not specified	Verdin, 1982, 1985	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
TM, MSS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	From 1972 onwards	0.03 - 0.08	ca. 25 days
Ancillary data:								
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>The algorithm presented here is a simple band-ratio turbidity index that has been used in an operational context for inland water monitoring.</p> <p>MSS4 / (MSS4 + MSS5 + MSS6)</p> <p>TM2 / (TM2 + TM3 + TM4)</p> <p>MSS4: 500 - 600 nm TM2: 520 - 600 nm MSS5: 600 - 700 nm TM3: 630 - 690 nm MSS6: 700 - 800 nm TM4: 760 - 900 nm</p>								

Parameter: water colour - chromaticity co-ordinates X,Y (relative units)						Form: 36			
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of X&Y values:		Accuracy		References	
semi-analytical		CIE-algorithm		0 - 1		not specified		Pozdnyakov <i>et al.</i> , 1998	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
	SeaWiFS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared				microwave
<u>Ancillary data:</u> requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)									
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>The algorithm is applicable both to Case I & II waters. Its realisation requires values of water leaving radiance L_w at SeaWiFS wavelengths. Calculating tri-stimulus values x, y, z through tabulated CIE colour mixtures for equal energy spectra x',y',z' (Anonymous, 1957):</p> $x = \int x'(\lambda)L_u + 0, \lambda)d\lambda,$ $y = \int y'(\lambda)L_u + 0, \lambda)d\lambda,$ $z = \int z'(\lambda)L_u + 0, \lambda)d\lambda,$ <p>permits to ultimately calculate the chromaticity co-ordinates X,Y,Z:</p> $X = \frac{x}{x + y + z},$ $Y = \frac{y}{x + y + z},$ $Z = \frac{z}{x + y + z}.$ <p>The chromaticity co-ordinates thus derived determine the radiometric colour of water. Since $X+Y+Z=1$, the radiometric colour could be exhaustively described by only two colour co-ordinates (XY or YZ or XZ), in the colour triangle.</p> <p>This algorithm can equally be used with data from CZCS and OCTS. Irrespective of the satellite sensor, it implies application of atmospheric correction to the values of the radiance signal captured by the space. This, in turn, necessitates elimination of the water surface reflection-driven component L_{ws} from L_w.</p>									

Parameter: Water Surface Temperature, WST						Form: 37		
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of values:		Max. error outer-limits:		References
Split-Window		MCSST (multi-channel WST).		All values of WST		1K globally 0.5K regionally		McClain, 1985
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
	AVHRR	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared			
<p><u>Ancillary data:</u> brightness temperature calibration; cloud screening. Accurate brightness temperature is calculated, using the 2-point linear radiance calibration available by the on-board blackbody and the space-view signals as described in Lauritson, 1979.</p>								
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>The basic equation as given by McClain (1985) is:</p> $WST = a*T4 + b_1*(T4 - T5) + c + b_2*(T4 - T5)*(sec(\theta) - 1) + c$ <p>$a=1.02015$, $b_1=2.32$, $b_2=0.489$, $c=-278.52$, θ = scan angle, temperature in degree Celsius.</p> <p>By linear combination of brightness temperature $T4$ of channel 4 (10-11μm) and $T5$ of channel 5 (11 - 12μm) on AVHRR, the effect of varying atmospheric emission and transmission is largely corrected. Since buoys have been used to calibrate the algorithm, also effects of water emission coefficient and skin-to-bulk water temperature gradient are eliminated.</p> <p>This is the Multi-channel WST, or MCSST. The given coefficients are used globally for routine processing at NESDIS for daytime passes of NOAA-11. Slightly different values are used for night-time passes, and for instruments on other NOAA satellites. Note that some AVHRR instruments do not have split channel.</p> <p>Many authors use a simplified version, which has been demonstrated as theoretically correct as early as 1980:</p> $WST = d T4 + e T5 + f$ <p>where d, e and f are coefficients adjusted for local conditions (e.g., the Mediterranean Sea, the Arctic seas, ...). Accuracy is better than with the basic MCSST.</p>								

Parameter: Water Surface Temperature, WST						Form: 38			
Algorithm type: Dual-View (and Split-Window).		Algorithm name: ATSR - WST		Range of values: All values of WST		Max. error outer-limits: 0.5K globally <0.5K regionally		References Zavody, 1994	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave				
ATSR						from 1991 onwards	1 - 2	ca 6 day	
<u>Ancillary data:</u> brightness temperature calibration; geolocation of views; cloud screening									
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>The basic equation as given by Zavody,1994 is:</p> $WST = c0 + c1 * T11n + c2 * T12n + c3 * T11f + c4 * T12f$ <p>By linear combination of brightness temperature T11n (nadir-view) and T11f (forward-view) of channel 10-12µm, and similarly of T12n and T12f of channel 11 -13µm on ATSR, the effect of varying atmospheric emission and transmission is largely corrected. The coefficients are derived from an atmospheric model, and are given in (Zavody, 1995).</p> <p>A variation of the algorithm is also to include T3.7n and T3.7f of channel 3.2 -4.1µm (night only) in the linear algorithm above.</p> <p>Before use of the dual-view algorithm, accurate brightness temperatures are calculated, using a 2-point linear radiance calibration available by the two on-board blackbodies as described in Zavody 1994, including a slight non-linearity correction. The geolocation of the nadir and the forward view pixels is a complex procedure due to the conical scan geometry.</p> <p>The procedure for the processing of the ATSR is very sophisticated. End-users are recommended to purchase final products instead of trying to apply such an algorithm onto original images.</p>									

Parameter: Water Surface Temperature, WST						Form: 39		
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of values:		Max. error outer-limits:	References	
Single band		Single band-WST		All values of WST		0.5 K	Markham & Barker 1986	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
Landsat TM6 AVHRR	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1984 onwards	0.12 1	ca 6 day 0.25 day
<u>Ancillary data:</u> atmospheric correction (Markham 1986); cloud screening								
<u>Algorithm description:</u>								
<p>Sensors may not permit to correct brightness temperatures for atmospheric effects and to retrieve sea surface temperature with a satisfactory accuracy. This is the case of Landsat TM6. If L is the radiance (in $\text{mW cm}^{-2} \text{sr}^{-1} \mu\text{m}^{-1}$) observed by the sensor, the brightness temperature of the sea can be derived from the Planck radiation equation (Xiangmin, 1997):</p> $T = K_2 / \log((K_1/L) + 1)$ <p>where $K_1 = 60.776 \text{ mW cm}^{-2} \text{sr}^{-1} \mu\text{m}^{-1}$, and $K_2 = 1260.56 \text{ K}$. Slightly different values for K_1 and K_2 is given by Goetz 1995.</p> <p>The error in assimilating the brightness temperature to the sea surface temperature depends strongly on the atmospheric conditions and on the ancillary data.</p> <p>Nevertheless, images of brightness temperatures are very useful to map the distribution of the sea surface temperature at local scales; the relative accuracy of the magnitude of the transitions observed in an image is approx. 10 % (Wald, 1980). For Landsat TM6, the sensitivity in mapping relative variation of sea surface temperature is approx. 0.5 K.</p> <p>For AVHRR, this sensitivity is much higher: approx. 0.09 K (Wald, 1989). This property explains why, when a high priority is given to gradients at local scale, one does not correct for atmospheric effects by using e.g., the MCSST algorithm. Such algorithms introduce noise in the resulting image, which partially masks the gradients. Noise standard deviation amounts to approx. 0.5-0.8 K, a value much larger than the sensitivity of the sensor.</p> <p>In the case of AVHRR, the procedure to convert L into brightness temperature is fully described in Lauritson (1979) and subsequent technical documents issued by the NOAA.</p>								

Parameter: Water depth (bathymetry) (<i>m</i>)						Form: 40			
Algorithm type: semi-empirical		Algorithm name: Bierwirth method		Range of values: Range for optical sensors, typical : 0-20m		Max. error outer-limits: Depending upon turbidity and sampling. Typically : 2m for clear waters		References Lyzenga, 1981 Bierwirth <i>et al.</i> , 1993	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
Landsat TM	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	since 1985 onwards	0.03	ca. 18 days	
Ancillary data:									
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>Step 1: Black pixel correction, starting with raw image of pixel counts C, compute $C_1 = C - C_{\min}$. C_{\min} is the mean of minimum pixel count, computed over a sample of a clear water column.</p> <p>Step 2: Estimate reflectances: $C_2 = C_1 G/I$. Where G is the sensor gain, and I is the total solar irradiance.</p> <p>Step 3: Estimate water depth z, by :</p> $z = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \ln(R_i)}{-2k_i N} - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \ln(R_{bi})}{-2k_i N}$ <p>where R_i is estimated with C_2, i is the number of the spectral band, N the total number of spectral bands, R_{bi} the bottom reflectance, k the effective attenuation coefficient for the water body. If k is expressed in m^{-1}, z is expressed in m.</p> <p>Empirically, the second term in the previous equation is set to zero, while a second approach consists in its estimation correlating $\ln(R)$ with z using in situ measurements.</p> <p>If the depth is known, then the algorithm can be reversed to retrieve the bottom reflectance, and to map the sea-floor.</p>									

Parameter: Bathymetry - bottom topography (<i>m</i>)						Form: 41		
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of values:		Max. error outer-limits:	References	
Spectral analysis		Hydrodynamic method		50 - 250m		20m	Forget 1987, 1995	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
	SAR	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared			
Ancillary data:								
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>The algorithm is based on the analysis of the refraction of monochromatic swells by the sea bottom over continental shelves. The swell wavenumber and direction are computed, and the refraction phenomenon is modelled, starting in offshore conditions, and following the swell propagation lines toward the coast. The variations in wavelength are used to estimate the water depth, until a limit depth given by the half wavelength of the swell. The method assumes the linearity of the transfer function for the swell imagery. This may be verified for typical radial swells, or with propagation angles between 10° and 90° with respect to the flight direction. Additional hydrodynamic phenomena that may affect the evolution of the swell, such as coastal drifts of tidal currents can be also taken into account through a data assimilation scheme, given the knowledge of the current field.</p> <p>Starting with the SAR image:</p> <p>Step 1 : divide the field in 256x256 pixels areas Step 2 : compute Fast Fourier Transform for each area Step 3 : detect peak value for each spectrum, and plot each propagation vector Step 4 : starting from the offshore area (infinite depth, stationary wavelength), build a propagation model for the swell, and compute locally the depth with:</p> $\omega = (gK \tanh(KH))^{1/2}$ <p>where ω is the period of the monochromatic swell (in rad./s), g is the gravitation constant, K is the modulus of the wave vector for the swell (in rad./m), H is the water depth (in m).</p>								

Parameter: Bathymetry - bottom topography (<i>m</i>)						Form: 42			
Algorithm type: Correlation method		Algorithm name: Venturi		Range of values: depth :0-50m tidal current u : > 0.5 m/s		Accuracy The method is generally used for updating bathymetric charts, the resulting precision depends upon reference mapping. Typical positioning error is 30m		References Alpers & Hennings 1984	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
SAR	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	since 1978 onwards	0.025	ca. 10 days	
Ancillary data:									
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>Bathymetric features may appear on SAR images, despite the fact that microwaves do not penetrate into water columns. The phenomenology is well described, first by Vesecky and Stewart, and then by Gordon <i>et al.</i> (1984). Complete case studies were achieved over well-documented sites, (<i>e.g.</i> Valenzuela <i>et al.</i>, 1985). In 1984, Alpers and Hennings give the hydrodynamical model for the bottom signature of bathymetric features on SAR images. It is shown how features such as shoals or margins may modify strong current fields, such as tidal currents. When properly oriented variations of the surface current by the <i>venturi</i> effect affects significantly the sea state, resulting especially in breaking wave zones downstream the shoal position. Alpers and Hennings build a complete model for the SAR imagery of the phenomena, the main results are :</p> <p>The phenomenon does affect both imaging processes of hydrodynamic modulation and velocity bunching. The consequence is that one may observe bathymetric features whatever their orientation with respect to the image synthesis, but with possible strong distortions.</p> <p>The most visible signature of shoals is the breaking wave zone, that may appear de-localised downstream the actual position of the target.</p> <p>The authors then achieve a complete modelling of the image modulation. It is then shown that a quantitative analysis of the signal variations may be related to the bathymetry through the relation: $\Gamma/I = f(d'/d^2)$. Where I is the image intensity, d is the water depth, and the symbol ' denotes the differentiation. « f » is an arbitrary functional, depending upon both surface wind conditions, and tidal current. The algorithm may thus be used, not for absolute bathymetry, but relative measurements, such as map updating or shoal detection and/or tracking (Vogelzang <i>et al.</i>, 1992).</p>									

Parameter: Altimetry / regional mesoscale marine geoid(<i>m</i>)							Form: 43	
Algorithm type: Dynamical modelling		Algorithm name: ISSH		Range of values: 1° square grid according to both models and altimeter covering		Max. error outer-limits: Undetermined		References Metzner & Grafarend, 1992
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
Altimeter	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	since 1985 onwards	5 (beam) mapping : depending upon orbital mesh	from 3 to 170 days, depending upon orbit phasing
<u>Ancillary data:</u> regional circulation models, bathymetry, wind speed, SWH								
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>Instantaneous Sea Surface Heights (ISSH) calculation:</p> <p>The method is devoted to the separation between regional geoid and dynamical effects in coastal areas and shallow waters, between 0 and 200 m. Depending upon the reliability of ancillary data, comparisons between ISSH and geoid may enhance purely dynamical effects e.g., “seiches”, trends in sea level changes, or gravitational phenomena linked with water properties, as salt domes or ridges.</p> <p>Starting with global ALT data, ISSH is retrieved using ancillary data including bathymetry, water circulation, SWH and wind.</p> <p>Correction values to the regional geoid are calculated using ISSH.</p> <p>Due to the restriction of the method to both regional and short time scales, the precision is metric. This value may not be compared to the precision of global geoid reached over a full oceanic basin, i.e. between 4 and 15 cm.</p>								

Parameter: Coastline detection and tracing(<i>m</i>)						Form: 44			
Algorithm type: Morphometry		Algorithm name: Directional mask		Range of values: > 5 pixels		Max. error outer-limits: depending upon sea/land contrast		References Lee & Jurkevich 1990	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
SAR	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	since 1978 onwards	0.025	ca. 10 days	
Ancillary data:									
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>Note 1: Coastline detection on SAR images is mainly depending upon two difficulties. The speckle noise, which is a multiplicative noise, results in strong variations of the image intensity in both land and sea. Thus classical thresholding of SAR images may not be used as in optics. The second problem is due to the dependency of the mean image intensity over water areas upon the surface wind conditions. For typical values of wind varying from 0 to 15 m/s, the sea may appear respectively as a smooth target or with a surface roughness comparable to the one of land. In the later condition, the present algorithm, and all algorithms based on intensity analysis do not lead to proper results.</p> <p>Note 2: This family of algorithms may be used for oil slick detection.</p> <p>Starting with the SAR image:</p> <p>I - Preprocessing steps: Step 1; Despeckling the image, using a sigma filter (twice) Step 2: Edge filtering using Sobel operator Step 3: Mean filtering 5x5 (twice) Step 4: Computing image histogram and Thresholding at $\bar{m} + 2\sigma$.</p> <p>II – Edge tracing algorithm: Step 1: Edge detection with Robert's filter or Hough transform Step 2: Iterate on contour tracing using directional masking Step 3: Dilation by 5x5 mean filtering (twice) Step 4: Thresholding Step 5: Contour tracing of inside edge</p>									

Parameter: Shoreline rate of change (<i>m/year</i>)						Form: 45			
Algorithm type:		Algorithm name:		Range of values:		Maximum error outer-limits:		References	
Statistical estimation		Semivariogram method		points estimates on erosion / accretion : 20 m/year		depending upon sampling, from 0.5 to 7 m/year		Dolan <i>et al.</i> 1992	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
SAR, HRV TM	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave		0.01 – 0.03	Few days	
Ancillary data:									
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>The method is devoted to the retrieval of the shoreline rate change as observed on time series of geolocalised remotely sensed images. Due to the possibility of great variability, in both spatial and time domains, the main difficulty is to provide local estimates of rate changes as well as reliable error estimations.</p> <p>Starting with a couple of images, N+1 transects, orthogonal to the shoreline are defined. The position of the shoreline at a given date on transect <i>i</i> is x_i. The first step of the algorithm is to remove trends in order to provide a stationary field for the geostatistical analysis:</p> <p>Step 1 – De-meaning: subtracting the great mean value from each value of the series. Step 2 – De-trending: subtracting the value of a linear trend at a point in a series from the corresponding data value. Step 3 - Differencing: replacing values in the series with the difference between that value and the preceding value.</p> <p>Step 4 - Log transformation of the form : $y' = \frac{ x }{x} \ln(x + 1)$</p> <p>Step 5 - An arc-tangent transformation of the form $y = \text{atan}(y')$</p> <p>The semivariogram of the rate changes is given by : $\gamma(h) = \frac{1}{2N} \sum_{i=1}^{i=N-h} (Y_i - Y_{i+h})^2$</p> <p>Estimating locally the rate of change of the shoreline is achieved using the geostatistical approach, where the local estimate E is given by :</p> $E = \sum_{j=0}^{i=N} w_j \cdot Y_j$ <p>where the weights w_j are computed through : $[w] = [D] \times [C]^{-1}$</p> <p>[w] - Column matrix of weights [D] - column matrix of covariance between all sample locations and location estimates [C] - rectangular matrix of covariance between all sample locations and themselves</p> <p>A covariance is given by: $\text{COV}(h) = C_0 - \gamma(h)$, where C_0 is the asymptotic variance, estimated from the semivariogram $\gamma(h)$.</p>									

Parameter: Oil Slick (detection / tracking)						Form: 46			
Algorithm type: Image Processing		Algorithm name: Threshold Analysis		Range of values: 2.5 - 8 dB		Max. error outer-limits: depending mostly upon wind speed conditions 2.5 minimal threshold may be reached between 2 and 15 m/s surface wind speeds		References Okamoto <i>et al.</i> 1993	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
SAR	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	since 1978 onwards	0.025	ca. 10 days	
Ancillary data:									
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p>An oil slick is generally detectable in a SAR image through the effect of damping of the Bragg scatterers at sea surface (i.e. centimetric waves). It results in a weakening of the radar cross-section, that may range between the radiometric limit (2.5 dB) to a deep damping of the signal (6dB).</p> <p>Simple thresholding techniques are not usable, and generally oil slick detection in SAR images requires the intervention of an operator. Due to the presence of the speckle effect in SAR images, a thresholding operation must be preceded by a noise reduction step. The most commonly used technique is the multi-looking technique.</p>									

III.4 Requirements versus EO achievements

III.4.1 Achievements of EO versus environmental parameters

Table 17 summarises the quantitative achievements of EO techniques regarding the identified geophysical parameters. The values indicated in the table correspond to the best results expected under favourable conditions (satellite fast programming, no weather constraints, no delay in data provision, etc.). The “range of value” arises from the larger interval that it is possible to obtain when grouping all the algorithms related to the geophysical parameter under concern.

“Accuracy” is given either as a percentage of the measured quantity or an absolute accuracy expressed in the unit of the parameter. It also refers to the highest accuracy that can be achieved with present sensors and algorithms.

Spatial resolution is the sensor spatial resolution at nadir. “Frequency of sampling” corresponds to the average revisiting time, which takes into account off-nadir-pointing capability of certain sensors, when appropriate.

“Delay of availability” is the order of magnitude of the average delay between acquisition and delivery to customers.

A comparative analysis has been performed to evaluate where EO-derived products do meet the user requirements that are synthesised by subject of concern in Table 14.

On the one hand, the evaluation is performed in terms of the quality of the retrieved parameters (range of value and accuracy) which is mostly dependent upon the sensor sensitivity and algorithm performance. On the other hand, the capability of the satellite/sensor system to achieve an adequate spatial and temporal sampling of the phenomena or area of concern is analysed. Finally, an assessment of present and short-term EO capability for operational applications is addressed.

A number of general statement may be expressed when comparing Tables 7.1 – 7.7, Table 14 and Table 17.

- About 20 % of the geophysical parameters of concern for the characterisation of coastal and inland waters are potentially derivable with EO techniques.
- Most applications identified in coastal areas require spatial resolution of about 100 m. This accuracy is not met with present and planned sensors, which are not dedicated to operational issues and local investigations (Table 17).
- Most of the algorithms implemented are based on empirical or semi-analytical models that are generally not tuned for coastal and inland waters (Table 18). Moreover these algorithms are not robust. Then it is difficult or even impossible to predict the accuracy that could be obtained in specific regions.

Table 17. Quantitative achievements of EO algorithms. The values reported in the table result of a compilation of the various algorithms presented, and are representative of the best achievement that can be expected for EO.

Remotely sensed geophysical parameters	Algorithms			Satellite / sensor		
	Units	Range of value	Relative or absolute accuracy	Spatial resolution (m)	Frequency of sampling (days)	Delay (days)
Water constituents						
C_{chl} [Chl-a]	mg.m ⁻³	0.019 - 50	30 - 40 %	30 & 1000	1	7 - 14
Primary production	gC.m ⁻² .d ⁻¹	0.5 - 3.0	NS	1000	1	7 - 14
C_{sm}	mg.l ⁻¹	0.1 - 30	30 - 50 %	20 to 1000	1 - 3	3
C_v / a_v (380 or 440)	mgC.m ⁻³	0.1 - 20	50 %	1000	1	7 - 14
C_{det}	% [chl]	10 - 15	NS	1000	1	7 - 14
Optical properties						
Absorption coef.: a	m ⁻¹	all	NS	1000	1	7 - 14
Scattering coef.: b	m ⁻¹	all	NS	1000	1	7 - 14
Diffuse attenuation: K_d	m ⁻¹	0- 6.5	0.1	20 to 1000	1	7 - 14
Photic depth	m	all	NS	20 to 1000	1	7 - 14
Turbidity/Secchi depth	m	0.25 - 5.0	50 %	1000	1	7 - 14
Water colour, λ_{dom}	nm	472 - 575	10	1000	1	7 - 14
Surface Temperature						
WST	°C	all	< 0.5	1000	1	1
Depth-related						
Bathymetry	m	1 - 30	1	20 - 100	3	3
Topography	m	> 1	0.6	30	35	14
Water level	m	0.1	0.1	5.10 ⁴	35	14
Morphometry						
Oil spill area	km ²	> 0.5	0.04	20	3	10

Delay: delay of availability of products

NS: not specified

III.4.2 Spatio-temporal coverage: requirements versus EO capability

The capability of EO data to meet the requirements for monitoring of coastal and inland waters depends in part on the spatial and temporal sampling characteristics of the sensor systems that are used derived the relevant geophysical parameters. A number of geophysical parameters are usually needed for a particular “subject of concern”. It is from the “higher-level” perspective that one can assess how well EO data can meet the users’ requirements. The spatio-temporal requirements for each subject of concern were surveyed in Part II and summarised in Table 14. These requirements are summarised graphically in Figure 7 below. Note that within a subject of concern there can be various sampling requirements. For example, Figure 7 illustrates that monitoring natural hazards in a crisis situation (e.g., flooding) will be more demanding in term of observational frequency (i.e., hourly) than is monitoring natural hazards such as climatic variations of inland water levels (i.e., seasonally).

Table 18. Statistics on algorithm types

Environmental parameters	Type of algorithm		
	Empirical	Semi-analytical	Inverse method
Water constituents			
C_{chl} [Chl-a]	13	1	3
Primary production	2	1	-
Auxiliary pigments	-	1	-
C_{sm}	6	-	3
$C_y/a_y(380)$	-	1	3
C_{det}	-	-	1
Optical properties			
Inherent properties: a, b	-	3	-
Diffuse attenuation: K_d	4	-	-
Photic depth	1	-	-
Turbidity/Secchi depth	2	-	-
Water colour, λ_{dom}	-	1	-
Surface Temperature			
WST	-	3	-
Depth-related			
Bathymetry / topography	-	2	1
Water level	-	1	-
Morphometry			
Shoreline	-	2	-
Oil spill extent	-	1	-
Total	28	17	4

The spatio-temporal sampling capabilities of a single overpass of a single sensor are shown in Figure 7. Shown are the main presently operating sensors that are used to derive coastal and inland water environmental parameters. The lower and upper limits of the spatial scale of the sensor systems correspond to the sensor resolution (e.g., 30 m for Landsat TM) and the swath width (e.g., 185 km for Landsat TM). The lower limit of the temporal scale corresponds to the nominal repeat period (e.g., 16 days for Landsat TM).

Figure 7 readily reveals the degree of inadequacy in the sampling characteristics of the EO sensors. For natural hazards (crisis) and anthropogenic hazards, neither the spatial nor temporal requirements are close to the EO capabilities. For eutrophication / algae blooms, the mismatch is less severe, though neither requirement is really met. For subjects of concern such as ecological assessment and shore processes, there is at least partial overlap in space and time, though not necessarily with the optimal sensors for retrieving the relevant geophysical parameters, e.g., SeaWiFS vs. SPOT.

On the one hand, the EO sampling limitations appear formidable, especially given that the effective temporal sampling rate (for optical and thermal IR sensors) is reduced because of cloud cover common over European marine and coastal regions.

On the other hand, satellite EO should not be summarily dismissed as a means for monitoring of coastal and inland waters. First, the specified sampling requirements represent a user's "wish list", which are generally not be realised with conventional monitoring with *in situ* measurements. Second, the spatio-temporal sampling at higher latitudes is generally better than the nominal, equatorial values shown in Figure 7. Moreover, combining EO data from similar sensors on different platforms (e.g., AVHRR and ERS-ATSR) can lead to improved, albeit irregular temporal sampling.

Nonetheless, it is apparent that the present spaceborne sensor systems have spatio-temporal sampling capabilities that are only partially adequate to meet the monitoring requirements for most of the subjects of concern.

Figure 7. Spatio-temporal requirements versus capabilities of spaceborne EO sensor systems presently used for deriving water environmental parameters. The water environmental parameters per se are not shown, but rather the “subjects of concern” that require information on these parameters.

III.4.3 Range-of-value/accuracy: requirements versus EO capability

The range of values and the level of accuracy are also important in assessing the present capabilities of EO techniques for monitoring of coastal and inland waters. Table 17 lists both the range-of-values and the absolute or relative (%) accuracy of the present-day geophysical parameter-retrieval algorithms pertinent to the coastal and inland water monitoring. Each subject of concern has, of course, its own set of relevant geophysical parameters, as surveyed in Part II. For a given geophysical parameter, the quantitative requirements are generally consistent between subjects of concern (Table 14), though there are exceptions. For example, ecological monitoring deals with C_{sm} values $< 5 \text{ mg.l}^{-1}$, whereas anthropogenic hazard monitoring may involve C_{sm} values up to about 1000 mg.l^{-1} . The correspondence between the various requirements versus EO capabilities is summarised graphically in Figure 8, and evaluated afterwards.

Figure 8. Range-of-value and accuracy requirements versus earth observation (EO) algorithms capabilities of the main presently-operating spaceborne sensor systems used for deriving water environmental parameters.

III.4.4 Synthesis of EO capability

Remote sensing has a valuable role in defining the baseline conditions against which the impact of natural disasters can be evaluated, even if remote sensing cannot play a very helpful operational role during the evolution of the disaster.

Although measurements from water samples might be more accurate and allow deriving more variables, they have their limitation when extrapolated in time and space. Isolines drawn from samples are often less accurate than maps derived from satellites, thus, a comparison of the accuracy of both methods should be done on the level of spatial temporal maps, not on the level of comparing the accuracy of a sample and the derived quantities from a pixel.

A. *Water constituents:*

Most of the algorithms implemented for the retrieval of water constituents concentration are based on empirical or semi-analytical models that are tuned for Case I oligotrophic waters, and then that are not directly usable for coastal and inland waters. These empirical models are based either on worldwide open ocean data sets or local data sets that are only representative of a region. Moreover, these algorithms are not robust. Therefore, it is difficult or even impossible to predict the accuracy that could be obtained by using one of these models in a different region.

Only a small range of chlorophyll concentration is determinable with space sensors because the current algorithms only work for Case I oligotrophic waters. These algorithms saturate when C_{chl} is greater than 40 mg.m^{-3} . This is a main limitation for the use of satellite-derived chlorophyll for coastal and particularly for inland waters where a chlorophyll concentration up to 500 mg.m^{-3} may be encountered. This limit has implications on all those parameters, which are based on estimates of chlorophyll concentration, and in particular on the estimation of primary production.

Same types of remarks can be made about suspended matter. Very high load of suspended sediment may be found in coastal and inland waters under certain conditions (run-off, hydrodynamics, storm, etc.). Available algorithms may saturate for extreme environmental conditions.

Nevertheless, even if EO capability cannot cover the entire range of value of interest for final users. Satellite data can certainly be valuable in many cases representing average conditions.

The last years have seen the emergence of algorithms for Case II waters (coastal and inland waters). Solutions are mathematically more complex, often more computer-time consuming. Therefore, performance regarding operational applications must be assessed. Most of these new methods are based on inverse techniques, and involve the retrieval of all optically active components simultaneously.

B. *Optical properties*

Optical properties are not directly used in operational context, as they are basic physical properties of the water environments. However, they play a fundamental role for hydro-ecological models, and for the development of new and more robust algorithms such as analytical models and inverse methods.

C. *Surface temperature*

SST is certainly the most popular geophysical parameter since it is considered as important for all user applications investigated in this study.

Requirements are met in terms of range of value, accuracy and temporal resolution. An effort remains to be made in order to meet the requirements of high spatial resolution required by most of environmental and industrial applications in coastal and inland water areas.

D. *Depth-related parameters*

Depth-related parameters have been described as important for ecological assessment, management of natural resources and natural hazards monitoring.

Both range-of-value and accuracy required by the users are achieved by EO technology. The algorithms available have been developed for both optical and microwave sensors.

However an operational level has not been reached yet. In general the methods involved in the retrieval of depth-related parameters require ancillary data and *a priori* knowledge of the site that is investigated.

Spatio-temporal requirements are met for bathymetry, but not for water level as estimated by altimeter data.

E. Morphometry

The two parameters identified, i.e., shoreline changes and oil slicks, have been mentioned in relation to anthropogenic and natural hazards. For these applications, the required range-of-value and accuracy are achieved by EO algorithms. Spatio-temporal requirements are met for shoreline detection and changes, but they are not reached for oil spill monitoring, which requires quasi-real time observations on an hourly basis.

Anthropogenic and natural hazards often necessitate an emergency response. This implies an operational context based on real time data acquisition (satellite programming, data recording and downloading, fast data processing and product delivery). Such context requires an efficient collaboration between space agencies/data providers, added-value companies and field teams (final users).

III.5 Software and standard data products

This section provides a synthetic analysis of solutions relevant for decision makers. For each application areas, information and references on the availability of standard product and commercial/ or free of charge software are listed.

III.5.1 Standard data products

Information on standard products provided by space agencies and other data providers.

III.5.1.1 Water constituents products

Table 19.1 Geophysical parameter available as standard products from space agencies and other data providers (water constituents).

Geophysical parameters	Product name	Provider	Remarks
C_{chl} , K(490)	SeaWiFS Level 2 & 3	SeaWiFS: NASA/SeaWiFS (http://seawifs.gsfc.nasa.gov/SEAWIFS.html).	Authorised research users
C_{chl} , K(490)	SeaWiFS Level 2 & 3	Orbimage (http://www.orbimage.com)	For commercial applications
C_{chl} , K(490)	OCTS Level 2 & level 3	http://www.eorc.nasda.go.jp/ADEOS/D_ataAdeos.html	Authorised research users
C_{chl} , water type	POLDER Level 2 & level 3	http://earth-sciences.cnes.fr:8060/polder/Mission.html	Authorised research users
C_{chl} , K(490)	CZCS Level 2 & level 3	http://seawifs.gsfc.nasa.gov/SEAWIFS/IMAGES/CZCS_DATA.html	
C_{chl} , K(490)	CZCS Level 2 & level 3	http://me-www.jrc.it/OCEAN/ocean.html	Limited to Europe
Radiances	MOS level 1	http://www.ba.dlr.de/NE-WS/ws5/data_access.html	Level 1 product for research

No standard products for other parameters, including C_{sm} and C_y .

Satellite-derived primary production maps should be available in the future as a standard product from MODIS sensor.

III.5.1.2 Optical properties products

Only diffuse attenuation product - K(490) - is delivered by standard data providers. Other optical properties discussed in this report are not distributed as standard products.

III.5.1.3 Water temperature products

Table 19.2: Geophysical parameter available as standard products from space agencies and other data providers (surface temperature).

Geophysical parameters	Product name	Provider	Remarks
WST	NOAA pathfinder AVHRR	http://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/cdrom/Pathfinder2/index.htm http://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/sst/ http://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/cdrom/Pathfinder2/index.htm	
WST	ESA-ATSR	http://earth1.esrin.esa.it/14/eo4.10077/eeo2.500	
WST	ADEOS/OCTS SST	http://www.eorc.nasda.go.jp/ADEOS/D ataAdeos.html	

III.5.1.4 Depth related products

Water-depth related parameters derived from EO data are not available as standard products. Nevertheless, we give hereafter a list of providers of satellite data that are used in the algorithms described in Chapter 2.

Table 19.3: Geophysical parameter available as standard products from space agencies and other data providers (depth related parameters).

Geophysical parameters	Product name	Provider	Remarks
Topography	ERS and Topex-Poseidon sea surface height and topography	http://earth1.esrin.esa.it/14/eo4.10077/eeo2.267 http://www.spotimage.fr	Altimeter data
Bathymetry Topography	ERS SAR	http://earth1.esrin.esa.it/14/eo4.10077/eeo2.100 http://www.spotimage.fr	SAR data
Topography	Topex-Poseidon sea surface height and topography	http://podaac.jpl.nasa.gov/topex/ http://neptune.gsfc.nasa.gov/ocean.html (altimeter pathfinder)	Altimeter data
Topography	AVISO service	CLS, France http://www-projet.cnes.fr:8170/HTML/information/general/guide_uk.html	Altimeter products from ERS and Topex-poseidon

III.5.1.5 Morphometry products

Morphometric parameters derived from EO data are not available as standard products. Nevertheless, we give hereafter a list of providers of satellite data that are used in the algorithms described in Chapter 2.

III.5.2 Availability of processing algorithms

This section mainly shows tables that synthesise the availability of the main algorithms. These tables include references to web-pages for freeware and shareware and contacts for commercial software.

Table 20 presents a list of software package that integrate algorithms described in the report.

Table 20. Software and computing programs that integrate at least one algorithm described in this report.

Geophysical parameters	Product name	Contact point	Description
C_{chl} , K(490)	PC-SEAPAK	ftp://dacc.gsfc.nasa.gov/pub/czcs/software/SeaPAK (commercial)	Analysis of CZCS and AVHRR data
C_{chl} , K(490)	SeaDAS	NASA/GSFC http://seadas.gsfc.nasa.gov/ (free of charge, requires IDL)	Image Analysis and Processing for SeaWiFS, OCTS & CZCS
Primary production	BIO-OPT	http://www.ioccg.org/software/Ocean_Production/index.html (Bedford model) (free of charge)	Primary production model based on CZCS-derived chlorophyll
Primary production	VGPM	http://warrior.rutgers.edu/ (VGPM) (free of charge)	The Vertical Generalised primary Production Model
Algal bloom	ABMS	Anite Systems. E-mail: environment@anitesystems.com	Algal bloom monitoring
WST	PESKET	Service Applications de la Télédétection, IFREMER, Centre de Brest, BP. 70, 29263 Plouzané, France Phone: +33 98 22 40 40	Sea surface temperature calculation, AVHRR
WST	XV AVHRR	http://smis.iki.rssi.ru/inform/engl/soft/e_avhrr.htm (commercial)	Sea surface temperature calculation, AVHRR
Bathymetry	Multiscope	Alain DENIZON MultiScope Sales Engineer e-mail : denizon@matra-ms2i.fr	Image processing software that includes the French Navy algorithm for water-depth retrieval in clear water.
Bathymetry, Topography	SAR bathymetry	ARGOSS (service): http://www.argoss.nl/a81_ameland	Bathymetry retrieval from SAR data
Oil spill detection and morphometry	SAR Ocean Feature Extraction	Satlantic Inc. (Canada) E-mail: norman@satlantic.com	Surface ocean feature detection and analysis package, that includes oil spill detection.
Oil spill detection and morphometry	Oil spill	http://www.oceanor.no/oceanor/frames.htm	Oil spill movement prediction
C_{chl} , C_{sm} , C_y , C_{det}	SNNS	http://www.informatik.uni-stuttgart.de/~ipvr/bv/projekte/snns/snns.html (free of charge)	Artificial neural network system. May be customised to match ocean colour applications
C_{chl} , C_{sm} , C_y , C_{det}	TNTlite	http://www.microimages.com/ (free of charge)	Include a neural network algorithm
C_{chl} , C_{sm} , C_{yc} , C_{det}	IDL/ENVI	http://www.rsinc.com/ (commercial) + http://www.techexpo.com/WWW/opto-knowledge/	Include neural network

PART IV. PROSPECTIVE VIEW ON FUTURE IMPROVEMENTS

IV.1 The challenges of the society of the 21st century

The regions surrounding or bordering water bodies are favourite areas for human expansion. The global increase of the world population induces an increase of the population in the coastal areas and those bordering inland waters. To this general trend should be superimposed the seasonal migrations due to tourism which are increasing because of several factors, including the increasing human life time and life level and the decreasing amount of working hours. Modern intensive agriculture has a tendency to increase the run-off of pollutants into the water bodies. This also holds for the bordering cities whose population (and consequently sewage) is increasing with the decrease of the rural population. Also observed is an increasing water transport either of persons or of goods. Finally the European population is more and more sensitive to environment preservation. All these facts result into an increasing pressure on coastal areas and inland waters with an increasing need for a better knowledge and management of these areas. The sustainable development of these areas together with the preservation of the environment are major challenges of the century to come and EO is one of the key instruments to deal with these challenges.

Among the most important parameters to know, are water quality, and sea level and shoreline changes. EO data have already demonstrated their usefulness as shown in previous parts of this document, and will still be useful though much more efforts should still be devoted in the near future in order to increase the quality (taken in a broad sense) of the parameters under concern.

As a whole it can be concluded from previous parts that no dedicated and manageable EO system is capable of fulfilling all the needs for coastal and inland waters. Accordingly scientists and managers should also devote a great deal of effort to set up integrated systems for the management of these areas.

The main challenges for EO are on the one hand technical: instruments, missions, resolutions, algorithms, models, and on the other hand, cultural: the EO community should make efforts towards managers and customers and make EO products more attractive and usable.

IV.2 The main technical challenges with respect to EO data

IV.2.1 Hydro-optical models

As it was explicitly stated above, due to extremely complex composition of case II waters, it is practically impossible to use efficiently simple and universally applicable colour-ratio parametrisations as water quality retrieval algorithms. The most promising water quality retrieval algorithms are those which are based on application of sophisticated mathematical techniques in conjunction with appropriate hydro-optical models. These may vary, depending on a real water body and/or vegetation season, from rather simple (including two-three optically-active components) to fairly complex (encompassing four, five and even six optically-active components) hydro-optical models. Development of such hydro-optical models is one of the

most urgent tasks for the scientific community whose activities are focused on remote sensing of inland and marine coastal waters. The hydro-optical models in question should be representative of each optical/trophic status class of water bodies/water masses encountered in Europe. Besides they should be vegetation season-specific.

However, for automated processing of case II water images without any preliminary or *a priori* information, it is important, as a first step, to qualitatively identify the targeted water body/water mass composition, and hence the complexity of the hydro-optical model to be used for water quality retrieval purposes. Once identified, this model can then be used in conjunction with such retrieval techniques discussed in the previous sections as Multivariate Optimisation Technique, Neural Network Simulation Technique, Singular Value Decomposition Technique, etc.

The identification of the number and nature of major optically active components could be done by applying, for instance, methods of differential spectroscopy. In turn, a very detailed information on the spectral distribution of the radiance captured by a remote sensor is required. Ideally, a continuous spectrum of the radiance is needed. The present ocean colour satellite sensors (such as SeaWiFS) provide information in a limited number of wavebands in the visible spectrum (e.g., 6 in the case of SeaWiFS). Application of differential spectroscopy to such spectra will not result in accurate determination of the desired information.

Development of hyperspectral satellite sensors (e.g., the sensor envisaged under NEMO- the Naval EarthMap Observer Satellite Program) could be a solution to this problem. Besides, the hyperspectral information would be equally a powerful tool for a more precise determination of optical characteristics of the atmospheric aerosol over the targeted scene. It offers a possibility of applying much more adequate atmospheric correction to the raw radiances captured by a remote sensor. Given that the path radiance (i.e., the radiance contribution due to the intervening atmosphere) generally accounts for *ca.* 95-97 per cent of the signal captured by a satellite sensor, a considerable improvement of the atmospheric correction technique would result in further enhancement of water quality parameter retrieval precision.

This atmospheric problem is enhanced for small water bodies and along the shoreline where the radiance diffused by the near land elements contribute to the signal sensed by satellite through atmospheric scattering in a non-negligible way. Some sensors to come, such as MERIS, MODIS, MOS or POLDER, are partly dedicated to the monitoring of water content. Though not being hyperspectral sensors, they are expected to make a breakthrough mostly by providing well-calibrated measurements and water-leaving radiances well-corrected for atmospheric and water surface effects.

Improvements in sensor technology, optronics and data flow downlinked to the ground stations have been large and some are still to come. The limits related to satellite/sensors technology include transmission capabilities, orbits, optronics, including signal-to-noise ratio, and calibration. Calibration is of paramount importance, and many efforts have been devoted to that domain. Some limits have been attained regarding the hardware embarked aboard for calibration purposes. Recently, techniques for vicarious calibrations have been developed, which allow external calibration by analysis of image output from the sensor or from a set of sensors. Calibration has several aspects depending upon the instrument. Consider a hyperspectral instrument using a CCD matrix. At stake is the co-registration of the spectral bands, the absolute calibration of each band, the relative calibration of each band relative to the others, the relative calibration of each CCD relative to the others for each spectral band, and also relative to the other spectral bands. Though the results are not yet available, the POLDER mission is an excellent example of the mixing of pre-flight calibration using standard laboratory procedures and in-flight vicarious calibrations. If not well handled, calibration may be an obstacle to the use of EO data.

IV.2.2 Space missions and improvements of spatial and temporal resolution

From the preceding discussion it appears clearly that improving spatial and temporal coverage of earth observation over inland and coastal waters are at the centre of the concern if the identified requirements would be met.

Many important characteristics of inland water bodies and marine coastal zones have spatial scales ranging from several tens to several hundreds of meters. This imposes stringent requirements to the spatial resolution of satellite sensors. The present ocean colour sensors (such as SeaWiFS) have a much coarser spatial resolution (about 1 km). Future satellite sensors designed for surveillance of inland and marine coastal waters should comply with these requirements.

Not infrequently, some hydro-biological and hydro-thermodynamic processes in marine coastal and inland waters have characteristic temporal scales ranging from several hours to one day. SeaWiFS, for example, has a revisiting frequency of about two days on the average. Taking into account the obscuring impact of cloudiness and sunglint, this frequency, in reality, is even much less. Obviously, to overcome this difficulty, one may think of at least three (Dr. Gregg's estimation: "Backscatter", August 1998, pp. 34-35) polar orbiting ocean - colour satellites (better identical). Actually, the main trends for improving of spatial and temporal resolution are:

- Dedicated missions that aim to cover specific regions at high frequency. Low orbit can be considered to enhance the spatial resolution,
- Constellation of micro-satellites on complementary orbits,
- Mathematical techniques and synergy between missions.

IV.2.2.1 Foreseen missions and instruments

Many EO missions and instruments are planned in the years to come. Given the large amount of parameters to measure and the large range of time and space scales to monitor, most of them are relevant to coastal and inland waters. Several are mentioned here because they may represent a real breakthrough.

The most awaited missions are the European Space Agency mission MERIS and the NASA mission MODIS. Though the MERIS instrument is by itself an imaging spectrometer, it would work as an imaging radiometer with 15 spectral bands, a large number compared to the present situation. These spectral bands have been defined prior to the mission and will constitute the baseline of the mission with possible changes to explore potentials of hyperspectral in other fields on interest. The Japanese space agency NASDA is also proposing a mission GLI, with rather similar objectives and instrument. More information can be found at

- MERIS: <http://envisat.estec.esa.nl>
- MODIS: <http://ltpwww.gsfc.nasa.gov/MODIS/MODIS.html>
- GLI: http://hdsn.eoc.nasda.go.jp/guide/guide/satellite/sendata/gli_e.html

The instrument PRISM, proposed by the European Space Agency, is a hyperspectral imager which would cover two main regions, namely the visible-short-wave infrared from 0.45 to 2.35 μm , where the instrument works as an imaging spectrometer with a spectral resolution of about 10 nm, and the Thermal Infrared range from 8 to 12.3 μm , divided into 3 spectral bands with a typical width of 1 μm , where the instrument works as an imaging radiometer. The spatial resolution at nadir is about 50 m over a swath of 50 km. Access to any site on Earth could be provided within three days (directional measurements).

The U. S. Navy has launched a programme for a dedicated mission to monitor open and coastal waters. The Naval EarthMap Observer (NEMO) would have spatial resolutions of 30 and 60 m, 228 spectral bands (from 400 to 2500 nm), a swath of 200 km, and a revisit time of 7 days.

- <http://nemo.nrl.navy.mil/public/index.html>

The U. S. company Orbimage proposes an all-round mission, for terrestrial, ocean and atmosphere purposes, called Orbview-4. It would have a resolution of 8 m, 200 spectral bands (from 450 to 2500 nm, a swath of 5 km, a revisit time of less than 3 days, at an orbital altitude of 470 km (www.orbimage.com)).

The new technology of miniaturisation allows us to build small satellites that are ten times lighter and cheaper than the traditional earth observation satellites, while performing identical missions. This revolution gave birth to the new generation of mini-satellites of about 100 kg to 1 t, to micro-satellites of about 10 to 100 kg, and to nano-satellites lighter than 10 kg.

Alcatel Space Industries, France has recently proposed a Mediterranean system named COSME which integrate the telecommunication satellite MedSat, a mini-satellite COALAS that use the Proteus platform, and the associated ground-based infrastructure. The implementation of such a regional system should be decided before this end of 1998. It will be entirely privately funded. In particular, COALAS should be used for risk assessment and management (earthquakes, storms, flooding, etc.), with derived products dedicated to insurance companies. The launch date is foreseen for 2001 or 2002. The investment is planned to be reimbursed within three to four years. Furthermore, Alcatel also plans to make use of the Proteus space platform for the satellites 3S et ISIS .

Besides, NASA develops two other remote sensing advanced programmes, namely the Earth Orbiter-1 satellite in the frame of New Millennium programme, and the two missions of the new programme Earth System Science Pathfinder (ESSP). The satellite EO-1, that should be launched in 1998 will carry the *Advanced Land Imager* with a spatial resolution of 10 m in panchromatic mode, and about 30 m in hyperspectral (200 bands) mode. The missions under ESSP are the *Vegetation Canopy Lidar* and the *Gravity Recovery Climate*, which will respectively be launched in 2000, and the Cosmos-3M in 2001.

In Israel, several programmes are planned. The first one concerns the micro-satellite Techsat-2, which must carry a high resolution camera. The second one is a Germany-Israel co-operation project between OHB, El-Op, GAF and Ben-Gourion University. It aims at the development of a small satellite which will carry a 12-bands multispectral (0,435 to 1 mm). 5 m-resolution images will be provided, covering 30 km swath. They are planned to be used for agriculture, forestry, hydrology, etc. Besides, it will be compatible with all existing receiving stations.

The US-Israel project EROS gathers Core Software, Ltd and Israel Aircraft Industries (IAI). The goal is to use two satellites derived from Ofeq-3 in order to build an image database that should be available on the world-wide network ImageNet. Exploitation will be performed by Paragon Imaging Inc., a filial of Core Software. 10 m-resolution data from the two EROS satellites should be available from 1999.

In UK, SSTL, Ltd (Surrey Satellite Technology Limited), after having built eleven micro-satellites of about 50 kg (four UoSAT, two Kitsat, S80T, Healthsat, PoSat, Cerise, FaSat-Alpha), is constructing a brand new 300 kg-platform for UoSAT-12. The satellite will carry one 10 m-panchromatic camera and one 40 m- multispectral one.

One way to improve spatial and temporal coverage is to launch a constellation of identical or similar satellite/sensor on complementary orbits. Data provided by such satellites can then be used in synergy to information at the required space and time intervals for an identified application. Several programs that address this goal are planned:

The project *Resource 21*, gathers Boeing et GDE Inc. It is focused on a six-satellites constellation with a payload consisting of a 10 m resolution multispectral camera that will be dedicated to farming assistance in USA.

Project for the Mediterranean: Alenia Aerospazio (Italy) propose the COSMO/Skymed constellation for the survey of the Mediterranean basin. The constellation will be made of three satellites equipped with optical sensors and four others with radar sensors. The platform are derived from the Globalstar (450 kg), and should cost about US\$ 30 et 40 M each. Alenia has also undertaken a study for ESA on the future generation of satellite at the horizon 2010. The constellation would be made of five “optical satellites” (resolution of about 0.5 m) and ten radar satellites (resolution of 1 m). The satellites in the latter constellation will be lighter (300 kg), and will include the latest technology, such as adaptive optics, inflating structures, cryostats a cycle of Stirling, ultra-light antennas, nano and micro-technology, electrical propulsion, etc.

DLR (Germany) considers the launch of the micro-satellites FIRES and BIRD. The first one will be constructed in co-operation with OHB, and will be equipped with a MOMS camera for fire detection, the second is planned to be built in partnership with the Free University of Berlin, and will include a wide-angle camera, named WAOSS.

IV.2.2.2 Mathematical techniques and synergy between missions

Data from various ocean colour sensors can be used in order to improve sampling coverage, and to provide annual means of chlorophyll-a concentration. Cloudiness prevents deriving chlorophyll-a concentrations over about 60 percent of the ocean on a daily basis, excluding that already lost (about 30 per cent) due to high sun glint. It results into a global coverage of about 12 per cent on a daily basis. Merging chlorophyll-a concentrations derived from multiple sensors in complementary orbit is the primary means to increase sampling frequency to obtain information at times shorter than the spatial decorrelation times in the coastal zones and other dynamic areas (3-5 days, Denman & Abbott, 1988).

Until 2005, not less than seven ocean-colour sensors should be launched and operating in overlapping: the European MERIS, the American MODIS AM, MODIS PM, and MISR (Multi-angle Imaging, Spectro-Radiometer), the Japanese OCTS/GLI and the French POLDER-2 (Polarisation and Directionality of the Earth Reflectances) and SeaWiFS. The task of assessing errors in these combined and merged data, taken with different designs, bands, swaths, and times of day, is discussed within the proposed plan for Sensor Intercomparison and Merger for Biological and Interdisciplinary Ocean Studies (SIMBIOS).

Requirement for higher resolution data in all areas indicates the strong need for modelling for all sites in order to integrate *in situ* data and to intelligently interpolate between observations to intelligently estimate higher resolution fields. Many users stressed that there was a critical need for “routine” data availability and that methods would be needed to “fill gaps” in cloud data and that modelling may need to be employed to provide continuous fields both in space and time. Data fusion paradigm can be called upon, and approaches combining data / products from different missions and advanced mathematical tools for the modelling of processes in time and space are to be developed, validated and turned into operational routine.

IV.2.3 Observation network

Each year meteorologists receive over 20 million sets of data describing the atmosphere. The picture for the ocean as well as for the coastal areas and inland waters is, by contrast, quite bleak except for the limited satellite views of the sea surface. The Global Climate Observation System, under joint development by WMO, IOC, ICSU and UNEP, is providing comprehensive information on the total climate system, involving a multi-disciplinary range of physical, chemical and biological properties and atmospheric, oceanic, hydrologic, cryospheric and terrestrial processes. It even goes beyond climate, up to operational models. The Global Ocean Observation System (GOOS) constitutes the oceanographic component of the GCOS. The EuroGOOS is the European contribution to GOOS.

Within EuroGOOS, the coastal areas have a high priority because of their importance in Europe and the intimate effects of coastal changes on economic development and human habitation. The initial emphasis of the coastal zone module is on the changes in coastal current and frontal structures, especially those related to cross-shelf transport. Another module "assessment and prediction of the health of the ocean" aims at establishing a framework for monitoring the levels and trends in levels of pollution on global as well as on regional scales and for assessments of the health of the ocean, in particular the coastal and shelf areas. The data collection and analysis is based on the use of commonly agreed methods, standards and methodologies.

A companion programme to GOOS, the Global Terrestrial Observation System (GTOS), deals with land, including inland waters, and was launched later.

Though several documents of the GOOS or GTOS recognise the effectiveness of EO data, it is a real challenge of the years-to-come for EO data to be used in operational services. Among difficulties to overcome are

- the operational aspects of the space missions themselves, including the assessment and control of the quality of the products,
- the continuity of EO data,
- the development of techniques, methods and means for integration of EO derived information and product into standard procedures or methodologies.

The EO community should direct its efforts to this observation network in which EO data are naturally taking place. This challenge is certainly the most rewarding for the EO community.

IV.3 What can be expected for the next 20 years

As reported in the conclusion of Part III of this document, none of the twenty geophysical parameters identified in this study entirely satisfied the expressed requirements in terms of range-of-value, accuracy, spatial resolution, and frequency of sampling. This section tries to underline the main solutions that are or could be considered in order to enhance in one way or another the quality and the effectiveness of EO-derived geophysical parameters in operational contexts.

IV.3.1 *Improvement of identified geophysical parameters*

IV.3.1.1 **Water constituents and derivable parameters**

Efforts are in progress concerning a more accurate estimation of water constituents in case II waters (coastal and inland). In particular, MERIS spectrometer that will fly onboard the European Envisat, has been designed to better match requirements for coastal water applications. This leads to an enhanced spatial resolution (300 m in full resolution mode), and more robust algorithms that are described hereafter.

A. Chlorophyll-a, suspended sediments, gelbstoff and detritus concentrations

Assessments of chlorophyll-a, suspended sediments, gelbstoff and detritus concentrations will strongly benefit from these algorithms and from the MERIS capabilities. An accuracy of 20 - 25 % is expected for these parameters. The algorithms are described in the following forms.

Parameter: Chlorophyll-a C_{chl} ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)						Form : 47			
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: MERIS case I water		Range of pigments concentration values: 0.03 - 30 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$		Accuracy: +25% or -20%		References Morel & Antoine, 1997	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
MERIS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1999	0.3 or 1.2 at nadir	ca 2 days	
<u>Ancillary data</u> : requirements for atmospheric correction: ozone concentration, atmospheric pressure, wind speed, flag case I/case II waters, database of aerosol models.									
<u>Algorithm description</u> :									
The following algorithm has been proposed by Morel & Antoine as the standard method to derive chlorophyll index from MERIS.									
$\rho_w(\lambda, \theta_s, \theta', \Delta\phi) = \pi t_{\theta_s}(\lambda) \mathfrak{R}(\theta') \frac{f(\lambda, \theta_s)}{Q(\lambda, \theta_s, \theta', \Delta\phi)} \left[\frac{b_b(\lambda)}{a(\lambda)} \right]$									
<p>ρ_w is the water-leaving reflectance, t_{θ_s} is the irradiance transmittance, $\mathfrak{R}(\theta')$ is a geometrical factor accounting for all refraction and reflection effects at the air-sea interface, Q describes the bi-directional character of the diffuse reflectance of oceanic case I waters and f is the ratio of $R(0)$ to (b_b/a).</p>									
It is now assumed that [Chl] is calculated as usual with a function Φ of the ratio of $[b_b/a]$ at two wavelengths, which is used as an index of the bio-optical state:									
$Chl = \Phi \left(\left[\frac{b_b}{a}(\lambda_1) \right] \left[\frac{b_b}{a}(\lambda_2) \right]^{-1} \right)$									
The practical implementation of Φ leads to the following relationship:									
$\log_{10} [pigment\ index] = \sum_{x=0}^n A_x (\log_{10} \rho)^x$									
where $\rho = [b_b(443)/a(443)][b_b(555)/a(555)]^{-1}$									
The final adjustment of the order (n) of the expansion and of the numerical values of the coefficient (A) has not yet been performed. When the marine signal at 443 nm becomes too low (high chlorophyll content) or if it is believed that atmospheric correction at 443 nm is not accurate enough, another couple of wavelength will be used, such as 490 - 555 nm.									

Parameter: Chlorophyll-a C_{chl} ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), C_{sm} ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$), C_y ($a(440)$ in m^{-1})						Form : 48			
Algorithm type: Neural network		Algorithm name: MERIS case II water		Range of values: Chl: 0.003 - 50 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ sm: 0.03 - 50 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ CDOM: 0.002 - 2 m^{-1}		Accuracy:		References Doerffer & Schiller, 1997	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave				
MERIS						from 1999	0.3 or 1.2 at nadir	ca 2 days	
<p><u>Ancillary data</u>: requirements for atmospheric correction: bright pixel algorithm from Plymouth Marine laboratory, ozone concentration, atmospheric pressure, wind speed, flag case I/case II waters, database of aerosol models.</p>									
<p><u>Algorithm description</u>:</p> <p>The algorithm is a multiple non-linear regression method (neural network) that derives the concentrations of non-absorbing suspended matter and phytoplankton pigments, and the coloured dissolved organic carbon absorption at 440 nm from water-leaving reflectances of eight MERIS bands.</p> <p>Since the range of concentrations of water constituents in the targeted water bodies is generally limited, the possible reflectance spectra can be computed in advance with an appropriate radiative models (ocean-atmosphere photon tracing Monte Carlo radiative transfer code, in the present algorithm, see Gordon, 1994; Mobley, 1994; Morel & Gentili, 1991). Establishing an inverse relationship between the state vector (concentration vector C, wind speed, atmosphere vector) and the corresponding computed reflectances, the results of such simulations are stored in the form of a neural network and used for retrieval of remotely sensed data. For this specific application, a feed forward error-back-propagation neural network is used only as a multiple non-linear regression technique to parameterise an inverse relationship between C and other parameters, and the computed reflectances. Actually, the construction of such a look-up table for the required combinations of C_i and respective reflectances is hardly practicable since such a table would be too large to be effectively operative. However, if an approximation function derived from such a table could be developed, then it would be possible to affect the desired interpolation and ultimately reduce the required computing time to emulate the inverse model.</p> <p>The algorithm uses a four-layer neural network. The first-layer neurones are the elements of a feature vector which consists of the water-leaving reflectances from 8 MERIS bands (412, 442, 490, 510, 560, 620, 665, 705 nm), and 3 angles (viewing and sun-zenith angles, and difference between the azimuth of the solar and viewing directions). The second and third layers are internal or "hidden" layers. The fourth layer is the output layer, the number of neurone in the output layer equals the number of parameters to be determined, i.e., the concentration of the three water-column constituents. Each neurone in the network is connected to all neurones in both the preceding and subsequent layers by connections with associated weights.</p> <p>The NN algorithm is experimental, it has not gone through a thorough ground truth validation, and consequently lacks substantiated estimations of retrieval accuracy which greatly is determined by the actual applicability (translatability) of the hydro-optical model to the water body/water mass targeted by the remote sensor. The NN algorithm is believed to be particularly efficient in the case of sounding waters rich in OAC.</p>									

Parameter: Chlorophyll-a C_{chl} ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$), C_y ($a(440)$ in m^{-1})							Form : 49		
Algorithm type: Band ratio		Algorithm name: MODIS case I water		Range of pigments concentration values: 0.03 - 30 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$		Accuracy: +25% or -20%		References Clark, 1997	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
MODIS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1999	0.25, 0.5, 1 at nadir	ca 1 days	
<u>Ancillary data</u> : requirements for atmospheric correction: ozone concentration, atmospheric pressure, wind speed, flag case I/case II waters, database of aerosol models.									
<u>Algorithm description</u> :									
In case I waters, all water-column constituents (product) are expected to be retrieved using radiance ratios. A general form for the ratios is given as: $\log \text{Product} = A (\log X)^3 + B (\log X)^2 + C \log X + D/E$ where A , B , C , D and E are least-squares regression coefficients or constants, and									
$X = \frac{(e)L_{wn}(band9 - 443nm) + (f)L_{wn}(band10 - 490nm) + (g)L_{wn}(band11 - 530nm)}{L_{wn}(band12 - 550nm)}$									
Here the constants e , f and g are 0 or 1 and are used to select the spectral bands to derive the specific product. Preliminary regression and band selection coefficients are as follows:									
Product	A	B	C	D	E	e	f	g	
log(Pigment) CZCS	0	0	-1.27	0.5	1	1	0	0	
log(Pigment) SeaWiFS	-0.63	4.43	-11.2	8.73	1	1	1	1	
log(Chl-a)	0	0	-1.40	0.07	1	1	0	0	
log(K(490))	-0.15	1.44	-4.53	3.56	1	1	1	1	

Parameter: Chlorophyll-a C_{chl} ($\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$)						Form : 50			
Algorithm type: Semi-analytical		Algorithm name: MODIS case II water		Range of pigments concentration values: 0.03 - 30 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$		Accuracy: +25% or -20%		References Clark, 1997	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
MODIS	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave	from 1999	0.25, 0.5, 1 at nadir	ca 1 days	
<p><u>Ancillary data</u>: requirements for atmospheric correction: ozone concentration, atmospheric pressure, wind speed, flag case I/case II waters, database of aerosol models.</p>									
<p><u>Algorithm description</u>:</p> <p>In case II waters, MODIS scientific team suggests a semi-empirical method based on the relation that links the remote sensing reflectance (R_{rs}) to the ratio of the backscattering coefficient (b_b) to the absorption coefficient a.</p> $R_{rs}(\lambda) = \alpha \frac{b_b(\lambda)}{a(\lambda)}$ <p>where α is a constant close to 0.3.</p> <p>b_b can be expressed as the sum of the contribution from the water itself (see Smith & Baker, 1981) and from the particles, and a is expressed as the sum of the contribution of water itself, chlorophyll, and a term that combines detritus and dissolved coloured organic matter.</p> $b_b(\lambda) = b_{bw}(\lambda) + b_{bp}(\lambda) \quad a(\lambda) = a_w(\lambda) + a_{chl}(\lambda) + a_y(\lambda)$ $b_{bp}(\lambda) = X \left[\frac{551}{\lambda} \right]^Y \quad a_y(\lambda) = a_y(400\text{nm}) \exp^{-S(\lambda-400)}$ $X = X_o + X_1 R_{rs}(551) \quad a_{chl}(\lambda) = a_0(\lambda) \exp \left[a_1(\lambda) \tanh \left[-0.5 \log \left(\frac{a_{chl}(675)}{0.01} \right) \right] \right] - a_{chl}(675) \quad a_w \text{ is}$ $Y = Y_o + Y_1 \frac{R_{rs}(443)}{R_{rs}(488)}$ <p>given by Pope <i>et al.</i> (1997). X_o, X_1, Y_o, Y_1, a_o, a_1 and S are empirically determined.</p> <p>Then only two unknowns remain: $a_{chl}(675)$ and $a_y(400)$. The system is solved by using the two following equations:</p> $\frac{R_{rs}(412)}{R_{rs}(443)} = \frac{b_b(412)}{b_b(443)} \frac{a(443)}{a(412)} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{R_{rs}(443)}{R_{rs}(551)} = \frac{b_b(443)}{b_b(551)} \frac{a(551)}{a(443)}$ <p>The system is then solved for $a_{chl}(675)$ and $a_y(400)$.</p> <p>When the semi-analytical algorithm returns a value for $a_{chl}(675)$, [chl-a] is determined via a direct relationship to this value. This step requires precise knowledge of the chlorophyll-specific absorption coefficient for phytoplankton at 675 nm, $a_{chl}^*(675)$.</p>									

Parameter: Concentrations of Chl-a & auxiliary pigments C_{pigm} ($\mu\text{g l}^{-1}$)					Form : 51				
Algorithm type: Semi-analytic		Algorithm name: Gaussian decomposition (GD)		Range of values: not specified		Accuracy: not specified		References Hoepffner & Sathyendranath, 1993	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operationa l period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
hyperspectral	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave		ca. 0.02	airborne	
<u>Ancillary data</u> : requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.).									
<u>Algorithm description</u> : The GD algorithm is an experimental tool to infer the concentrations of major algal pigments (Chl a, b, c, carotenoids) from the total absorption coefficient a of bulk water. The bulk water absorption is assumed to be controlled by water <i>per se</i> (a_w), particulate material (a_p) and coloured dissolved organic matter (yellow substance) (a_y): $a(\lambda) = a_w(\lambda) + a_p(\lambda) + a_y(\lambda)$ [1]. The dissolved organic absorption spectral dependence can be expressed as C_{chl} [2], where λ_0 is a reference wavelength(e.g., 380). Particulate absorption could be decomposed into contributions from phytoplankton pigments (a_{ph}), and detritus (a_d): $a_p(\lambda) = a_{ph}(\lambda) + a_d(\lambda)$ [3], where $a_d(\lambda) = a_d(\lambda_0) \exp(-q(\lambda - \lambda_0))$ [4]. q takes values over a range (0.006 - 016) nm^{-1} ; λ_0 is the reference wavelength (e.g., the same as in [2]). Absorption by phytoplankton is controlled by the contribution of all pigments composing the algae pigment system: $a_{ph}(\lambda) = \sum_{i=1}^n a_i^*(\lambda)C_i$ [5], where a_i^* is the specific absorption coefficient of the i th pigment with concentration C_i . The specific absorption coefficients of each pigment can be estimated by decomposition of $a_{ph}(\lambda)$ into several Gaussian bands simulating the absorption properties of these pigments: $a_{ph}(\lambda) = \sum_{j=1}^l C_j a_j^*(\lambda_{mj}) \exp\left \frac{(\lambda - \lambda_{mj})^2}{2\sigma_j^2} \right $ [6] where λ_{mj} is the position of maximum absorption for the j th Gaussian band, σ_j determines the width of the peak, $a_j^*(\lambda_{mj})$ is the specific absorption coefficient for the j th absorption band at λ_{mj} , C_j is the concentration of the pigment responsible for the λ_{mj} absorption band . Since a given pigment may be responsible for more than one absorption band, $l > n$. The regressions between the height (y) of each Gaussian band and the concentration of the pigment responsible in each case are as follows: $y_{chla}(415) = 0.0002 + 0.018C_{chla} \quad y_{chla}(435) = 0.0017 + 0.044C_{chla}$ $y_{chla}(460) = 0.0015 + 0.021C_{chla}$ $y_{chlb}(460) = 0.0015 + 0.097C_{chlb} \quad y_{chlb}(655) = 0.0006 + 0.019C_{chlb}$ $y_{chlc}(460) = 0.0015 + 0.097C_{chlc} \quad y_{chlc}(643) = 0.0005 + 0.037C_{chlc}$ $y_{carot}(490) = 0.0026 + 0.031C_{carot} \quad y_{carot}(532) = 0.0007 + 0.018C_{carot}$ In all cases the regression was found significant ($r > 0.89$) with linear fits that explained more than 75% of the variance. The GD algorithm is experimental and has not undergone a thorough field validation. For its implementation it requires first the application of those algorithms which retrieve bulk water absorption coefficient a (see relevant forms).									

B. Total carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus

Carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus are essential parameters to describe and characterise coastal and inland water quality, in terms of ecological and trophic status, from which one can assess anthropogenic impacts for example. There is no way that is foreseen for the direct determination of these quantities from remote sensors. Since these parameters can be estimated to some extent, from chlorophyll concentration derived from EO ocean colour data, improvements are only expected if significant improvements are obtained for chlorophyll estimation in turbid waters. Besides, the present methods only deal with empirical relationships, which are obviously limited (see Form 52). Improvements in estimates of total carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus could come from the assimilation of EO data such as satellite-derived chlorophyll and sea-surface temperature in biogeochemical models.

C. Primary production

Primary production is not directly derivable with space sensors since the production is by definition estimate over a period of time (e.g., day, month, season, year). No major improvement is foreseen in the near future on algorithms with relevance to coastal and inland waters.

Efforts are being made on the use of near-surface phytoplankton concentration measurements to estimate water column primary productivity, but there is considerable scatter in this empirical relationship, and it has been shown that a simple, constant relationship will not work for the world ocean. Use of ancillary data such as water physical properties, solar irradiation and meteorological information, improve models. However, this uncertainty points to the need for continued work on the factors and processes affecting the water column production. Despite the relative inaccuracy of satellite estimates of water column productivity, it is likely that the improved sampling characteristics of EO data will help reducing these errors.

Parameter: Total carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus						Form : 52			
Algorithm type: Converting factor		Algorithm name: Constant ratio		Range of values: not specified		Accuracy: not specified		References See description	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)	
Ocean Colour	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave				
<u>Ancillary data</u> : requirements for atmospheric corrections: ozone climatology, atmospheric pressure, orbital navigation software, scene parameters (date, time, location, etc.)									
<u>Algorithm description</u> :									
<p>Empirical relationships have been proposed to relate chlorophyll concentration with total carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus, since these three elements are commonly used to characterise the ecological status of natural water bodies. It is clear that all the empirical algorithms presented hereafter require tuning to local conditions. The purpose of listing them is to show how they could be built basing on the site-specific statistics which should be collected or used from archived data.</p> <p>The first approach is based on a constant ratio between chlorophyll-a concentration and total organic carbon: $[C] = 55 * [Chl-a]$. Then, other elements may be derived using the Redfield ratios, based on the proportion of carbon, nitrogen and phosphorus in organic matter ($C_{106} N_{16} P_1$): $[N] = [C] / 6.7$ and $[P] = [C] / 106$</p> <p>The algorithm obtained by Dillon and Rigler (1974) relates the chlorophyll concentration to total phosphorus in lake: $\log[Chl] = 0.596\log[Ptotal] - 0.080$, where $[Chl]$ and $[Ptotal]$ are the annual mean concentrations of chlorophyll and phosphorus in lake euphotic zone</p> <p>Petrova (1990) suggested a relationship between the mean annual concentration of phosphorus and chlorophyll concentration averaged over the vegetation summer period: $\log[Chl] = 1.43 \log[Ptotal] - 1.64$</p> <p>For Lake Ladoga the following relationship is established between total phosphorus and total nitrogen for the vegetation summer time (Petrova, 1987): $[Ptotal] = 37.5 [Ntotal]$</p> <p>We have not found at the time of this report the relevant expressions for total carbon. May be it could be again recommended to the interested people to establish such a relationship between the phytoplankton chlorophyll concentration in the euphotic zone and the total carbon for each individual water body (or water mass in the case of coastal waters)?</p> <p>Besides, an expression has been presented in an OECD report (1980) that relates primary production (PP, mgC/m2) to $[Ptotal]$ in the euphotic zone: $\log PP = 0.558 [Ptotal] + 1.494$</p>									

IV.3.1.2 Optical properties

A. Inherent properties (a, b)

Improvements are expected by developing inverse models to derive inherent optical properties from remote sensing reflectance. Inverse models are commonly based on multivariate optimisation approach, such as the Levenberg-Marquardt method, and multiple non-linear regression, such as neural network classification. These methods require hyperspectral data as inputs to better solve the system, and thus will be fully operational by taking advantage of the planned spaceborne spectrometer (NEMO-COIS, Orbview-4).

B. Diffuse attenuation coefficient

Inverse modelling approach can also be considered for retrieving the diffuse attenuation from ocean colour data, instead of empirical or semi-empirical relationships (Durand & Cauneau, 1997a [250]; 1997b [251]; 1998 [252]). The proposed approach leads to an unbiased estimate of K_d .

C. Water colour

The requirements are already met by using present technology.

D. Turbidity / Secchi disk depth

Retrieval algorithms for Secchi depth have mainly been implemented to allow inter-comparison with *in situ* measurements. Secchi disk measurements are still popular because it is easy and cheap. Nevertheless, the trend is to reduce the use of such measurements while accurate and affordable instruments are available nowadays (e.g., AC-9), measuring directly inherent optical properties. For the above reasons we believe that no effort will be made on improving Secchi depth retrieval, in the future.

IV.3.1.3 Physical properties

A. Surface temperature

There is no foreseen improvement on the accuracy of the retrieval of the surface temperature. The present and near-future radiometric sensitivity of 0.1 K with a noise level lower than this value is sufficient for most applications dealing spatial distribution of temperature. Current algorithms for the correction of atmospheric effects, including no correction for a better mapping of the short-scale gradients, should be sufficient for future use.

Efforts are being made for the assessment of the vertical gradient of the temperature, and to define precisely the different temperatures occurring in surface processes. This requests efforts for better models. The trend toward smaller pixel is ongoing. No definite plan for space sensors with pixel below 60 m is currently known.

B. Surface salinity

Airborne passive microwave sensor as been successfully used to map salinity in Chesapeake Bay (Miller & Zaitzeff, 1997 [267]). Similar technology, adapted for spaceborne platforms, has been proposed to the ESA Earth Explorer Opportunity Mission.

C. Surface current

Surface current is a parameter of interest that is not currently derived from EO data. Several attempts have been made and published (see e.g., Wald, 1985 [283]). The techniques used are either cross-correlation methods (tracking movements of "patches") or solving the heat preservation equation using reasonable assumptions. They apply to time series of surface temperature (for both techniques) or of optical or biological properties.

The advances made in the automatisisation of image processing techniques (mostly accurate geolocation and pattern recognition) should allow maps of surface currents to be derived on a routine basis, with an accuracy of approx. 0.5 m/s. The main obstacle is still the "access" to the site, which includes cloud coverage and revisit time for a single mission or for combined missions.

IV.3.1.4 Depth-related parameters

A. Water depth

Durand & Cauneau (1997a [250]; 1997b [251]; 1998 [252]) algorithm for bathymetry estimation from hyperspectral images is based on an inverse modelling with synthesised database. This algorithm is still under development. It is believed that its products will meet the requirements for accuracy.

B. Bottom topography

A peculiarly promising algorithm is based on the method given by Forget (1995 [253]) based on the analysis of the refraction of monochromatic swells by the sea bottom over continental shelf. This method, where variations in wavelength and direction of quasi-monochromatic swells are used to estimate the water depth, has been previously described.

Starting with the a propagation model for the swell, the changes of wavenumber \mathbf{K} and direction Y are given by:

$$\Omega = \omega_0 + \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{U}$$

$$\omega = (gK \operatorname{th}(KH))^{1/2}$$

$$\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial s} = - \left\{ \frac{1}{K} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial H} \frac{\partial H}{\partial v} + \frac{\partial}{\partial v} \left(\frac{\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{U}}{K} \right) \right\} \times \left(\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial K} + \frac{\mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{U}}{K} \right)^{-1}$$

where ω is the period of the monochromatic swell (in radian/s), g is the gravitation constant, K is the modulus of the wave vector for the swell (in radian/m), H is the water depth (in m), \mathbf{U} is the current vector, n and s are the curvilinear co-ordinates respectively along and perpendicular to the swell radius.

Perspectives for an operational application of this method may be envisioned by using new data processing techniques in data assimilation and synergy between SAR and other remote sensing instruments. This may allow taking explicitly into account additional hydrodynamic phenomena that may affect the evolution of the swell, such as coastal drifts or tidal currents. A data assimilation scheme may help to process simultaneously the information on the swell field given by a SAR and the information on currents given by radiometers as previously described.

C. Water level and shoreline

A second perspective may also be offered by the possibilities in SAR interferometry. In fact, this technique that already shown to be of a great reliability for measuring water level in well defined water bodies, such as reservoirs offers really good possibilities (Schwabisch, 1997 [281]). Accurate measurements of water level (half of the radar wavelength, typically 2.5 cm in C band) can thus be achieved in near all-weather conditions, with good applications for dams, lakes, etc.

The main limitations encountered in the method are in coastal areas, where the complex imagery of waves in surf zones drastically hinders the possibilities for interferometry. An additional problem is that, in some coastal zones, rates of changes of coastline between two image acquisitions may vary significantly, *i.e.* with vertical surface variations greater than the half radar wavelength, under processes of tides, seiches, erosion or sedimentation. Interferometric methods are quite accurate for relative mapping, but generally do not allow to achieve absolute measurements, as any phase shifts greater than one wavelength in the image results in an equivalent ambiguity for the absolute positioning of the corresponding pixel in space.

Parameter: Coastline detection and tracing(m)						Form : 53		
Algorithm type: Supervised classification		Algorithm name: Textural analysis		Range of values: ➤ 5 pixels ➤		Max. error outerlimits: depending upon surf zone extent, 20 pixels	References Bijaoui, Cauneau, 1995	
Sensor name	Sensor type		spectral range			operational period	spatial resolution (km)	temporal resolution (at 45° N)
	airborne	spaceborne	visible	infrared	microwave			
SAR						from 1978	typical :25m	typical 10 days
Ancillary data:								
<p><u>Algorithm description:</u></p> <p><i>Note 1:</i> Coastline detection on SAR images is mainly depending upon two difficulties. The speckle noise, which is a multiplicative noise, results in strong variations of the image intensity in both land and sea. Thus classical thresholding of SAR images may not be used as in optics. The second problem is due to the dependency of the mean image intensity over water areas upon the surface wind conditions. For typical values of a wind varying from 0 to 15 m/s, the sea may appear respectively as a smooth target, or with a surface roughness comparable to the one of land. In the latter condition, the present algorithm is the only one to lead to proper results.</p> <p><i>Note 2:</i> This algorithm may be used for oil slick detection.</p> <p>Starting with the SAR image :</p> <p>I - Pre-processing steps: None, the algorithm may be used on both single or multi-look images.</p> <p>II - Edge tracing algorithm :</p> <p>Step 1: Multiresolution analysis, to the scale 1 :16 using the « à trous » Wavelet transform, and keep the first level of coefficients image</p> <p>Step 2: Define samples areas over sea and land</p> <p>Step 3: Compute co-occurrence matrices, mean and variances over the two samples</p> <p>Step 4: Classify the whole coefficients image, by computing at every point the co-occurrence matrix, and applying a Bayesian classification scheme.</p>								

IV.3.1.5 Morphometry

A. Oil spill extent and thickness

Perspectives for improvements of oil spill extension measurements are expected in two domains. Advanced methodologies for the quantitative estimation of slick extension have been investigated, especially in the context of the French/Canadian/British GATT projects, and EC the Clean Seas project.

If laser fluoro-sensors are still envisioned as the best instruments for slick thickness measurements, such sensors will always be limited to applications in airborne remote sensing, due to the use of the near-ultraviolet domain for detection. Possibilities offered by multiband and multipolarisation SARs should be further investigated, especially for the X+C VV bands, and with some possibilities for the L band.

Regarding the aspects of slick extension, the range of the meteorological conditions under which a slick may be detected in SAR images is large, as previously described, but no perspective may be envisioned for slick detection in strong winds conditions. From the point of view of end users, requirements in terms of spatial and radiometric resolutions are already met, the most important limitation for operational applications being the restricted time cover.

New methods for measuring extension, diffusion and age of an oil slick using are under investigation (Redondo, 1998 [276]). In this work, it has been shown that an oil slick extension may be characterised by the type of transport mechanism occurring at sea surface: wind or hydrodynamic transport and diffusion. In the latter case, it has been shown that turbulent diffusion may affect significantly both shape and spatial extension of a slick, resulting in a weak detectability in a SAR image. A new method, based on the analysis of the structure function of the sea surface turbulent field has been developed, its application in recent tests has shown significant improvements in the accuracy of the morphometry of oil slicks, compared with classical methods.

B. Run-off and plumes

Classical detection of run-off and plumes in both visible, thermal and microwave domains has been extensively studied, with a recent review in the Clean Seas project. As the detection of the major European-river plumes in AVHRR, ATSR or ERS-SAR images is nowadays quite operational, recent developments for an automatisation of the detection, tracking, and morphometry of the plumes have been achieved. The goal of such projects is to ensure a proper integration of the remote sensing data into devoted coastal management integrated systems.

Advanced methodologies based on multi-resolution analysis, mathematical morphology used in test cases on the Rhône river and the Rhine river plumes have proved to be reliable for future operational applications (Lecat, 1997 [263], and Moriconi, 1998 [268]). Automatic measurements of plume perimeters and surfaces, as well as geo-localisation and mapping have been used in such tests to feed coastal GIS (Geographical Information Systems) in order to design future decision-making tools for coastal management.

IV.3.2 Expected new EO-derived geophysical parameters

EO data are foreseen to contribute to the retrieval of a number a geophysical parameters, either directly using a retrieval algorithm or by providing low level parameters, which can then be used in high level algorithms, including numerical models of the water dynamics.

Presents a prognostic list of such “new EO-derived” parameters. The domain of application is mentioned as well as hints on the probable method of retrieval.

Table 21. New water quality/environment parameters related to coastal and inland waters that should be derivable with space sensors in the future.

Water quality/ Environmental parameters	Concern for		Method of retrieval
	Inland waters	Coastal waters	
1. Physical			
water conductivity	yes	yes	Derived from water salinity
water density	yes	yes	Derived from water temperature and salinity
water radioactivity	yes	yes	Dynamical information derived from C_{sm} and sediment transport pattern
2. Chemical			
water salinity	yes	yes	Passive microwave (low-frequency microwave radiometer). Technology presently available for airborne platform.
Total carbon	yes	yes	Empirical relationships between chlorophyll +sm+CDOM concentrations and total carbon
total phosphorus	yes	yes	Empirical relationship between total carbon and phosphorus or hydro-optical model, statistically significant correlation between C_{chl} and total phosphorus
total nitrogen	yes	yes	Empirical relationship between total carbon and nitrogen or hydro-optical model, statistically significant correlation between C_{chl} and total phosphorus
heavy metals	yes	yes	Dynamical information derived from C_{sm} and sediment transport pattern
oil type	yes	yes	Polarimetric observation of oil spill with SAR. Directional radiance pattern from directional optical sensor such as POLDER
3. Biological			
phaeopigments	yes	yes	[CZCS-pigments] minus [Chl-a]
phytoplankton concentration / biomass	yes	yes	Empirical relationship between [chl-a] and phytoplankton
bacterioplankton: concentration / biomass	yes	yes	Empirical relationship between EO-derived phycoerythrin concentration and cyanobacteria
zooplankton: concentration / biomass	yes	yes	Assimilation of EO-derived bio-parameters in ecological models
Detritus concentration	yes	yes	Assimilation of EO-derived bio-parameters in ecological models
4. Ecological			
Biodiversity: phytoplankton	yes	yes	Hyperspectral sensor: Estimate from the concentration of the main photosynthetic pigments (chl-a,b,c; phycoerythrin, carotenoids)
Biota habitat status: littoral zone pelagic zone benthos	no no yes	yes yes yes	
5. Dynamics			
river flow, current	yes	yes	time series of suspended sediment concentration, and/or surface temperatures

Correlation of P/N and chlorophyll depends on the phase of the algal bloom.

IV.3.3 *Hyperspectral technology to space*

A majority of the EO community believes that spaceborne hyperspectral technology (continuous spectrum obtained from instrument with a high number of narrow and continuous spectral bands) will greatly enhance the benefit of EO in the monitoring of the water quality. Presently there is no spaceborne hyperspectral sensor, but several missions are planned (see previous section). Nevertheless, numerous studies and research have been carried out, which aim at monitoring of inland and coastal waters with airborne hyperspectral sensors such as CASI, CAESAR, DAIS, GER, HYDICE and AVIRIS. The two last have been used and modified in order to prepare the future spaceborne hyperspectral sensor, e.g., COIS on NEMO, which will be dedicated to coastal zone monitoring and surveillance.

Examples of application of airborne spectrometers to inland- and coastal-water quality monitoring can be found in the following articles: Borstad, 1992 [240]; Borstad and Hill, 1989 [241]; Borstad *et al.*, 1994 [242]; Denman and Abbott, 1988 [249]; Gower and Borstad, 1993 [254]; Jupp *et al.*, 1994 [260]; Keller *et al.*, 1999 [261]; McLeod *et al.*, 1992 [265]; Matthews *et al.*, 1994 [266]; Ostlund *et al.*, 1994 [271]; Petterson *et al.*, 1993 [273], Populus *et al.*, 1994 [274]; Robinson and Dyer, 1997 [277]; Sandridge and Holyer, 1995 [278]; Schaepmann *et al.*, 1997 [280] and Terrie and Arnone, 1994 [282].

Since this technology has a high potential, some elements of hyperspectral image processing algorithms are presented hereafter.

Two major approaches based on hyperspectral data are presently considered:

- Because of the large number of spectral bands, spectrometers deliver a huge quantity of data that can be selected, combined and processed in order to optimise the extraction of specific information. In this approach, hyperspectral data serve as a pool of potential information in which a user can choose or create spectral bands that are optimal for his application, by respectively selecting channels or averaging several bands together. Then classical multispectral processing may be applied to these bands. Examples of such approach applied to inland and coastal waters can be found in Dekker, 1993 [247]; Dekker *et al.*, 1994 [248]; Hoogenboom, 1998b [257], 1998c [258]; Hudson *et al.*, 1994 [259]; Keller *et al.*, 1999 [261]; Olbert and Fischer, 1997 [269] and Olbert *et al.*, 1994 [270]).
- Method based on the spectrum analysis in order to retrieve optically-active components (AOC). General information concerning this approach can be found in for example in Clark *et al.* (1987 [244]; 1991 [245]). Such approach is likely to improve the retrieval of the various water-column constituents, and even to facilitate the discrimination of different types of algae pigments (chlorophyll-a, phycoerythrin, carotenoids, etc.) by the analysis of absorption peaks that are specific of each pigments (Boardman, 1989 [238]; Hoepffner and Sathyendranath, 1993 [185]).

Approach based on the analysis of absorption spectra necessitates algorithms that are dedicated to spectral analysis, such as the Minimum noise fraction transform (MNF), the spectral angle mapper (SAM) and spectral feature fitting (SFF). These algorithms have been implemented in the context of hyperspectral data analysis. Their applications to the retrieval of water quality parameters in coastal and inland waters are under investigation by several science teams, worldwide. Hereafter we just give an introduction to some of these techniques.

The **minimum noise fraction (MNF)** transformation is used to determine the inherent dimensionality of image data, to segregate noise in the data, and to reduce the computational requirements for subsequent processing (Green *et al.*, 1988 [255]). The MNF transform is

essentially two subsequent principal component transformations. The first transformation, based on an estimated noise covariance matrix, decorrelates and re-scales the noise in the data. This first step results in transformed data in which the noise has unit variance and no band-to-band correlation. The second step is a standard Principal Components transformation of the noise-whitened data. For the purposes of further spectral processing, the inherent dimensionality of the data is determined by examination of the final eigen-values and the associated images. The data space can be divided into two parts: one part associated with large eigen-values and coherent eigen images, and a complementary part with near-unity eigen values and noise-dominated images. By using only the coherent portions, the noise is separated from the data, thus improving spectral processing results. The noise estimate can come from one of two sources; from the dark current image acquired with the data (for example AVIRIS), or from noise statistics calculated from the data themselves.

The **Spectral Angle Mapper (SAM)** is an automated method for comparing image spectra to individual spectra or a spectral library (Kruse *et al.*, 1993 [262]). SAM assumes that the data have been reduced to apparent reflectance. The algorithm determines the similarity between two spectra by calculating the “spectral angle” between them, treating them as vectors in a space with dimensionality equal to the number of bands (*nb*). SAM determines the similarity of an unknown spectrum *t* to a reference spectrum *r*, by applying the following equation:

$$\alpha = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{t \bullet r}{\|t\| \|r\|} \right)$$

For each reference spectrum chosen in the analysis of a hyperspectral image, the spectral angle α is determined for every image spectrum (pixel). This value, in radians, is assigned to the corresponding pixel in the output SAM image, one output image for each reference spectrum. The derived spectral angle maps form a new data cube with the number of bands equal to the number of reference spectra used in the mapping.

The result is a classification image showing the best SAM match at each pixel and a “rule” image for each AOC showing the actual angular distance in radians between each spectrum in the image and the reference spectrum. Darker pixels in the rule images represent smaller spectral angles, and thus spectra that are more similar to the reference spectrum. The rule images can be used for subsequent classifications using different thresholds to decide which pixels are included in the SAM classification image.

Spectral Feature Fitting (SFF) is an absorption-feature-based method for matching image spectra to reference AOC spectra. Techniques for direct identification of AOC, via extraction of specific spectral features from field and laboratory reflectance spectra have been in use for many years (Clark *et al.*, 1987 [244]). Recently, these techniques have been applied to imaging spectrometer data (Clark *et al.*, 1991 [245]).

All of these methods require that data be reduced to reflectance and that a continuum be removed from the reflectance data prior to analysis. A continuum is a mathematical function used to isolate a particular absorption feature for analysis (Clark and Roush, 1984 [243]). It corresponds to a background signal unrelated to specific absorption features of interest.

Spectral feature fitting requires that reference AOC spectra be scaled to match the unknown spectrum. A “scale” image is produced for each AOC selected for analysis, by first subtracting the continuum-removed spectra from one, thus inverting them and making the continuum zero. A single multiplicative scaling factor is then determined that makes the reference spectrum match the unknown spectrum. Assuming that a reasonable spectral range has been selected, a large scaling factor is equivalent to a deep spectral feature, while a small scaling factor indicates a

weak spectral feature. A least-squares-fit is then calculated band-by-band between each reference AOC and the unknown spectrum. The total root-mean-square (RMS) error is used to form a RMS image for each water constituent.

IV.4 Towards future management systems for coastal and inland waters

Monitoring and documenting changes in coastal and near-shore areas require an interdisciplinary approach that integrates physical, chemical, biological and geological observations with socio-economic uses of the coastal zones. A global strategy is also required.

An efficient management, exploitation and planning of shore area is recognised as a major stake for most countries. This awareness has recently shown itself through the emergence of new concepts such as sustainable development, integrated coastal management, and adaptive management, and by associated actions and research programmes.

At the interface between the marine and terrestrial domains, the coastal zone is a very special environment where takes place specific and complex biological, chemical and physical processes and phenomena. These processes are generally coupled which make them difficult to study and understand. Furthermore, extensive anthropogenic activities (i.e., industries, marine culture, fisheries, and tourism) that grow in these areas, lead to rapid modifications of the medium properties. Likewise, it is now acknowledged that interactions between natural systems and people are bilateral, i.e., human beings induce ecological changes and are influenced by these changes (Scavia, 1997 [279]).

Estuarine, coastal, and large lakes ecosystems should thus be at the centre of environmental policy development because of the enormous economic and ecological benefit these region provide to the countries. Coincident with that attention, there should be a demand for improved data and information and an advanced understanding of how ecosystems functions and how human and natural processes interact to cause changes within them.

Besides it is now widely approved that the research efforts should move to larger spatial scales because cumulative spatial impacts can and do override small-scale processes and individual actions. This required working from watershed perspective, paying more attention to ocean-estuarine and land-sea interactions, and looking to “distant” impacts such as atmospheric transport and climate effects. Likewise, longer time scales must be considered because cumulative temporal effects can mask contemporary impacts. Working at longer time scales requires a recognition that long time-series data sets and monitoring are essential to both effective management and comprehensive science agendas, as evidenced by the GOOS and GTOS programmes. *EO techniques offer unique opportunities for such data sets and monitoring programmes.*

The complexity and the dynamic nature of the coastal environment coupled with the fact that the coastal zone community is multi-user and multi-agency poses a challenge for representing coastal information in a generic decision support system. The ability of GIS (Geographical Information System) to i) represent data dynamically, at a range of spatial scales, ii) facilitate customised presentation and display by the user, and iii) combine, aggregate, integrate and analyse disparate data in a variety of value-added ways, enables decisions to be taken based on the best possible interpretation of the available information. Although aiming at a common objective – the need to manage the coast in a sustainable way and seeking the optimum balance between uses and their effects – ICZM (Integrated Coastal Zone Management) policy and decision making initiatives have been quite heterogeneous, namely in the adopted frameworks and instruments. Considerable

differences also arise in the methodologies used to handle biophysical and socio-economic data, as well as criteria and methods used to support decision making.

The spatial dimension associated with the biophysical and socio-economic processes and pressures occurring in the coastal zone is often underestimated. In order to achieve sustainable use of coastal zones, namely through an adequate allocation of existing ecological, socio-economic and institutional resources, space should not be neglected in ICZM policies and decision making. So, *there is a need and opportunity for the development of adequate methodologies that can handle and integrate such spatial data, such as EO data, assembling it in valuable information, directed to support the decision making process, namely in the design of instruments and frameworks.*

EO data and techniques are to be used more and more for the management of coastal and inland waters. A recent example is the effort undertaken by the Geodetic Survey, USA, which produces maps of the shorelines.

At their lowest levels, shorelines represent the basis for the computation of the internationally accepted boundaries of Territorial Sea, the Exclusive Economic Zone and the High Sea, and at their highest levels determine the legal boundary of a Nation. The two measurements, which sometimes are 20 to 30 meters apart, must be very accurate because in USA and other federal nations, they establish the legal basis for the determination of federal versus coastal state sovereignty. The Geodetic Survey has already demonstrated the quality of EO data in producing accurate shoreline charts. It now wants to use more and more EO data since remote sensing will shorten the time it takes the Geodetic Survey to produce shoreline charts. It now takes up to two years to acquire shoreline imagery via aerial photography, extract the shoreline and deliver the map. Acquiring the images involves taking a series of photographs as an airplane moves across an area. Using EO data aboard satellite and airplanes could reduce that to a period of months. At the Geodetic Survey, aerial photographs must be scheduled one year in advance and be taken during high and low tides, which is not always when the sky is clear. Sensors like SAR can operate regardless of time of the day and weather conditions. However this flexibility with respect to the tides may be hindered by the sun-synchronous properties of the carrying space platform, as it is presently the case. The time-savings with SAR can be immense. However there will always be a place for aerial survey because it still yields the highest resolution and highest-fidelity available.

This example illustrates several trends in the use of EO data. It firstly shows *the increase of awareness about EO data in the users community.* More and more agencies, companies and industries are ready to use EO data in their routine operations.

Secondly, it shows that *many customers are not opposing spaceborne sensors and airborne campaigns, or spaceborne sensors and in situ campaigns:* they understand the advantages and drawbacks of each approach, which depend upon the application and the geographical area. They are trying to take the best of the two worlds.

Thirdly, and with the same spirit of efficiency, *customers do not hesitate to use different types of data.* In the case of the shorelines, the Geodetic Survey uses spaceborne SAR and optical data, and optical airborne instruments. A recent work made for the French Navy (Bardey *et al.*, to be published) for the survey of frontal structures with respect to the propagation of sound waves was made by combining images of surface temperature and pigments.

Future systems for the management of coastal and inland waters will follow these trends. EO products will be more and more integrated into intelligent systems capable of ingesting different types of information to produce what is requested by the managers.

Though the obstacles foreseen for the realisation of such systems are not relevant to EO data for most of them, the EO community has a role to play. Major problems pertain to database management, networking for easy and fast access of computers by other computers, and interface to computing services so that investigators can initiate through networks processing on remote supercomputers for analysis and interpretation of the data in the library, resulting in finished, custom data products. *Access to data or products is crucial for customers*, whether they are scientists or engineers or managers. Large efforts are spent on data organisation, archiving and retrieval and the EO community has strongly participate to these. Standards have been established in EO domain by the Committee on EO standards (CEOS). Catalogue Interoperability Protocol (CIP) is a recent means for a fast retrieval of any type of EO data, linking archives proposed by different operators and sites. Recent progress in information technology has strongly improved access to data, including EO data. The Internet is one example, data compression techniques another one. Surfing on the crest of this progress, retrieval and access to data and products will be strongly enhanced in the near-future. The NASA has proposed a concept called database-in-the-sky which means that scientists and others EO users could tap into a fleet of Earth-observing satellites able to process, sort and store the information they collect. The US Navy is developing a software that will give scientists equipped only with a personal computer instant access to weather and ocean data transmitted via satellite from remote locations such as buoys at sea.

However some efforts are to be made by the EO community for a better use of EO data.

The EO community should pursue its efforts towards customers. It is very likely that under the influence of the coastal areas and inland waters managers, new indices / integrated parameters will appear. For land studies, some indices such as the NDVI (Normalised Difference Vegetation Index) and more elaborated others are currently used. They have the advantage of being simple to use; they integrate several processes of different nature and are a synthesis of complex phenomena. As such, they are welcomed by managers and decision systems. The EO community should be ready to propose such indices, preferably in a multi-disciplinary approach.

Data quality should be increased, data continuity should be ensured, access to a given site and to its properties in terms of time and space scales should be improved. EO community should work on better algorithms and should also promote dedicated EO missions in close co-operation with customers. Because of the large number of parameters that are to be accessed on a large range of time and space scales, a single EO mission cannot be fully satisfactorily. Monitoring coastal and inland waters will still request a combined use of space missions of different nature. *Data fusion will become a major research domain in EO data.* A multi-disciplinary approach is requested since it calls upon fundamental physical and biological processes, applied mathematics and instrument engineering. Integration / ingestion of EO products in decision system that can be based upon GIS is a key issue of the following years.

EO has a formidable potential for water quality in coastal and inland waters. EO data are and will be more and more integrated into intelligent systems for management of these waters and surrounding lands. The EO community has an important role to play for increasing the quality, taken in a broad sense, of the products derived from EO data, including support to dedicated space missions, and their use by customers or integration in systems, and for the education of customers and managers

PART V. APPENDICES

V.1 Bibliographic references

V.1.1 Bibliography for Part I

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V.2 Acronyms

V.2.1 General abbreviations

Abbreviation	Meaning
CalCOFI	California Cooperative Oceanic Fisheries Investigation
CEO	Centre for Earth Observation
CEOS	Committee on Earth Observation Satellites
DG	Directorate General
EC	European Community
EEA	European Environment Agency
CEC	Commission of the European Communities
EO	Earth observation
ESA	European Space Agency
EU	European Union
E&C	Environment and Climate
ESA	European Space Agency
FAO	Food and Agricultural Organisation
GIS	Geographic Information System
GOOS	Global Ocean Observing System
GTOS	Global Terrestrial Observing System
ICAM	Integrated Coastal Area Management
ICAMS	Integrated Coastal Analysis and Monitoring System
JRC	European Joint Research Centre
MAST	Marine Science and Technology
SAI	Space Applications Institute
WWW	World Wide Web
[P]	Phosphorus concentration
[N]	Nitrogen concentration
[C]	Carbon concentration
[NO ₃]	Nitrate concentration
BOD	Biological Oxygen Demand
COD	Chemical Oxygen Demand

V.2.2 Geophysical parameters and remote sensing

Parameters	Abbreviation	Definition / application
Chlorophyll a	Chl-a	Significant of living biomass. Limited to the surface layer (profile not addressed).
Suspended sediment	SM / sm	Significant of pollution of other-than-biological origin.
Coloured dissolved organic matter (yellow substance, gelbstoff, gilvin)	CDOM (subscript "y")	Significant of biomass undertaking decomposition processes.
Sea Surface Temperature Water surface Temperature	SST WST	Temperature representative of the water/atmosphere interface. Remote sensed temperature may be more or less representative of the skin (most frequent case), or the bulk, or the air near to surface, depending on sea wind/roughness and on the spectral band used to perform the observation (IR or MW). Two figures are specified for accuracy (standard deviation and bias).
Bathymetry		Map of sea-bottom depths, as can be inferred from sea-surface imagery. Accuracy is specified for both height and horizontal location.
Ocean topography		Ocean topography is the map of mean sea levels. Its use for steady-state ocean circulation is associated to knowledge of the geoid.
Significant wave height		Average height of the 33 % highest waves. Sea state and roughness are not explicitly addressed but may be derived by this and others parameters of this list
Wave period and direction)		Wave spectrum is not explicitly addressed. Period and direction refer to the dominant wave (the most energetic one). Wavelength is not explicitly addressed.
Sea level		Actual, local sea level inclusive of mean sea level and perturbations (tides, etc.).
Coastal currents (speed and direction)		Surface currents only, as can be inferred from sea-surface imagery or derived from ocean surface topography. Depth of current is not addressed.
Sea surface features		Generic term reserved for observations of fractal nature (thermal fronts, eddies, internal waves, etc.) besides those explicitly listed. Accuracy is not specified. Horizontal resolution should refer to what is thought necessary to detect those features
Ocean salinity		Limited to the ocean surface layer. Accuracy is specified, according to use, as parts per thousands (ppt, or ‰).

V.2.3 Terms of optics

Abbreviation	Meaning
a, b, c	Coefficients of absorption, scattering and attenuation of light by bulk water
λ_{dom}	Wavelength of maximum reflection
K_d	Diffuse attenuation coefficient for downwelling irradiance
R	Water volume reflectance
L_u	Upwelling radiance at null depth (just beneath the surface)
L_w	Water leaving radiance just above the surface
E_d	Downwelling solar irradiance at the water surface
R_{rs}	Remote sensing reflectance – $R_{rs} = L_w / E_d$
$C_{chl}, C_{sm}, C_{det}, C_y$	Concentrations of chlorophyll, suspended minerals, detritus and coloured dissolved organic matter, respectively
P^B	Daily primary production rate
Z_{SD}	Secchi disk depth
IOPs	Inherent optical properties (absorption coefficient a , scattering coefficient b , attenuation coefficient c , volume scattering function $\beta(\theta)$)
AOPs	Apparent optical properties (Radiance, irradiance, reflectance, diffuse attenuation, etc.)
AOC	Optically-active components: Water-column constituents that interact with the incident and scattered light, and thus contribute to the signal measured by an EO sensor.

V.3 List of EO sensors

V.3.1 Spaceborne sensors

Satellite	Instrument	Acronym	Swath width	Spatial Resolution	Repeat period	Start year	End year
High resolution							
SPOT-1; 2; SPOT-3	High Res. Visible	HRV	60 km or 117 km	10m / 20m	3 days	1986	- 1995
SPOT-4	HRV and MIR	HRVIR		10m / 20m	3 days	1998	2003
SPOT-5A; 5B	High Res. Geometry	HGR		5m / 10m	3 days	2002	2007
LANDSAT-4; 5	Thematic Mapper	TM	185 km	30m / 120m	16 days	1976	-
LANDSAT-7	Enhanced TM	ETM+	705 km	15m / 30m / 60m	16 days	1999	2004
	High Res. Multispectral Stereo Imager	HRMSI			16 days		
IRS-1A; 1B; P2; 1E(P1)	Linear Imaging Self Scanning	LISS-1 & LISS-2	140 km	72.5m 30m	22 days 24 days	1988	
IRS-1C/1D	Linear Imaging Self Scanning	LISS-3	140 km	23.5m / 70.5m	24 days	1995	2001
	Panchromatic camera	PAN	70 km	5.8m	5 days (steering)		
IRS-1C/1D/P3	Wide Field Sensor	WiFS	774 km		5 days		
IRS-1E(P1)	Monocular Electro Optical Stereo Scanner	MEOSS				1999	2004
IRS P5	High Res. Panchromatic instr.	HR PAN	30 km	2.5m	26 days		
	Linear Im. Self Scan.	LISS IV	40 km	10m	22 days		
ERS-1; 2	Along Track Scanning Radiometer	ATSR	500 km	1 km (IR) 50 km (SST)	3 (4) days revisit	1991	
	Synthetic Aperture Radar	SAR	100 km	20 km (μ) 25m / 100m	3 (4) days revisit		
RADARSAT	Synthetic Aperture Radar	SAR	max. 500 km	28m / 50m / 100m	24 days (3 & 7 day subcycles)	1995	2000

Satellite	Instrument	Acronym	Swath width	Spatial Resolution	Repeat period	Start year	End year
Medium resolution							
PRIRODA (remote sens. Module, space station MIR)	IR Spec. Rad. system	ISTOK-1	FOV	0.6-2km		1995	1999
	Travers SAR		50 km	50-150m			
	TV Camera		FOV	3.3 ang. min.			
	MOS	MOS	85 km	650 m			
IRS-P3	Modular opto-electronic scanner	MOS	200 km	500	3 days	1996	onward
Low resolution							
NOAA-9; 10; 11; 12; 14; K; L; M; N; N'	Advanced very high resolution radiometer	AVHRR/2 AVHRR/3	approx. 3000 km	1.1 km	4-12 hrs	1984	2010
Orbview-2	Sea-viewing, Wide Field Sensor	SeaWiFS	1500-2800 km	1.1km / 4.4km	2 days revisit	1997	2002
GMS Program 4; 5	Visible and IR Spin-Scan Radiometer	VISSR	Full Earth disk	1.25km / 5km	Every hour	1995	2000
GOMS Program	Scanning TV Radiometer	STR			24 hours	1994	1998
GOES 7	Visible and IR Spin Scanning Radiometer	VISSR	Horizon to horizon	1km (vis.) 7 & 14km (IR)		1987	1998

Future sensors							
ENVISAT	Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer	MERIS	1150 km	300m / 1200m	3 days revisit	2000	2005
	Advanced SAR	ASAR	400 km	30m / 100m / 1km	3 days revisit		
EOS Program	Advanced Spaceborne Thermal Emission and Reflection Radiometer	ASTER	60 km	15m / 25m / 90m	16 days revisit	2000	2005
	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectro radiometer	MODIS	2300 km	250m / 1000m	>2 days		
ADEOS-II	Global Imager	GLI	1600 km	250m - 1km	4 days	1999	2002
	Polarization and Directionality of the Earth's Reflectance	POLDER	2400km	6km	1 day		
Fengyun program	Multispectral Visible and IR	MVISR					

	Scanning Radiometer						
POES series	Advanced Very High Resolution Radiometer	AVHRR/3					
MSG-1; 2; 3	Spinning Enhanced Vis and IR Imager	SEVIRI	Full Earth disk	1km / 5km	Full disk every 15 minutes	2000	2014
ALOS	Upgraded AVNIR (Advanced Vis. and NIR Radiometer)	AVNIR-2	70 km	10m			
CBERS-1; 2	High Resolution CCD Camera	HRCC	778 km		26 days	1999	2002
	IR Multispectral Scanner	IRMSS	19.5km	80m / 160m	26 days		
	Wide Field Imager	WFI	890km	258m	5 days revisit		

V.3.2 Hyperspectral airborne sensors

Abbreviation	Meaning
GER	GER image Spectrometer
CASI	compact airborne spectrographic imager: 288 bands (visible-NIR)
ROSI	reflective optics system imaging spectrometer: 105 bands (visible-NIR)
AVIRIS	advanced visible and near-infrared radiometer: 224 bands (visible-IR)
HRIS	high resolution imaging spectrometer: 65 bands (visible-NIR)
MIVIS	multispectral infrared and visible spectrometer: 20 bands (visible-NIR)
AOCI	airborne ocean color imager spectrometer: 9 bands (visible-NIR)
DAIS	Digital Airborne Spectrometer: 30(76) bands (visible-NIR)

V.4 List of algorithms

Form	Parameters	Type	Name	Sensors ¹	Water type
1	Chl	Polynomial	TM	TM	Case II
2	Chl	Band ratio	Radiance ratio	CZCS	Case I & II
3	Chl	Band ratio	CZCS –NASA	CZCS	Case I & II
4	Chl	Band ratio	Reflectance ratio	CZCS	Case I & II
5	Chl	Band ratio	Cubic polynomial	CZCS, POLDER, SeaWiFS	Case I
6	Chl	Band ratio	OC-2	SeaWiFS	Case I
7	Chl	Band ratio	OC-4	SeaWiFS	Case I
8	Chl	Band ratio	Power	OCTS, SeaWiFS	Case I
9	Chl	Band ratio	Hyperbolic/power	OCTS, SeaWiFS	Case I
10	Chl	Band ratio	Multiple regression	OCTS, SeaWiFS	Case I
11	Chl, sm, CDOM	Band ratio	Multiple regression	SeaWiFS, MOS	Case II
12	Chl	Empirical	Spectral curvature	SeaWiFS	Case I
13	Chl	Band ratio	NDPI	POLDER	Case I & II
14	Chl	Semi-analytic	Bates & Watts	SeaWiFS	Case I
15	Chl, sm, CDOM	Multivariate optim.	Two-flow approx.	CZCS, MOS	Coastal - inland
16	Chl, sm, CDOM	Non linear regression	Neural network	SeaWiFS, MOS	Coastal – inland
17	Chl, sm, CDOM	Multivariate optim.	Levenberg-Macq.	SeaWiFS, MOS	Coastal – inland
18	P ^B	Band ratio/analytic	Bedford	CZCS, SeaWiFS	Case I
19	P ^B	Band ratio/ analytic	LPCM	CZCS, SeaWiFS	Case I
20	P ^B	Band ratio/empirical	VGPM	CZCS, SeaWiFS	Case I
21	sm	Reflectance ratio	SPOT – SM	HRV	Coastal - inland
22	sm	Reflectance ratio	TM – SM	TM	Coastal- inland
23	sm	Logarithm	Unified model	TM, MSS	Coastal - inland
24	sm	Normal. band sum	MSS – SM	MSS	Case II
25	sm	Single band	AVHRR – SM	AVHRR	Case II
26	sm	Band ratio	Seston algorithm	CZCS	Case II
27	a	Semi-analytic	Lee algorithm	SeaWiFS	Case I
28	a _{dm} , b _{bp}	Semi-analytic	Garver & Siegel	SeaWiFS	Case I
29	b _b / a	Semi-analytic	Cubic polynomial	SeaWiFS	Case I & II
30	K _d	Band ratio	K(PAR)	CASI, Caesar	Inland
31	K _d	Linear regression	MSS – K _d	MSS	Case I & II
32	K _d	Band ratio	“K” algorithm	CZCS	Case I
33	K _d	Band ratio	“K” algorithm	SeaWiFS	Case I
34	Z _{SD}	Band ratio	“SD” algorithm	CASI	Inland
35	Turbidity	Band ratio	Turbidity index	MSS, TM	Inland
36	Chromaticity	Semi-analytic	CIE algorithm	SeaWiFS	Coastal - inland
37	WST	Split-window	MCSST	AVHRR	Coastal – inland
38	WST	Dual view split-win	ATSR – WST	ATSR	Coastal – inland
39	WST	Single band	-	AVHRR, TM6	Coastal – inland
40	Water depth	Semi-empirical	Bierwirth	TM	Coastal – inland
41	Topography	Spectral analysis	Hydrodynamic	SAR	Coastal
42	Topography	Correlation method	Venturi	SAR	Coastal
43	Sea level	Dynamical modelling	ISSH	Altimeter	Coastal offshore
44	Shoreline	Morphometry	Directional mask	SAR	Coastal– inland
45	Shoreline	Statistical estimation	Semi-variogram	SAR, HRV, TM	Coastal – inland

¹ Here we only indicates the sensors for which references concerning the application of the algorithm, have been found. Nevertheless, algorithms are not restricted to the sensors mentioned in the list, but can obviously be applied to similar sensors based on similar technology or presenting similar characteristics. For examples, algorithms developed for CZCS can generally be used with minor adjustment to other ocean colour sensors such as SeaWiFS, OCTS, POLDER, etc.

46	Oil slick	Image processing	Threshold analysis	SAR	Coastal – inland
Prospective					
47	Chl	Radiance ratio	MERIS – Case I	MERIS	Case I
48	Chl, SM, CDOM	Neural network	MERIS – Case II	MERIS	Case II
49	Chl, SM, CDOM	Radiance ratio	MODIS – Case I	MODIS	Case I
50	Chl	Semi-analytic	MODIS – Case II	MODIS	Case II
51	Chl & auxiliary pigments	Semi-analytic	Gaussian decomposition	Hyperspectral data	Case I
52	P, N, C	Converting factor	Constant ratio	CZCS, SeaWiFS	Case I
53	Shoreline	Classification	Textural analysis	SAR	Coastal – inland

V.5 Summary table for present and future algorithms

Remotely determinable parameters from space- /airborne sensors, and identification of appropriate retrieval algorithms/techniques.

Inland/coastal water environment parameter	Space- / airborne sensors	Retrieval algorithm/technique identification	Bibliographic references
Phytoplankton chlorophyll concentration C_{chl}	TM, ETM CZCS, OCTS, POLDER SeaWiFS, MOS-B MODIS, OCM, MERIS, GLI ROSIS, CASI, AVIRIS, HRIS, AOCI, DAIS, MIVIS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> area-specific radiance-ratio regression semi-analytical regression spectral curvature regression method of principal components multivariate optimisation technique regularisation technique simplex method neural network simulation technique 	O'Reilly et al., 1998 Tassan, 1994; Jerome et al., 1996 Sathyendranath et al., 1994; Habbane et al., 1998 Sathyendranath et al., 1994 Bukata et al., 1995 Kondratyev et al., 1990 Doerffer and Fisher, 1994 Pozdnyakov et al., 1998.
Phytoplankton diversity: auxiliary pigments concentration C_{pigm}	ROSIS, CASI, AVIRIS, HRIS, AOCI, DAIS, MIVIS	a decomposition into Gaussian bands	Hoepffner and Sathyendranath, 1993; Smith et al., 1996
Suspended minerals Concentration, C_{sm}	TM, ETM, AVHRR, MSU-M, MIVIS CZCS, OCTS, POLDER SeaWiFS, MOS-B MODIS, OCM, MERIS, GLI ROSIS, CASI, AVIRIS, HRIS, AOCI, DAIS, MIVIS	area-specific radiance-ratio regression semi-analytical regression spectral curvature regression method of principal components multivariate optimisation technique regularisation technique simplex method neural network simulation technique	O'Reilly et al., 1998 Tassan, 1994; Jerome et al., 1996 Sathyendranath et al., 1994; Habbane et al., 1998 Bukata et al., 1995 Kondratyev et al., 1990 Doerffer and Fisher, 1994 Pozdnyakov et al., 1998.
Dissolved organic matter Concentration, C_y	CZCS, OCTS, POLDER SeaWiFS, MOS-B MODIS, OCM, MERIS, GLI, ROSIS, CASI, AVIRIS, HRIS, AOCI, DAIS, MIVIS	semi-analytical regression spectral curvature regression method of principal components multivariate optimisation technique regularisation technique simplex method neural network simulation technique	Tassan, 1994; Jerome et al., 1996 Sathyendranath et al., 1994; Habbane et al., 1998 Bukata et al., 1995 Kondratyev et al., 1990 Doerffer and Fisher, 1994 Pozdnyakov et al., 1998.

